

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Federated Data Sharing and Analysis for Social Utility

Project Acronym: **HARPOCRATES**

Project Number: **101069535**

Programme: **Civil Security for Society**

Call: **Increased Cybersecurity 2021**

Call Identifier: **CL3-2021-CS-01-04**

Funding Scheme: **Research and Innovation Action**

Start date of project: 01/10/2022

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable:

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Due date of deliverable: 31.03.2025

Actual submission date: 24.06.2025

WPL: RISE

Author(s): Alfonso Iacovazzi, David Eklund, Apostolos Pyrgelis, Han Wang, Antonis Michalas, Nicolae Paladi, Tanveer Khan, Ana Kovacevic, Dejan Jovic, Stevan Jokic

Dissemination Level: PU

Version: <1.0>

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

1 Table of Contents

1	Table of Contents	2
2	Lists of Figures and Tables	4
3	Change History	6
4	Introduction	11
4.1	Privacy preserving machine learning	11
4.2	Feature selection	12
4.3	Classification	13
4.4	Federated learning	13
4.5	Contributions	15
4.6	Organisation	16
5	Privacy preserving feature selection	17
5.1	Introduction	17
5.2	Related Work	18
5.2.1	Feature Selection	18
5.2.2	Federated Feature Selection	18
5.2.3	Privacy-Preserving Feature Selection	19
5.2.4	Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning	20
5.3	Preliminaries	20
5.3.1	Feature Selection with the Filter Method	20
5.3.2	Cross Entropy and Mutual Information	21
5.3.3	Secure Multi-party Computation	21
5.4	Problem Statement	22
5.4.1	System and Threat Model	22
5.4.2	Solution Overview	23
5.5	Building Blocks for Privacy-Preserving Feature Selection with Mutual Information	23
5.5.1	Notation	23
5.5.2	A Baseline Secure Protocol for Mutual Information	24
5.5.3	Bounded Mutual Information	25
5.5.4	A More Efficient Secure Protocol for Mutual Information	27
5.5.5	Secure Feature Filtering Based on Mutual Information	29
5.6	Experimental Evaluation	29
5.6.1	Datasets	29
5.6.2	Experimental Results	30
6	Privacy preserving classification	33
6.1	Introduction	33
6.2	Background	34
6.2.1	Homomorphic Encryption	34
6.2.2	Split Learning	35
6.2.3	Function Secret Sharing	35
6.3	Public Local and Split Learning Protocols	37
6.3.1	Local model without split learning	37
6.3.2	Local model with vanilla and U-shaped Split	38
6.4	Private SL Training Protocol using HE and FSS	39

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

6.4.1	Private SL Training Protocol using HE	40
6.4.2	Performance Analysis	43
6.5	Private SL training protocol using FSS	46
6.5.1	Threat Model & Security Analysis	48
6.5.2	Performance Analysis	52
6.5.3	Evaluation	53
6.6	Privacy-preserving Video and Audio Classification	56
7	Privacy preserving federated learning	57
7.1	Privacy-preserving federated learning with secure aggregation	57
7.1.1	Homomorphic Encryption	58
7.1.2	Flashe: A practical symmetric additive HE scheme	59
7.1.3	Quantization Method	60
7.1.4	The Challenge of Weighted Averaging	60
7.1.5	Threat Model	60
7.1.6	Heflp	62
7.1.7	MWAvg with M-prime	64
7.1.8	MWAvg with Flashev2	64
7.1.9	Implementation	66
7.1.10	Secure Aggregation Process	67
7.1.11	Evaluation	69
7.1.12	Conclusion	72
7.2	Federated learning with homomorphic encryption	73
7.2.1	Proposed Solution	73
7.2.2	Threat Model	73
7.2.3	Architecture System and Components	73
7.2.4	Workflow Execution	76
7.2.5	Conclusion	77
7.3	Privacy-Preserving Hyperparameter Tuning for Federated Learning	78
7.3.1	Introduction	78
7.3.2	Related Work	80
7.3.3	Problem Statement & Solution Roadmap	81
7.3.4	Evaluating Single-shot HP Tuning Strategies for Federated Learning	83
7.3.5	Towards Privacy-Preserving Hyperparameter Tuning for Federated Learning	89
7.4	Federated learning with DP-based data synthetization and weight tuning	96
7.4.1	Introduction	96
7.4.2	DP-Synthesizer	97
7.4.3	Weight Tuning for FL	101
7.4.4	Conclusion	105
8	Conclusion	107

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

2 Lists of Figures and Tables

Figures

1	Different Split Learning Configurations	36
2	Function secret sharing	37
3	Local model without split learning	38
4	Local model with vanilla split learning	39
5	Socket Initialization	41
6	Forward and Backward Propagation	42
7	Utilizing FSS between two servers	47
8	Visual invertibility inference attack: First row shows the original images (image size: 28×28) from the MNIST dataset. Second row shows the AT_m after the first Conv2D layer before the first max-pooling operation (image size: 24×24). Third row displays the AT_m after the second Conv2D layer before the second max-pooling operation (image size: 8×8).	50
9	Visual invertibility inference attack with FSS applied: First row shows the original AT_m after the first Conv2D (before the max-pooling operations) from the MNIST dataset. Second row shows what P_0 receives when the FSS protocol is applied. Third row what P_1 receives when the FSS protocol is applied. (a) Image Size: 24×24 ; (b) Image Size: 8×8	53
10	FL Process	57
11	Example Flashe usage	59
12	An example of Flashev2	62
13	MAE comparison	63
14	System overview	66
15	Federated Training process with Homomorphic Encryption	67
16	Two numerical solutions	69
17	Results of the time efficiency test when the weights of clients are in the range [1000, 5000]. Fv2+ denotes Flashev2+MWAvg without M-prime.	70
18	Results of the time efficiency test for three models: FCN (49.7k parameters), LSTM (215.2k parameters), and MobileNet (2.13M parameters).	71
19	Two numerical solutions	72
20	Node architecture	74
21	Server architecture	75
22	Sequence diagram of the HE-enhanced FL workflow	76
23	Our HP tuning method for cross-silo FL. hp_k and hp_g denote the local best HP configuration at client k and the global best configuration (denoted by g), respectively.	79
24	Barplots of learning rate, momentum, and accuracy for the iid setting with Mean as the Combine(\cdot) strategy, on various datasets and experiments. The ground truth (GHO result) is indicated by black dots. The remaining bar colors represent the results of combining the clients' optimal HPs with the Mean Combine(\cdot) strategy, for a variable number of clients (N).	86
25	Barplots of learning rate and momentum for the non-iid setting with $N = 20$ clients, variable datasets and Combine(\cdot) strategies. The top-row results are for feature skew ($\beta_f = 0.02$), middle-row results for label skew ($\beta_\ell = 1.0$), and bottom-row results are for quantity skew ($\beta_q = 0.4$). Bar colors represent the HPs derived using various combination strategies.	87

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

26	Comparison of the various combination strategies proposed in FLoRA [1] vs. the density-based clustering (DBSCAN) strategy identified in our measurement study. The blue bar indicates the federated grid search results as ground truth. Each plot represents a different skew type (averaged across skew parameters with 10 and 20 clients).	88
27	Proposed Framework	97
28	AE-(dp)MERF architecture	99

Tables

1	Deliverable Change History	6
2	List of abbreviations and acronyms	8
3	Base vs. BMI : Number of multiplications and additions per feature.	28
4	Characteristics of the employed datasets.	30
5	Classification accuracy and regression error (iid case).	31
6	Classification accuracy and selected features (non-iid case).	31
7	Base vs. BMI : Computation time (ms) for passive and active adversaries and # of multiplications required.	32
8	Training results of HESplit network on the MIT-BIH abd PTB-XL dataset using different sets of HE parameters and batch sizes. The training duration (in sec) and communication (in Gb) overhead are reported as the average value per epoch	45
9	Performance comparison: training and testing results for various privacy-preserving models	55
10	Results of the communication overhead test for three models.	71
11	HP grids for LHO and GHO.	85
12	Microbenchmarks with $N=10$ clients, $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$.	94
13	Microbenchmarks with $N=20$ clients, $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$.	94
14	Summary of anomaly detection performance	101
15	BAs on defenses with 10 clients (1 adv.) and 20 clients (3 adv.)	105

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

3 Change History

Version	Date	Pages	Author	Modification
0.1	20.03.2024	10	TUNI	Template made
0.2	20.09.2024	10	RISE	Template updated
0.3	30.05.2025	128	RISE, TUNI, CBIT, ZEN	Added all technical content
0.4	12.06.2025	128	RISE, TUNI	Completed internal review
1.0	23.06.2025	128	RISE	Finalized editing and ready for submission

Table 1 – Deliverable Change History

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

List of abbreviations and acronyms

WP	Work Package
ML	Machine Learning
PPML	Privacy Preserving ML
SP	Split Learning
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
MHE	Multi-party HE
FSS	Function Secret Sharing
MPC	Multi-Party Computation
SMPC	Secure MPC
FL	Federated Learning
HFL	Horizontal FL
VFL	Vertical FL
DP	Differential Privacy
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
PPFS	Privacy Preserving Feature Selection
MLaaS	ML as a Service
MI	Mutual Information
NN	Neural Network
CNN	Convolutional NN
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
FCN	Fully Convolutional Network
ECG	Electrocardiography
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
FSHA	Feature-Space Hijacking Attack
BA	Byzantine Attack
VM	Virtual Machine
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MSE	Mean Squared Error

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

RMSE	Root MSE
HP	hyperparameter
HPO	HP optimization
LHO	Local HPO
GHO	Global HPO
PET	Privacy-Enhancing Technology
NAS	Neural Architecture Search
MNIST	Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology
EMNIST	Extended MNIST
SVHN	Street View House Numbers
iid	independent and identically distributed
SGM	Single global model
SGM+U	SGM with Uncertainty
MPLM	Maximum of per-party local models
APLM	Average of per-party local models
CKKS	Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song
RLWE	Ring Learning with Errors
PF-Mean	Private Federated Mean
PF-DBSCAN	Private Federated DBSCAN
SIMD	Single Instruction, Multiple Data
MIA	Membership Inference Attack
AE	Autoencoder
MMD	Maximum Mean Discrepancy
ACC	Adaptive Cruise Control
FNR	False Negative Rate
FPR	False Positive Rate
AUC	Area Under Curve
IDS	Intrusion Detection System

Table 2 – List of abbreviations and acronyms

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Disclaimer

This deliverable may be subject to final acceptance by the European Commission. The results of these deliverables reflect only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Statement for open documents & Copyrights

This document is property of the HARPOCRATES Consortium. The content of all or parts of these documents can be used and distributed provided that the HARPOCRATES project and the document are properly referenced.

The HARPOCRATES consortium is keen on ensuring that all information in this document is correct and fairly stated but does not accept liability for any errors or omissions.

To the best of our knowledge, all third-party literary (articles/studies/reports/etc. or excerpts thereof) or artistic (photos/graphs/drawings/etc.) used to support this document are correctly cited and acknowledged. If the reader should find something not compliant, an additional courtesy acknowledgement or correction can be made to this version thereof.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Executive Summary

The HARPOCRATES project aims to develop solutions for private and secure data analysis and sharing. As such, this deliverable (D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning) covers the outcomes of our research conducted in Work Package 2 (WP2). In particular, WP2 has explored and developed advanced privacy-preserving machine learning techniques to address one of today's most pressing challenges in data science: how to learn from data without exposing it. In an era where AI systems depend on massive volumes of personal and often sensitive data, safeguarding privacy during machine learning tasks is critical – especially in domains such as healthcare, cyber threat intelligence, etc.

This deliverable focuses on three key areas: feature selection, classification, and federated learning — each enhanced with novel privacy-preserving approaches that improve efficiency, scalability, and data protection.

In feature selection, we introduce a lightweight, secure protocol using multi-party computation. Our method significantly reduces the complexity of mutual information estimation, enabling over 1,000× speed-up in regression tasks while maintaining model performance. This makes privacy-friendly data preparation both practical and fast.

For classification tasks in distributed environments, we address the risks associated with split learning, where a client and server train a model together without sharing raw data. Although split learning helps distribute computation, it still leaks sensitive intermediate information. We designed two secure split learning protocols using homomorphic encryption and function secret sharing, ensuring that intermediate outputs remain protected — even from untrusted servers.

In the field of federated learning, we advance the state-of-the-art in privacy-preserving federated setups. We optimized existing homomorphic encryption schemes such as Flashe, and proposed a new version — Flashev2 — for better support of encrypted training.

We also tackled the overlooked problem of secure hyperparameter tuning in federated learning. Our new framework, PRIVTUNA, enables collaborative tuning using multiparty homomorphic encryption, achieving high accuracy and efficiency without privacy loss.

Additionally, we explore the use of differentially private synthetic data for time series anomaly detection. Our findings suggest that adding differential privacy to the data generation process can maintain strong utility, even outperforming some non-private synthetic data.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

4 Introduction

Privacy is no longer just a technical issue, it is also a societal demand. As machine learning (ML) systems become more common and powerful, they also need access to more data. But this data is often sensitive: medical records, personal behaviors, etc. In this context, the HARPOCRATES project investigates how to build ML systems that can learn from data without actually sharing or seeing it. This is the key idea behind privacy-preserving ML (PPML).

In this section, we give an overview of the core concepts behind PPML, which will help to understand how HARPOCRATES contributes to three major areas in this space: feature selection, classification, and federated learning (FL). Each of these areas presents different privacy challenges, and our goal has been to design efficient, practical, and secure solutions for them.

4.1 Privacy preserving machine learning

PPML is a way to train ML models while protecting the sensitive data used in the process. In simple words, it tries to keep personal or private information safe, even while computers learn from it. This is very important today, as data from users (like health records, messages, or location) are often used to train powerful AI systems.

There are two common ways ML happens: (i) centralized learning and (ii) distributed learning. In centralized learning, all the data is collected and stored in one place (like a company's server). This can be risky because if someone hacks the server, all the private data can be exposed. In distributed learning, the data stays on users' devices. A popular version of this is FL. Here, the model is trained on devices like phones or computers, and only the learning updates (not the data) are sent back to a central server.

Several technologies are used to protect privacy in both centralized and distributed settings.

- Differential Privacy (DP): Adds noise to the data or model updates, making it hard to tell if any person's data was used. Companies like Apple and Google use this.
- Homomorphic Encryption (HE): Allows computations on encrypted data. The server never sees the raw data. It's still slow for large models but improving.
- Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC): Data is split among parties, and they compute together without revealing their part to others.
- Trusted Execution Environments (TEE): Hardware-based security (like Intel SGX) to keep data safe during computation.
- FL: Trains models across many devices without moving the data to a central server.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Even with these technologies, PPML still faces big challenges. One of the main issues is the performance versus privacy trade-off. When we add privacy protections like noise or encryption, models often lose some accuracy or become slower. This is a difficult balance to manage, especially in real-world applications.

Another problem is scalability. Some privacy methods, such as SMPC or HE, are still too slow or resource-heavy for large-scale systems. This makes it hard to use them in production for big models or large datasets. Robustness to attacks is also a concern. Even with privacy tools in place, models can be attacked using techniques like member inference attack, where attackers try to infer original data samples used to train a model, or poisoning, where fake data is added to harm the training process. A further challenge is personalization. We want models to give useful results for individual users, but it's hard to do this well without risking private data being exposed.

Lastly, there is a lack of regulation and standards as many countries and companies have different rules, and there is no global agreement on how to apply PPML. This makes it difficult to compare systems or ensure that they meet ethical and legal expectations.

Recently, big interest from industries and governments, especially with laws like the EU's AI Act and GDPR, is pushing research in this area forward. But it's still a long journey before PPML becomes easy and common for everyone.

4.2 Feature selection

Feature selection is one of the most important first steps when working with ML. It helps reduce the number of features (or variables) in a dataset by keeping only the ones that are most useful for the task. This makes the model easier to train, faster to run, and often more accurate in the end [2]. By removing features that are not needed or are too similar to others, feature selection helps make the model simpler and easier to understand. It also saves computing power and time, which is important when working with large datasets. This process becomes even more important today as we need to work with more and more sensitive data often distributed. In fields like [3] and finance [4], data is often stored in separate places that cannot easily be combined because of privacy rules. For example, two hospitals may each have different medical records for the same patient, but they are not allowed to share the full data. This creates a big question: how can we find the most useful features for ML when the data is spread out and private? To solve this, researchers are working on new methods that allow feature selection without needing to move or share the raw data. These methods include privacy-preserving tools like FL and secure multiparty computation [5].

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

4.3 Classification

ML classification is a widely used technique in which a model is trained to classify input data into predefined classes [6]. Training these models requires access to large datasets, which raises privacy concerns, especially in ML as a Service (MLaaS) scenarios. When ML models are trained on a Cloud Service Provider (CSP), users data are exposed to external servers, raising privacy concerns about data privacy and security – particularly in sensitive domains like healthcare and finance.

To address these concerns, collaborative learning techniques such as Split Learning (SL) [7] have been introduced. In SL, the ML model is split between client (who owns the data) and a server (which performs heavy computations). The client processes the first few layers of the model, while the remaining layers – typically the computationally expensive ones – are executed on the server. This approach reduces the computational burden on the client and allows collaborative training without directly sharing raw data.

Despite its advantages, SL presents significant privacy risks. Since the client sends intermediate output to the server, a malicious server could attempt to reconstruct raw input data from the shared intermediate output [8]. Thus, while SL improves data distribution and computational efficiency, it still requires strong privacy measures to prevent data leakage. To mitigate these risks, we incorporate privacy-preserving techniques such as HE [9] and Function Secret Sharing (FSS) [10, 11] into SL. These techniques enable privacy-preserving computations, ensuring that data remain encrypted throughout the training process. Based on these techniques, we designed two privacy-preserving SL protocols, which we will discuss in detail in [section 6](#):

- **Private SL training using HE:** In this protocol, the computation is performed on a single server using HE. The client encrypts the activation map before sending it to the server. The server performs computations on encrypted data but cannot decrypt or access the raw data [12].
- **Private SL training using FSS:** In this protocol, the server-side part of the model is split across two servers using FSS. Each server receives a masked version of the intermediate output and performs computations independently. Since neither server has full access to the data, privacy is preserved [13].

4.4 Federated learning

FL is a variant of the ML approach that allows multiple clients to collaborate on training a more capable global model without sharing training data with each other or the central server. This means that the data remains on local devices and the global model is trained in a decentralized

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

manner by only sharing intermediate results [14]. FL has the ability to train global models on decentralized data and retain data privacy and security at the same time. Since training data is kept locally, sensitive raw data, such as medical records or personal private information, could be protected from exposure. Another advantage of FL is that it can help reduce communication overhead by completing parts of training locally and only transmitting model parameters or gradients instead of raw data. FL is particularly suitable for scenarios where distributed training data is sensitive or too large to be sent to the central server [15]. There are also several types of FL, according to how data is distributed and how the collaboration is conducted [15, 16, 17], described as follows.

Horizontal FL (HFL) is the most common approach for the case where the data samples in different parties have similar features but different indices [14, 18]. In HFL all the participants are likely to share common characteristics in terms of data models and use cases. For example, multiple hospitals collaborate to train one global model for detecting a particular medical condition. In this case, the images from different hospitals have the same features but belong to different patients.

Vertical FL (VFL) takes the case that the data samples from different parties have different features but similar indices [19], i.e. from the same group of people.

Federated Transfer Learning (FTL) is designed for more complicated scenarios where data samples of different parties have different features and different indices as well [20]. FTL handles the demand that different parties need to leverage reinforcement learning to learn from their own actions and environment rewards [21, 22].

Considering HFL, each iteration of the training process is divided into 3 steps [23]. First, all the participants fetch the current global model from the central server and prepare a local dataset to initialize local training. In this step, all the participants have the same initial model but different training datasets and the ML algorithm for local training is decided. Second, local training is performed on each party's dataset to refine the model using the decided algorithm. In this step, each participant trains the model to adjust to their own data. Third, all the participants send the refined models back to the central server for global aggregation. The server uses a specific FL algorithm to aggregate the parameters of all participants' models and update the global model. Then the updated model is sent back to each participant to trigger the next iteration until the global model converges.

FL is a promising technique in many applications areas, such as image recognition [24], health-care [25, 16] or autonomous vehicles [15].

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Although FL was created to improve privacy by keeping user data on personal devices, many studies have now shown that this method still has serious privacy risks. Even without direct access to the raw data, attackers can analyze the model updates shared with the server and reconstruct private information, like typed messages, health data, or location patterns. These privacy leaks have been widely demonstrated.

4.5 Contributions

The core contributions covered in this document can be summarized as follows:

- C1. Privacy-Preserving Feature Selection:** We introduce a novel protocol for secure mutual information (MI) estimation using Multi-Party Computation (MPC). This method significantly reduces computational complexity from $O(NM)$ to $O(N)$, enabling scalable and fast feature selection for regression tasks. Our experimental results show a speed-up of over 1,000 \times compared to direct MPC implementations, with no loss in predictive performance.
- C2. Secure Split Learning for Classification:** We propose two privacy-enhanced SL frameworks to prevent leakage of raw or intermediate data from clients to servers. The first uses HE to perform encrypted computations on the server side. The second uses FSS to distribute model processing across two non-colluding servers. Both approaches ensure that client data remains private during model training.
- C3. Optimized Encryption for Federated Training:** We enhance the Flashe HE scheme, introducing Flashev2, which supports secure, privacy-preserving aggregation of model parameters while maintaining efficiency. Our improvements include novel mechanisms for protecting client-specific data within the encrypted computation process.
- C4. Containerized FL Architecture with Encrypted Aggregation:** We design a secure and modular FL system that integrates HE (CKKS scheme) into a containerized workflow using the Vantage6 infrastructure.
- C5. PRIVTUNA Framework for Secure Hyperparameter Tuning:** We propose PRIVTUNA, a new framework for privacy-preserving hyperparameter (HP) tuning in FL. It uses multiparty HE to aggregate and analyze local tuning results securely, preserving client privacy while enabling accurate global parameter selection, even in non-independent and identically distributed (non-iid) data settings.
- C6. Differentially Private Synthetic Data for Secure and Robust FL:** We introduce a comprehensive framework that combines synthetic data generation with DP to enhance client-side data protection and robustness in FL. At its core is the DP-Synthesizer, a client-side module that enables local training on differentially private synthetic data, shielding sensitive information from potentially curious or semi-honest servers. To guard against Byzantine attacks (BAs), we also propose a weight tuner on the aggregator side that dynamically ad-

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

justs the influence of client updates, reducing the impact of malicious behavior. Together, these modules support privacy-preserving and resilient FL in adversarial environments.

4.6 Organisation

This deliverable is structured to reflect the main technical focus areas of Work Package 2 in HARPOCRATES project. Following the introduction, Section 5 presents our work on privacy-preserving feature selection (PPFS), outlining the proposed methodology and performance results. Section 6 addresses privacy-preserving classification, with a focus on secure SL protocols. Section 7 is dedicated to privacy-preserving FL (PPFL) and is divided into several subsections, each covering a specific contribution: optimized HE for model aggregation, secure HP tuning with PRIVTUNA, containerized FL architecture with encrypted communication, and differentially private synthetic data for secure and robust training. Finally, Section 8 concludes the document by summarizing the key outcomes and highlighting future directions.

5 Privacy preserving feature selection

5.1 Introduction

Feature selection is a crucial preparatory data process for ML as it reduces the dimension of the ambient data space and retains the most suitable features for the downstream ML algorithm [2]. With the increased availability of sensitive data in multiple silos and the emergence of collaborative ML solutions, e.g., in the medical [3] and financial [4] sectors, there is an imperative need for enabling feature selection on distributed datasets used for ML purposes while preserving the privacy of the data [5].

Prior solutions for feature selection on distributed datasets provide limited privacy protection as they rely on data holders to share the plain results of statistics or intermediate computations on their data to a coordinating server [26, 27, 28]. On the other hand, earlier works on PPML focus primarily on model training and inference [29, 30, 31], and they do not consider feature selection or other data preparation steps, which aim to improve the performance and accuracy of the downstream ML task.

In this section we address this gap by contributing novel methods to the research of PPFS using SMPC [5, 32, 33]. We focus on feature selection with the feature filtering method which we instantiate with MI. We employ a federated approach that leverages on local computations by the data holders and we combine it with MPC to protect the end-to-end privacy of the feature selection process. To efficiently compute MI in MPC, we derive an upper bound based on the concavity of entropy and cross-entropy (Proposition 1), which exploits the similarities between the client distributions and the aggregate global distribution. Assuming a discrete feature with N possible values and a discrete label with M possible values, the upper bound requires $O(N)$ multiplications and it avoids logarithm computations which are expensive to realize in MPC; whereas, a straightforward MPC implementation of MI results in $O(NM)$ multiplications (Section 5.5.4).

We implement our protocol in the MP-SPDZ library and we experimentally evaluate it on multiple datasets and ML tasks (Section 5.6.2). Our results show that for regression tasks, our protocol results in a $1,000\times$ computation speed up with retained model accuracy for the feature selection process compared to a direct MPC implementation of MI. Similar improvements are achieved in terms of communication as the communication cost of the base MPC protocols employed is linear in the number of multiplications [34].

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

5.2 Related Work

We first discuss traditional feature selection methods (Section 5.2.1) and federated feature selection approaches (Section 5.2.2). Then, in Section 5.2.3, we examine the state-of-the-art on PPFS, and finally, we review PPML techniques (Section 5.2.4)

5.2.1 Feature Selection

In a ML pipeline, feature selection refers to the process of selecting a subset of the input variables to train an optimized model for a downstream task [2]. Common approaches for feature selection are: (i) filter methods which rank features based on statistics [35, 36, 37], (ii) wrapper methods which evaluate features based on model performance [38, 39, 40], (iii) embedded methods which integrate model training and feature selection [41, 42, 43], and (iv) unsupervised techniques which find hidden structure in the data using, e.g., similarity [44] or clustering [45]. We refer to [46, 47, 48] for exhaustive surveys on feature selection, and we note that these methods are envisioned for centralized data settings without privacy considerations, i.e., with full access to the dataset.

5.2.2 Federated Feature Selection

These works perform feature selection on datasets that are distributed among multiple entities (data holders). They work as follows: (a) each data holder identifies the most relevant features on its own part of the dataset, and (b) a (coordinator) server combines the local feature sets to derive the important features for the global dataset. Yao et al. [26] propose a feature fusion method based on convolutions and weight learning that reduces the high communication costs of FL. However, their technique is only suitable for image datasets. Banerjee et al. [27] present an information-theoretic approach based on feature-feature and feature-class MI. Hu et al. [49] propose a federated evolutionary feature selection method based on particle swarm optimization (PSO), and Fu et al. [28] propose FEAST, a feature selection method for VFL based on conditional MI.

Other works tackle the federated feature selection problem for specific use-cases. Qin and Kondo [50] employ a greedy algorithm that selects the best features for intrusion detection by evaluating the model accuracy over multiple feature subsets. Cassara et al. [51] propose a federated feature selection method for autonomous vehicles (AVs): Each AV executes local feature selection and generates a probability distribution of the information in features. Then, the edge server derives the global feature rank with a Bayesian-based aggregation approach. Finally, Zhang et al. [52] propose a federated feature selection method for Internet of Things (IoT) networks. Each IoT device executes a 1-class support vector machine algorithm and

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

eliminates irrelevant features via hierarchical clustering; then, the edge server computes the intersection of the local feature sets and yields the global feature set. While these works employ a federated approach to feature selection, they provide limited privacy protection as they rely on each data holder sharing intermediate results computed on their (sensitive) datasets (e.g., local feature scores, sets, etc.) with the coordinator server.

5.2.3 Privacy-Preserving Feature Selection

These solutions protect data privacy while performing the feature selection process. Jafer et al. [53] introduce a metric that estimates the private information in a feature and its utility for a downstream classification task and is used to filter out features. However, they assume a trusted party that performs the feature selection. Alishahi and Moghtadaiee [54] evaluate the effects of anonymization on feature selection methods that use Pearson correlation and information gain. Alishahi et al. [55] model the estimation of statistics for feature selection as frequency estimation problems and employ local DP to protect data privacy. Overall, anonymization techniques significantly degrade the utility of the feature selection process [54, 55], thus raising the need for accurate solutions.

Other works employ SMPC techniques that perform accurate feature selection without needing trusted parties. Banerjee and Chakravarty [56] design a secure aggregation protocol for feature selection based on virtual dimensionality reduction. Similarly, Sheiksalishahi and Martinelli [57] use secure aggregation to estimate the utility (feature score) and privacy (degree of uncertainty) of each feature in a distributed dataset. Rao et al. [58] employ 2PC to estimate the χ^2 statistic of binary features. But, as these works rely solely on secure aggregation, they leak statistical (aggregate) information about the input data. To this end, Li et al. [5] implement an end-to-end MPC protocol that reveals neither the feature values nor the feature sets to the computing parties. Similarly, Ono et al. [32] implement a consistency-based feature selection method using HE, and Akavia et al. [33] employ 2PC for recursive feature elimination with sparse linear regression under the L0 constraint. Similar to these works, we design an MPC protocol for feature selection without leaking information in the process. However, we employ a federated approach to improve the efficiency of MPC and focus on different feature selection method; we implement a filter method based on MI and contribute efficient approximations to realize it under MPC.

Another line of research combines federated feature selection techniques with MPC to enhance the privacy of the former and the performance of the latter. Dankar et al. [59] employ a distributed statistical learning approach: Each data holder locally computes its feature selection vector and these vectors are aggregated with a secure median protocol. Zhang et al. [60] propose MPC protocols for estimating the Gini impurity of features in VFL. In the same setting, Li

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

et al. [61] perform feature filtering with partial HE: Each data holder employs Gaussian stochastic dual-gates to approximate the Gini impurity of each feature, and the feature importance is updated while the federated training continues. Finally, Froelicher et al. [62] employ a federated approach to perform principal component analysis over a distributed dataset and they employ MPC to secure any information exchanged in the process. Similar to these works, we employ a federated approach to feature selection and we use MPC to enhance its privacy. However, our focus is on MI-based feature filtering for distributed datasets.

5.2.4 Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning

These works protect the privacy of sensitive data used for ML by incorporating privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) in the training process. Examples of such solutions employ SMPC [63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 29, 69, 70, 30, 71, 72], HE [73, 74, 75, 76], or hybrid MPC/HE approaches [77, 31, 78]. While these works pave the way for PPML, they do not consider feature selection (or any other pre-processing steps) that data analysts perform on datasets to improve the performance and accuracy of the downstream ML task.

5.3 Preliminaries

We provide background information for relevant concepts that are used in this work.

5.3.1 Feature Selection with the Filter Method

We consider the simplest form of feature selection, namely, filter methods which compute a lightweight statistic and use it to score the features one-by-one; the best features are selected based on a given threshold $\theta \in \mathbf{R}$. Commonly used statistics are variance, Pearson correlation coefficients, MI, and Relief [46, 47]. The most appropriate statistic for feature selection depends on the dataset and the available computational resources. In this work, we focus on MI, which measures the degree of independence between the feature and the target and which has superior performance compared to variance and correlation, as the following example shows.

Consider mutually independent random variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_m for $m > 2$ uniformly distributed on $[-1, 1]$ and $Y = X_1 X_2$. Then, the variance of X_i is the same for all i and the covariance of X_i and Y is zero for all i . This means that feature selection methods based on variance or correlation coefficient cannot distinguish between the features. However, the MI of X_i and Y is zero for $i > 2$ and non-zero for $i \in \{1, 2\}$.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

5.3.2 Cross Entropy and Mutual Information

Let x and y be discrete random variables with finite ranges of size N and M , respectively. For $1 \leq i \leq N$ and $1 \leq j \leq M$, let $p_i(x)$ be the probability that $x = i$, $p_j(y)$ the probability that $y = j$, and $p_{i,j}(x, y)$ the joint probability that $x = i$ and $y = j$. Let $p(x) = (p_1(x), \dots, p_N(x))$ and $p(y) = (p_1(y), \dots, p_M(y))$ denote the distributions of x and y , and $p(x, y)$ their joint distribution.

The entropy of x is defined by $H(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N -p_i(x) \log p_i(x)$, where \log denotes the natural logarithm and terms with $p_i(x) = 0$ are skipped. If $N = M$, the difference between $p(x)$ and $p(y)$ can be measured by their Kullback-Leibler divergence (KL-divergence):

$$D_{\text{KL}}(p(x), p(y)) = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i(x) \log \frac{p_i(x)}{p_i(y)},$$

skipping terms with $p_i(x) = 0$ and assuming that $p_i(x) = 0$ whenever $p_i(y) = 0$. If $p_i(y) = 0$ but $p_i(x) \neq 0$ for some i , the KL-divergence is defined to be infinite. The divergence is non-negative or infinite and zero if and only if $p(x) = p(y)$. We use the notation $D_{\text{KL}}(x, y) = D_{\text{KL}}(p(x), p(y))$. Still assuming that $N = M$, the cross-entropy between x and y is:

$$C(x, y) = H(x) + D_{\text{KL}}(x, y) = - \sum_{i=1}^N p_i(x) \log p_i(y).$$

Let $p(x) \otimes p(y)$ denote the product distribution of $p(x)$ and $p(y)$. The MI of x and y is defined by

$$I(x, y) = D_{\text{KL}}(p(x, y), p(x) \otimes p(y)) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M p_{i,j}(x, y) \log \frac{p_{i,j}(x, y)}{p_i(x)p_j(y)}.$$

The MI is non-negative or infinite and zero if and only if x and y are independent. The MI can be expressed as $I(x, y) = H(x) + H(y) - H(x, y)$, where $H(x, y)$ is the entropy of the joint variable (x, y) .

5.3.3 Secure Multi-party Computation

SMPC protocols enable a set of parties to jointly perform the computation of a desired function (a circuit) on their private inputs without disclosing them [79]. Since the seminal work of Yao [80], researchers have designed multiple MPC protocols with variable techniques, e.g., garbled circuits [80] and secret sharing [81], variable number of parties and circuit support, and different system and threat models, e.g., honest vs. dishonest majority with passive and active adversaries [82, 79]. As a result, there exist multiple public implementations of MPC [83, 84, 85, 86], and it has found application to various domains such as electronic vot-

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

ing [87], medical studies [88], financial trading [89] and fraud detection [90, 4], and ML [66, 30].

In this work, we employ the 2-out-of-3 replication secret sharing scheme proposed by Araki et al. [34] which enables 3-party computation of arithmetic circuits over the ring modulo 2^n for the honest majority passive and active adversarial settings. A secret value $x \in \mathbb{Z}_q$, where $q = 2^n$, is split into three shares x_1, x_2 and x_3 such that $x = x_1 + x_2 + x_3$ and shared among 3 parties P_1, P_2 and P_3 as follows: P_1 receives x_1 and x_2 , P_2 receives x_2 and x_3 , and P_3 receives x_3 and x_1 . This sharing scheme enables each party P_i to compute the addition z of two secret-shared values x and y as $z_i = x_i + y_i$ and $z_{i+1 \bmod 3} = x_{i+1 \bmod 3} + y_{i+1 \bmod 3}$. Moreover, the multiplication z' of two secret-shared values x and y as $z' = z'_1 + z'_2 + z'_3 = x \cdot y \bmod q = (x_1 + x_2 + x_3) \cdot (y_1 + y_2 + y_3)$ is computed as follows: P_1 computes $z'_1 = x_1 \cdot y_1 + x_1 \cdot y_2 + x_2 \cdot y_1$, P_2 computes $z'_2 = x_2 \cdot y_2 + x_2 \cdot y_3 + x_3 \cdot y_2$, and P_3 computes $z'_3 = x_3 \cdot y_3 + x_3 \cdot y_1 + x_1 \cdot y_3$, and the parties convert their additive share of z' to a replicated secret sharing representation by exchanging a randomized version of their shares [34]. Note that with additions and multiplication over secret-shared values, we can realize more complex operations such as comparison and division by employing the integer truncation protocols proposed in [91, 92].

5.4 Problem Statement

We describe the assumed system and threat model (Section 5.4.1) and we provide an overview of our solution (Section 5.4.2).

5.4.1 System and Threat Model

We consider a setting where multiple data holders (e.g., hospitals, companies) desire to collaboratively train a ML model on their sensitive data, hence, they employ a set of computing parties to execute a secure computation protocol towards this goal, e.g., [29, 30, 31]. To ensure the generalization of the global model and improve the computation and communication efficiency of the secure model training process, the data holders wish to collectively filter out irrelevant features from the global dataset in a pre-processing step. However, this pre-processing step should not reveal any information about the sensitive data of each data holder as this would invalidate the privacy protection of the ML pipeline. We assume that the global dataset is horizontally partitioned among k data holders and the number of computing parties is three. The data holders have computing power and network connectivity capabilities, hence, they can perform computations on their local datasets and share intermediate results with the computing servers. We assume that there exist secure communication channels between the data holders and the computing servers, and among the computing servers.

The data holders are honest, and they provide legitimate input for the computation. We assume

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

that the majority of the computing parties are honest-but-curious, i.e., they follow the protocol instructions and do not collude with each other; however, they are curious and attempt to learn as much information as possible for the datasets of the data holders by observing the information they process. We consider both the passive and active adversarial setting for the dishonest party.

5.4.2 Solution Overview

To realize feature filtering on the global dataset in a privacy-preserving manner, our solution relies on a hybrid approach that complements a federated feature selection process with SMPC. Our solution leverages the fact that the data holders can perform local computation and protect the information shared to perform feature selection with a secure computation protocol executed among the computing parties. Each data holder computes statistics on their local (cleartext) data and secret-shares their results among the computing servers which estimate global statistics by executing a SMPC. We instantiate our solution with a feature filtering method based on MI (Section 5.5): First, we design a baseline secure computation protocol to filter features by estimating their exact MI scores (Section 5.5.2) and analyze its computation/communication complexity. Then, we study the mathematical properties of MI and derive an upper bound (Section 5.5.3); this allows us to design an optimized version of our protocol for *approximate* privacy-preserving feature filtering based on MI (Section 5.5.4). We experimentally evaluate our protocols on synthetic and real-world datasets (Section 5.6), and we demonstrate that our optimized solution improves the efficiency of black-box SMPC while retaining the accuracy of the global model.

5.5 Building Blocks for Privacy-Preserving Feature Selection with Mutual Information

We present secure protocols for PPFs based on MI. We start by introducing the relevant notation (Section 5.5.1) and a baseline protocol for accurately estimating MI in MPC (Section 5.5.2). Then, we derive an upper bound on MI (Section 5.5.3) which we use to design a more efficient protocol for its estimation in MPC (Section 5.5.4). Finally, we conclude with a protocol for computing the mask of selected features under MPC (Section 5.5.5).

5.5.1 Notation

We consider a feature x and target variable y with finite ranges of size N and M , respectively. The data is horizontally distributed among k data holders (or clients). For $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, n_j denotes the number of samples at client j , $n = \sum_j n_j$ is the total number of samples, and

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

$\lambda_j = n_j/n$ is the weight of client j . We assume that n is publicly known by the data holders and that the same holds for a cutoff parameter $0 < \epsilon \leq \min_j(e^{-1/\lambda_j})$. Moreover, x_j and y_j denote the local feature and target variables. Then, (x, y) follows a mixture distribution of (x_j, y_j) with weights λ_j .

We use the notation z for a secret-shared fix-point number z . We denote addition, subtraction, and multiplication of secret-shared values by $z + w$, $z - w$, and zw , respectively. We represent multiplication by a constant c as cz and $-z$ is shorthand for $(-1)z$. Consequently, $z + w = z + w$, $zw = zw$, $z - w = z - w$, and $cz = cz$. Finally, we use $\sum_i z_i$ to denote the sum $z_1 + \dots + z_k$ of secret-shared values z_1, \dots, z_k .

5.5.2 A Baseline Secure Protocol for Mutual Information

We first design a baseline protocol for computing MI in the setting described in Section 5.4.1. Algorithm 1 computes the MI for one feature x and the target y ; the protocol is applied repeatedly for all features to obtain their scores. Following our federated approach, the data holders locally preprocess their data into an appropriate form, i.e., they compute histograms (joint between feature and target) of the discrete data scaled with the client weights; then, these histograms are secret-shared among the computing servers and they are used as input to the baseline protocol (Algorithm 1).

Note that to compute entropy, cross-entropy, and MI under MPC, we need to evaluate the logarithm, or more precisely the function $z \mapsto z \log_2 z$. We use base 2 logarithms instead of natural logarithms to measure information (the unit of information is bits). Converting to natural logarithms would cost one extra multiplication by $\ln 2$ per feature. The process we employ to approximate $\log_2 z$ is as follows. We convert z to base-2 floating point $z = w \cdot 2^p$ where p is an integer and $1/2 < w \leq 1$. Note that $\log_2 z = p + \log_2 w$ and employ a Padé rational function approximation to approximate $\log_2 w$ to the desired precision [93]. This approximation applied to a secret-shared value z is denoted $\log_2 z$. The total number of data points n can be computed in MPC by summing secret-shares of n_1, \dots, n_k .

The **Base** protocol yields $O(NMm)$ multiplications, where m is the number of multiplications required to approximate $z \mapsto z \log_2 z$, and $O(NMk)$ additions. Note that for discretized regression problems and classification problems with many classes, M can be large, hence executing the **Base** protocol can be costly (as illustrated in our experiments in Section 5.6). Thus, we propose to compute a lower complexity bound on MI and use it to filter out irrelevant features more efficiently.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Algorithm 1 Base: A Secure Protocol for MI.

Require: For each local dataset $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, secret-shared weighted probabilities p_{ijl} , where $p_{ijl} = \lambda_j p_{il}(x_j, y_j)$ for each $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and $l \in \{1, \dots, M\}$.

Ensure: Secret-shared approximation of MI $I(x, y)$ of the feature x and the target y .

```
1:  $r_3 \leftarrow 0$ 
2: for  $i = 1, \dots, N$  do
3:   for  $l = 1, \dots, M$  do
4:      $p_{il} \leftarrow \sum_j p_{ijl}$ 
5:      $r_3 \leftarrow r_3 - p_{il} \log_2 p_{il}$ 
6:   end for
7: end for
8: for  $i = 1, \dots, N$  do
9:    $a_i \leftarrow \sum_l p_{il}$ 
10: end for
11: for  $l = 1, \dots, M$  do
12:    $b_l \leftarrow \sum_i p_{il}$ 
13: end for
14:  $r_1 \leftarrow -\sum_i a_i \log_2 a_i$ 
15:  $r_2 \leftarrow -\sum_l b_l \log_2 b_l$ 
16:  $I(x, y) \leftarrow r_1 + r_2 - r_3$ 
```

5.5.3 Bounded Mutual Information

We derive an upper bound on MI of a mixture distribution and we characterize it in terms of Kullback-Leibler divergences of the mixture and its components. We use this upper bound as an alternative feature score to filter out features with small enough MI, i.e., we cut off features at a given threshold of the score. Cutting off features with a small MI score implies eliminating features with a weak dependence on the target variable. Note that filtering features based on this upper bound of MI is a conservative approach; all features with relatively strong dependence on the target variable are retained, and some extra features may be included in the selected set.

Our main idea is to use the concavity of entropy to bound from below the global joint entropy $H(x, y)$ in terms of the local joint entropies $H(x_i, y_i)$. This gives us an upper bound on the MI of feature x and target y . Furthermore, to avoid computing $H(x)$, we bound it from above in terms of the cross-entropies $C(x, x_i)$, which together with the concavity bound on $H(x, y)$ yields a looser upper bound of MI. The advantage of using the upper bound instead of the MI in a multi-party setting is that the entropies $H(x_i, y_i)$ of each data holder can be computed locally and the cross-entropies $C(x, x_i)$ are cheaper to compute than $H(x)$. This is because $C(x, x_i) = -\sum_{j=1}^N p_j(x) \log p_j(x_i)$ and the logarithms $\log p_j(x_i)$ can be computed locally. This gives rise to considerable improvements in computational and communication costs (see Section 5.5.4 and

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Section 5.6).

We now derive a Lemma that will help us bound MI. Note that the function $z \mapsto -z \log z$, for $z > 0$, is concave since it has a decreasing derivative. It follows by Jensen's inequality that $H(x) \geq \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i H(x_i)$. Furthermore, for all i , $D_{\text{KL}}(p(x), p(x_i)) \geq 0$ and hence $H(x) \leq C(x, x_i)$. Hence, $H(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i H(x) \leq \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i C(x, x_i)$. In summary,

$$\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i H(x_i) \leq H(x) \leq \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i C(x, x_i).$$

For the gap of the lower bound we have that

$$H(x) - \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i H(x_i) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i D_{\text{KL}}(x_i, x).$$

Proof. Note that $\sum_i \lambda_i C(x_i, x) = H(x)$ since $\sum_i \lambda_i (\sum_j -p_j(x_i) \log p_j(x)) = \sum_j -(\sum_i \lambda_i p_j(x_i)) \log p_j(x) = \sum_j -p_j(x) \log p_j(x)$. Furthermore, recall that for each i , $D_{\text{KL}}(x_i, x) = C(x_i, x) - H(x_i)$. Hence,

$$\sum_i \lambda_i D_{\text{KL}}(x_i, x) = \sum_i \lambda_i C(x_i, x) - \sum_i \lambda_i H(x_i) = H(x) - \sum_i \lambda_i H(x_i).$$

□

We apply the above observations to bound MI from above.

Proposition 1. Let $B(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i C(x, x_i) + H(y) - \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i H(x_i, y_i)$ and let $z_i = (x_i, y_i)$ and $z = (x, y)$ denote the joint variables. Then,

1. $I(x, y) \leq B(x, y)$,
2. $B(x, y) - I(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i (D_{\text{KL}}(x, x_i) + D_{\text{KL}}(z_i, z))$.

Proof. Following the properties of entropy (Section 5.3.2), we have that $I(x, y) = H(x) + H(y) - H(x, y) \leq \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i C(x, x_i) + H(y) - \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i H(x_i, y_i)$, which proves the first claim. For the second claim, note that $B(x, y) - I(x, y) = \sum_i \lambda_i C(x, x_i) - H(x) + H(x, y) - \sum_i \lambda_i H(x_i, y_i)$. Furthermore, $\sum_i \lambda_i C(x, x_i) - H(x) = \sum_i \lambda_i (C(x, x_i) - H(x)) = \sum_i \lambda_i D_{\text{KL}}(x, x_i)$. Finally, $H(z) - \sum_i \lambda_i H(z_i) = \sum_i \lambda_i D_{\text{KL}}(z_i, z)$ by Lemma 5.5.3. □

The second part of the proposition expresses the gap of the upper bound as the weighted mean of KL-divergences between components x_i and (x_i, y_i) , and the mixture distributions x and (x, y) . This means that the bound is tighter when the distributions x_i are in the mean similar to their mixture and, hence, similar to each other. In the extreme case where all the

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

client distributions are equal, $I(x, y) = B(x, y)$ and the bound is an equality. The converse is also true, i.e., if $I(x, y) = B(x, y)$, then (x_i, y_i) and (x, y) have the same distribution.

The bound $B(x, y)$ is useful when the local distributions are approximately equal to the global distributions; their similarity is measured implicitly by the bound. If, for a given i , some of the probabilities $p_i(x_j)$ are small or zero (but not all), the upper bound $B(x, y)$ grows as the cross entropy $C(x, x_i)$ becomes large. To remedy this, we modify the bound by cutting off small probabilities at a given level $0 < \epsilon \leq \min_j(e^{-1/\lambda_j})$.

We note here that a simple alternative approach is to only use the concavity bound on entropy and not use the cross entropy bound $H(x) \leq \sum_j \lambda_j C(x, x_i)$ but simply compute $H(x) = \sum_i -p_i(x) \log p_i(x)$ directly at a cost of N evaluations of the function $z \mapsto z \log z$.

The Mixture Information.

In our experiments, we also consider the mixture information $\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i I(x_i, y_i)$, which is a straightforward reduction of the global MI to local computations. We sample the underlying random variable of the mixture distribution as follows: first, we select a client i randomly with probabilities $0 < \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_k \leq 1$ independently of $x_1, y_1, \dots, x_k, y_k$, and then we sample (x_i, y_i) . We call this random variable the mixture variable of $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_k, y_k)$.

Consider local distributions (X_1, Y_1) and (X_2, Y_2) where X_1 and Y_1 are independent and both uniformly distributed in $[-1, 0]$, while X_2 and Y_2 are independent and uniform in $[0, 1]$. Moreover, consider the mixture variable (X, Y) which samples the clients uniformly with probability $1/2$. In this case, the local MI of (X_1, Y_1) and (X_2, Y_2) are both zero, and the mixture information is zero. However, the mixtures X and Y are not independent, thus the MI of X and Y is not zero.

Example 5.5.3 shows that the actual MI can diverge from the mixture information when the client distributions are dissimilar from each other (and the mixture distribution). While computing the mixture information incurs minor computational and communication costs in the multi-party setting compared to centralized computation, it may give incorrect results and be misleading, as we shall see in Section 5.6.2.

5.5.4 A More Efficient Secure Protocol for Mutual Information

Algorithm 2 shows how to compute with MPC the upper bound $B(x, y)$ for a feature x and target y from Proposition 1. Following our federated approach, the data holders locally preprocess their data: They compute weighted histograms, weighted logarithms, and local joint entropies between feature and target. They also filter out probabilities smaller than the cutoff parameter ϵ . The results are secret-shared among the computing servers and are used as input to Algorithm 2.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Algorithm 2 BMI: A Secure Protocol for the Upper Bound of MI.

Require: For each local dataset $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, secret-shared weighted histograms a_{ij} and b_{lj} , weighted logarithms c_{ij} and weighted local joint entropies d_j . Here $a_{ij} = \lambda_j \bar{p}_i(x_j)$ where $\bar{p}_i(x_j) = \max(p_i(x_j), \epsilon)$, $b_{lj} = \lambda_j p_l(y_j)$, $c_{ij} = \lambda_j \log_2 \bar{p}_i(x_j)$ and $d_j = \lambda_j H(x_j, y_j)$, for each $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and $l \in \{1, \dots, M\}$.

Require: Approximation of the upper bound $B(x, y)$ of a feature x and target y .

```

1: for  $i = 1, \dots, N$  do
2:    $a_i \leftarrow \sum_j a_{ij}$ 
3:    $b_i \leftarrow \sum_j b_{ij}$ 
4:    $c_i \leftarrow \sum_j c_{ij}$ 
5: end for
6:  $r_1 \leftarrow -\sum_i a_i c_i$ 
7:  $r_2 \leftarrow -\sum_i b_i \log_2 b_i$ 
8:  $r_3 \leftarrow \sum_j d_j$ 
9:  $B(x, y) \leftarrow r_1 + r_2 - r_3$ 

```

The cutoff parameter $0 < \epsilon \leq \min_j(e^{-1/\lambda_j})$ is computed with MPC as follows: As the total number of data points n is publicly known, so are the weights, and hence each data holder can compute e^{-1/λ_j} locally and ϵ can be determined using MPC protocols for comparison, see[91].

Since $H(y)$ does not depend on x , there is no need to re-compute it for every feature. In fact, we avoid computing $H(y)$ by using $I(x, y) - H(y)$ instead of $I(x, y)$, or the corresponding upper bound, when comparing feature scores. This is, however, a minor gain in cases where there are many features to score.

After an initial approximate feature filtering step using the MI bound, one can perform more accurate filtering for the remaining features using the **Base** protocol. This gives an efficient way of filtering features according to MI when the local distributions are sufficiently similar. However, such a procedure would likely leak additional information (for instance which features are filtered out in the first round) and therefore requires further study left for future work.

Operation	Base	BMI
Additions	$O(NMk)$	$O(Nk)$
Multiplications	$O(NMm)$	$O(N)$

Table 3 – Base vs. BMI: Number of multiplications and additions per feature.

The **BMI** protocol yields $O(N)$ multiplications and $O(Nk)$ additions. Note that the most important performance measure is the number of multiplications, as this determines communication costs and dominates computational costs in the multi-party protocol we employ [34]. Table 3 shows that **BMI** achieves a considerable reduction in the number of multiplications compared to **Base**, especially if M and m are large. This gives rise to considerable improvements in com-

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

putation and communication costs as can be seen in our experimental results (Section 5.6).

5.5.5 Secure Feature Filtering Based on Mutual Information

Finally, we formulate an MPC protocol for creating a feature mask which can be used to process the dataset by selecting the designated features. The input to the MPC protocol is a secret-shared vector $V = (s_1, \dots, s_f)$ of scores, with one score for each of feature, and a threshold value $\theta \in \mathbf{R}$. The output is the secret-shared feature mask: a vector of zeros and ones, with a zero if $s_i < \theta$ and 1 otherwise. For this purpose, we use an MPC protocol for comparison: $\text{comp}(z, w) = 1$ if $z < w$ and $\text{comp}(z, w) = 0$ otherwise, see [91]. The feature mask may then be expressed as $(1 - \text{comp}(s_1, \theta), \dots, 1 - \text{comp}(s_f, \theta))$.

Feature selection can be done with full privacy-preservation by following [5] or a similar protocol to project the datasets to the selected features. Alternatively, one may choose to leak information by revealing the feature mask, which enables efficient feature projection in cleartext by the data holders themselves.

5.6 Experimental Evaluation

We report the results of numerical experiments carried out on a number of datasets and we compare the performance of the **Base** and **BMI** protocols.

5.6.1 Datasets

We first describe the datasets used for the experimental results reported in Section 5.6.2 for both classification and regression tasks.

1. **SpO2**: This dataset consists of time-series of peripheral oxygen saturation levels in the blood recorded on sleeping subjects as part of the SIESTA project [94]. In this dataset, the saturation level is 69%-100% restricted to integer values. The time-series are labeled according to whether a desaturation event occurs, which is a drop in oxygen levels possibly caused by sleep apnea. The labeling has been done with the ABOSA desaturation detector [95]. We preprocess the data by extracting one histogram for each time-series counting saturation levels; this results in 32 features per sample whose values we quantize into 20 bins.
2. **Synth**: This is a synthetic dataset consisting of 20,000 samples drawn from the distribution described in Example 5.3.1 with $m = 300$. It contains 300 features but only 2 are important for predicting the target variable, i.e., a regression problem. Before feature selection, we preprocess the data by quantization in 35 bins on the interval $[-1, 1]$.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Dataset	# of Samples	# of Features	Task	N	M
SpO2	36,865	32	Classification	20	2
Synth	20,000	300	Regression	35	35
Gisette	6,000	5,000	Classification	30	2
Spambase	3,681	57	Classification	10	2
Synth2	10,000	10	Classification	35	2

Table 4 – Characteristics of the employed datasets.

3. **Gisette**: The Gisette dataset is a selection of images from the MNIST (modified National Institute of Standards and Technology database) handwritten digits dataset.¹ The dataset is based on images from the digits 4 and 9. The training set consists of 6,000 random example images from these classes, and we extract 5,000 features from each sample. The dataset is part of the NIPS 2003 variable selection Benchmarks.² We preprocess the data by aggregating feature values into 30 bins.
4. **Spambase**: This dataset consists of statistics derived from emails such as word counts and character counts (54 features) and lengths of sequences of capital letters (3 features). The emails are labeled as spam or not spam. The dataset is publicly available³, see also [96]. We normalize the data and we aggregate feature values into 10 bins.
5. **Synth2**: This is a synthetic dataset consisting of 10,000 points with 10 features x_0, \dots, x_9 uniformly distributed in $[-1, 1]$. The target variable y is the sign of x_0 (1 or -1) except that the value is flipped with probability 10%. In other words, $y = \text{sgn}(x_0) \cdot b$, where b is a Bernoulli variable which is 1 with probability 90% and -1 with probability 10% (if $x_0 = 0$, we let $\text{sgn}(x_0) = 1$). We quantize the feature values in 35 bins on the interval $[-1, 1]$.

Table 4 summarizes the characteristics of the datasets, i.e., the number of samples, number of features, and modelling task. Moreover, it displays how the data is discretized with N bins for the feature variables and M bins for the target variable.

5.6.2 Experimental Results

We train a Support Vector Machine with Radial Basis Function kernel for classification and regression tasks for all datasets except for **Spambase** where we train a logistic regression model. In each case, we randomly select 80% of the dataset for training and the other 20% is used as test set. We perform feature selection on the training data, and we evaluate the model's accuracy on the test set. To evaluate the computational overhead of the **Base** and **BMI**

¹<http://yann.lecun.com/exdb/mnist/>

²<https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/170/gisette>

³<https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/94/spambase>

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Dataset	NoFS	Base	BMI	F-Base	F-BMI	θ
SpO2	88%	86%	86%	6	8	0.1
Synth	0.31	0.046	0.046	2	2	0.3
Gisette	97%	95%	97%	84	129	0.12
Spambase	91%	88%	89%	15	17	0.1

Table 5 – Classification accuracy and regression error (iid case).

protocols, we implement them in the MP-SPDZ framework [85] and computations are carried out in the ring $\mathbb{Z}/2^m$ with $m = 128$. We consider the 3-party setting with honest majority and passive as well as active adversaries.

Model Accuracy.

We begin with the case where the clients have (roughly) the same data distribution, i.e., a homogeneous (iid) setting. We split the datasets evenly between three clients in a uniform manner with approximately the same number of data points at each client. Table 5 displays the model performance on the test set by reporting accuracy for classification and root mean squared error (RMSE) for regression tasks. For comparison purposes, we report the metrics for the case of no feature selection (**NoFS**), the baseline algorithm for MI (**Base**), and the feature selection using the upper bound (**BMI**). We display the accuracy for some example values of the threshold $\theta \geq 0$; features with MI below this level are filtered out. We also record the number of features selected by the filter methods **Base** and **BMI** (**F-Base** and **F-BMI**). We observe that for the classification problems, both feature selection methods reduce the number of features substantially while retaining a model accuracy close to the **NoFS** baseline. We also see that **BMI** is a bit more conservative than **Base** as it includes some extra features in the selection. For the regression problem, both methods correctly identify the 2 relevant features, while a model without feature selection has very poor performance.

Dataset	NoFS	Base	Mix	BMI	f-Base	f-Mix	f-BMI	θ
Synth2	89%	90%	50%	90%	$\{x_0\}$	$\{x_1\}$	$\{x_0, x_1\}$	0.5
Synth2	89%	90%	50%	89%	$\{x_0\}$	$\{x_1\}$	all 10	0.4

Table 6 – Classification accuracy and selected features (non-iid case).

Next, we consider a heterogeneous (non-iid) case with the dataset **Synth2** and illustrate the difference between **Base**, **BMI**, and a fully federated approach that uses mixture information as a feature score. To create a skewed client distribution that misleads the federated approach, we split the dataset into three client sets as follows: Client 1 has the points with $y < 0$ and $x_1 < 0$, client 2 has the points with $y \geq 0$ and $x_1 \geq 0$, and client 3 has the rest of the dataset. The results are shown in Table 6, where **Base**, **BMI**, and the mixture information score (**Mix**)

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Dataset	Base			BMI		
	active	passive	mult	active	passive	mult
SpO2	$16.4 \cdot 10^3$	$1.29 \cdot 10^3$	600	200	13.25	20
Synth	$347 \cdot 10^3$	$32.0 \cdot 10^3$	12600	382	31.3	35
Gisette	$25.5 \cdot 10^3$	$2.11 \cdot 10^3$	900	328	21.8	30
Spambase	$8.22 \cdot 10^3$	692	300	109	6.64	10

Table 7 – Base vs. BMI: Computation time (ms) for passive and active adversaries and # of multiplications required.

are compared for some threshold values θ . The table also displays the set of features selected in each case in the columns **f-Base**, **f-BMI** and **f-Mix**. We observe that with $\theta = 0.5$, **Base** and **BMI** manage to pick out the relevant feature x_0 and yield high accuracy, but the skew distribution makes **BMI** select the extra feature x_1 . When $\theta = 0.4$, the output of **Base** remains the same while **BMI** does not manage to filter out any features and high accuracy is retained. Meanwhile, **Mix** consistently picks the wrong feature x_1 which results in low accuracy.

Performance Results.

Table 7 shows the computation and communication costs of the feature selection step with **Base** and **BMI** implemented under MPC. We express the performance in terms of elapsed time per feature (ms) for both active and passive adversaries, as well as the number of multiplications required per feature. Communication costs a directly proportional to the number of multiplications. We observe that, in the passive setting, **BMI** provides a speedup of $100\times$ over **Base** for the classification problems and about $1000\times$ for the regression problem.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

6 Privacy preserving classification

6.1 Introduction

ML, specifically Deep Learning (DL), has garnered significant attention from researchers due to its solid performance in many tasks, such as speech recognition, spam detection, image classification, traffic analysis, face recognition, financial detection, and genomics prediction [97, 98, 99, 100, 101, 102]. Among the various tasks in ML, classification – the process of classifying data into predefined classes based on its features – stands as one of the most fundamental and widely studied problem [103].

Training these models requires vast amounts of data and significant computational power. To address this need, CSPs such as Google Prediction API [104], Microsoft Azure ML [105], and Ersatz Lab [106] offer MLaaS, allowing users to train and test ML models on CSP infrastructure. Typically, these models involve a training phase where the model learns from a dataset, and a testing phase, where it classifies or predicts outputs based on unseen inputs [107]. Once trained and deployed on the CSP, users can use it for online prediction or classification services. However, the adoption of MLaaS raises concerns about the privacy of data being outsourced, in sensitive domains such as finance and healthcare [108]. There is a risk of data misuse or theft when sending data to models hosted by CSPs [109]. In response to these concerns, the field of PPML has emerged, aiming to develop methods that ensure data privacy while still enabling accurate and effective model training and inference [110].

PPML seeks to enable accurate classifications without revealing sensitive information about the underlying data [6]. Techniques such as HE [9] and SMPC [111] have been proposed as a promising solutions for enabling privacy preserving classification. These techniques enable computations on encrypted data, ensuring that neither the input nor the model parameters are exposed during model training and inference. While these techniques offer strong privacy guarantees, their practical deployment is hindered by computational overhead in HE and high communication costs in SMPC [112].

To overcome these limitations, there has been a growing interest in developing decentralized techniques that allow models to learn from distributed data sources without directly accessing the raw data. Collaborative learning approaches such as FL [113] and SL [7] have emerged as a promising solutions that enable model training across distributed data sources without requiring direct data sharing. FL enables multiple users to train a global ML model locally, sharing only model updates with a central server. However, the exchange of model weights introduces potential privacy risks, as a malicious server can extract sensitive information from shared updates [114]. In contrast, SL partitions a model between a client and a server, ensuring that raw data remain on the client-side while only the intermediate output (activation map) are

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

shared with the server. This partition reduces computational overhead for clients and minimizes direct exposure of sensitive data. Additionally, SL offers advantages over FL, such as lower bandwidth requirements and improved efficiency in ML tasks [115].

Despite these advantages, research has shown that SL is vulnerable to privacy leakage [8], such as in scenarios involving time-series data, where intermediate representations can reveal sensitive information. Various mitigation techniques, including DP [116] and architectural modifications, have been proposed to reduce privacy leakage, but they often introduce trade-offs between privacy and model accuracy [117].

While extensive work has been conducted on PPML using HE [118, 119, 119, 110, 112] and SMPC [120, 121, 112], the integration of HE and SMPC with SL remains largely unexplored. The combination of these techniques has the potential to enhance privacy protection by leveraging encrypted feature representations within the SL framework, mitigating privacy risks without significantly compromising model performance. By integrating SL with cryptographic techniques such as HE and (FSS [10, 11, 122] – an SMPC approach, privacy-preserving classification can be achieved without compromising model performance. As research in PPML progresses, hybrid approaches combining SL with efficient cryptographic methods will play a crucial role in enabling secure and scalable ML applications.

6.2 Background

6.2.1 Homomorphic Encryption

HE is an encryption scheme that allows users to perform computations on encrypted data. Given two ciphertexts c and c' , a user can compute $f(c, c')$ where f is a function associated either with an addition or multiplication operation. A typical HE scheme consists of the following four algorithms:

Definition 1 (Homomorphic Encryption). *Let HE be a (public-key) HE scheme with a quadruple of probabilistic polynomial time algorithms $HE = (\text{KeyGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec}, \text{Eval})$ such that:*

- **HE.KeyGen** : The key generation algorithm $(pk, evk, sk) \leftarrow \text{HE.KeyGen}(1^\lambda)$ takes as input a unary representation of the security parameter λ , and outputs a public key pk , an evaluation key evk and a private key sk .
- **HE.Enc** : The encryption algorithm $c \leftarrow \text{HE.Enc}(pk, x)$ takes as input the public key pk and a message x and outputs a ciphertext c .
- **HE.Eval** : The algorithm $c_f \leftarrow \text{HE.Eval}(evk, f, c_1, \dots, c_n)$ takes as input the evaluation key evk , a function f , and a set of n ciphertexts, and outputs a ciphertext c_f .

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- **HE.Dec** : The decryption algorithm $\text{HE.Dec}(\text{sk}, c_f) \rightarrow x$, takes as input the secret key sk and a ciphertext c_f , and outputs a plaintext x .

6.2.2 Split Learning

It is a collaborative learning technique [7] in which an ML model is split into two parts, the client part (f_C), comprises the first few layers of model $(1, \dots, l) - l$ being the last layer on the client-side and the server part (f_P), encompassing the remaining layers of model $(l + 1, \dots, L) - L$ being the last layer on the server-side. The client and server collaborate to train the split model without having access to each other's parts. The client who owns the data uses forward propagation to train their part of the model and sends the intermediate output from the split layer (final layer of the client-side) to the server. The server continues the forward propagation on the intermediate output using their part of the model. After completing the forward propagation and computing the loss, the server performs the backward propagation, only returning to the client the gradients to complete the backward propagation. This process is repeated until the model converges and learns a suitable set of parameters. Although the client and server do not share any raw input data, this configuration requires label sharing. The sharing of labels can be eliminated by using a U-shaped SL configuration. The U-shaped SL configuration is nearly identical to the simple SL setup, with the exception that it does not require clients to share labels [123]. On the server-side, the network is wrapped at the end layer, and the outputs are sent back to the client. Upon reception, client generates gradients from the end layers and utilize them for backward propagation without revealing the corresponding labels.

The aim of SL is to protect client privacy by allowing clients to train part of the model, and share intermediate output (instead of their raw data) with a server running the remaining part of the model. It is also utilized to reduce the client's computational overhead by merely running a few layers rather than the entire model. Figure 1 illustrates three different models: the local model on the left, the vanilla SL model in the middle, and the U-shaped SL model on the right. In the local model, there is no split, while in the vanilla SL there is a split with labels being shared with the server. In contrast, the U-shaped SL model also has a split but with the final layer being executed on the client-side, resulting in no sharing of labels with the server.

6.2.3 Function Secret Sharing

FSS provides a way for additively secret-sharing a function f from a given function family F . More concretely, a two-party FSS scheme splits a function $f : (0, 1)^n \rightarrow G$, for some abelian group G , into functions described by keys such that $f = f_0 + f_1$ and every strict subset of the keys hides f . An FSS scheme for some class F has two algorithms (KeyGen, EvalAll):

Figure 1 – Different Split Learning Configurations

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- $\text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda, f) \rightarrow (f_0, f_1)$: The KeyGen algorithm that takes the security parameter 1^λ and some secret function f to be shared and outputs two different function shares (f_0, f_1) (also called function keys).
- $\text{EvalAll}(j, f_j, x_{pub}) \rightarrow f_j(x_{pub})$: The EvalAll algorithm takes three parameters, the input bit $j \in \{0, 1\}$, the key f_j , and the public data x_{pub} and outputs the shares $f_j(x_{pub})$.

An FSS scheme should satisfy the following two properties:

- **Secrecy**: A single key (f_j) hides the original function f .
- **Correctness**: Adding the local shares get the same output as the original function ($f_0(x_{pub}) + f_1(x_{pub}) = f(x_{pub})$).

As can be seen in Figure 2, function f is first split into two shares f_0 and f_1 and then each party locally evaluates the function on the input x_{pub} . In FSS, adding the locally evaluated functions ($f_0(x_{pub}) + f_1(x_{pub})$), gives the additive reconstruction of the original function applied on the input $f(x_{pub})$.

Figure 2 – Function secret sharing

6.3 Public Local and Split Learning Protocols

In this section, we describe the initial non-split or local model, explaining its structure and functionality before introducing the process of transforming it into a split model. Following this, we provide a brief overview of two widely used SL protocols: the public vanilla SL and the public U-shaped SL protocol. Here, the term *public* means that all computations are performed on plaintext data.

6.3.1 Local model without split learning

The local model consists of two convolution layers, two max-pooling layers, two fully connected layers and four ReLU layers. These layers operate without any split between client and server, with one party performing computations on the entire model (see Figure 3). The training process of this model can be described as follows.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 3 – Local model without split learning

Let $|\mathbf{D}| = \{(x_i, y_i) | i = 1, 2, \dots, m\}$ be a training dataset consisting of m data samples. Each data sample x has a corresponding encoded label vector y that represents its ground-truth class. Then, f_θ is a function representing the local model with θ being a set of adjustable parameters. θ is first initialized to small random values denoted as Φ . The goal is to find the optimal parameters θ to map x to a predicted output vector \hat{y} , where \hat{y} is as close as possible to y . \hat{y} is a vector of probabilities (called posteriors), and we use the highest probability to determine the class to which x belongs. To find the closest value of \hat{y} with respect to y , we try to minimize a loss function $J = \mathcal{L}(\hat{y}, y)$. Training the local model is an iterative process to find the best θ to minimize J . This process involves two steps: *forward* and *backward* propagation. The forward propagation computes each layer in the network on input x , reaching the output layer to predict \hat{y} . Backward propagation starts from the output layer and goes back to the input layer to calculate the gradients of the loss function J with respect to the network's weights θ . These weights are then updated according to the calculated gradients. We train the local model with numerous samples of x and corresponding y , through many iterations of forward and backward propagation. We do not train the network on each single data example, but use a number of them at a time (using batch size n). The total number of training batches is $N = \frac{|\mathbf{D}|}{n}$, where $|\mathbf{D}|$ is the size of the dataset. Once the model goes through all the training batches, it has completed one training E and this process continues for a total of E epochs. We implement and reproduce the results for this model. The best test accuracy that we obtained for this model is 99.29%.

6.3.2 Local model with vanilla and U-shaped Split

In this section, we discuss the split version of the Convolutional NN (CNN) model. We split the CNN model into multiple parts, each of which is processed and computed by a separate party. For our setting, we consider two parties, a client and a server, with one part of the model executed on the client and another part of the model executed on the server. Both parties participate in training the CNN model. The activation maps and gradients are exchanged between client and server to collaboratively train the joint model, but neither can access the other's data.

In vanilla SL protocol, we split the local model between the client and the server in such a

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 4 – Local model with vanilla split learning

way that the starting layers, convolution layers, max-pooling and the first two ReLU layers are executed on client-side while two fully connected layers and the last two ReLU layers are executed on the server-side. The training input data is residing on the client-side while the final prediction of the model is on the server-side (see Figure 4).

In the U-shaped SL, the first few layers and the last layer are executed on the client side, while the remaining layers are executed on the server side. As a result, only the client has access to the model's output, while the server does not know the model's output.

6.4 Private SL Training Protocol using HE and FSS

This section introduces the key participants in the protocols, followed by socket initialization and context generation. We then describe two key protocols: Private SL training using HE and Private SL training using FSS. We also designed another private protocol using hybrid HE, but since it is already included in D1.1, we will not cover it here. The term *Private* indicates that all computations are performed on encrypted data.

Actors in the model Now, we define the main actors participating in the protocols and detail their abilities:

- **Client:** The client provides the training data and is capable of computing the initial layer of the model in plaintext. The client uses their private data to compute the initial layers of the model and shares the intermediate output and the remaining layers with the servers.
- **Servers:** We have designed two protocols for Private SL training: one using HE and the other using FSS.
 - The HE-based protocol runs computations on a single server and supports only one linear layer. The server can access the weights, biases and other HE parameters like polynomial modulus \mathcal{P} , coefficient modulus \mathcal{C} and scaling factor Δ (except secret key sk).

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- The FSS-based protocol uses two servers to compute on secret shares. Each server processes the public input x_{pub} using the ML model, and both compute the final output, comparing it to the client's provided labels. We assume no collusion between the servers, and they operate independently to avoid reconstructing the original data from the shares.

Socket initialization and context generation This is same for both the protocols. The client first connects to the server through the socket and receives a number of training parameters to synchronize (see Figure 5). The parameters that are synchronized between the client and server are E, η, n, N . E is the number of training epochs, n is the batch size, N is the number of batches to be trained and, η represents the learning rate. These parameters should be synchronized on both sides in order to train the CNN model in the same way. In addition, both the client and server use the random weight initializer ϕ to initialize the weights w_i and biases b_i of their respective layers. The variables $\mathbf{a}^{(i)}$ (activation map), $\mathbf{z}^{(i)}$ (output of a tensor vector), and the gradients are also set to zero at the start of the phase.

6.4.1 Private SL Training Protocol using HE

In this section, we discuss in detail the U-shaped split model with the encrypted activation map. We refer to this protocol as HESplit network. Before delving into the details, consider a model with L layers in total, with the L^{th} layer serving as the model's output layer. Assume the model is divided into layers l and $l + 1$. As discussed earlier, most of the layers of the CNN model are executed on the client side, while only one layer is executed on the server side. Hence, the client owns the first l layers from layer 1 to layer $l + 1$, as well as the final output layer, whilst the server owns only one linear layer. The main reason for having only one linear layer on the server side is due to computational constraints when training on HE encrypted data. Furthermore, more layers on the server's side require us to insert non-linear operations, which have shown difficulties for encrypted computation. In particular, for the CKKS scheme, we need to resort to approximation [118] which may lead to further degradation in accuracy. Below, we describe the U-shaped SL training protocol with the encrypted activation map. This model consists of the initialization, forward and backward propagation. The initialization phase only takes place once at the beginning of the procedure, whereas the other phases continue until the model iterates through all epochs. In this protocol, during the initialization phase, the context is also generated, which holds the public key pk and secret key sk of the HE scheme as well as other parameters like polynomial modulus \mathcal{P} , coefficient modulus \mathcal{C} and scaling factor Δ .

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 5 – Socket Initialization

Forward propagation The forward propagation starts from the client side. As can be seen in Figure 6, the client and server initialize their part of the model. The client first generates the batch (x, y) , which has n data examples extracted from the train set D . x represents the input data, and y shows their labels. During the forward propagation phase, the client forward propagates the input x (see Equation 1) until layer l and generates an activation map (a^i) .

$$\begin{aligned} z^i &\leftarrow f^{(i)}(\mathbf{a}^{(i-1)}) \\ a^i &\leftarrow g^{(i)}(\mathbf{z}^{(i)}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where f^i and g^i are the convolution operation of layer i and activation function of layer i respectively.

The client encrypts the activation map and sends the encrypted activation map $(\overline{\mathbf{a}^{(l)}})$ to the server (see Algorithm 3). The server performs computation on the encrypted activation map and sends the output to the client $(\overline{\mathbf{a}^{(L)}})$. Finally, the client executes the final softmax layer of the CNN model and calculates the loss function (J) between the original y and the predicted output \hat{y} . The loss function produces error J by computing the cross-entropy loss.

Backward propagation As can be seen in Figure 6, the backpropagation starts from the client side. The client calculates the loss function, the gradients of the loss function with respect to the activation map and send these gradients to the server. On receiving the gradients from the client, the server calculates the gradients of the loss function with respect to its linear layer and update the parameter of this layer. More specifically, as shown in Algorithm 3 and Algorithm 4, the client calculates and sends the gradients of error with respect to $a^{(L)}$ to the

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 6 – Forward and Backward Propagation

server. The server continues the backpropagation, calculates $\frac{dJ}{db}$, $\overline{\frac{dJ}{dw'}}$ and $\frac{dJ}{da}$. The server then sends $\frac{dJ}{da}$ to the client. After receiving the gradients, the backpropagation continues to the first hidden layer on the client side. Note that as $\frac{dJ}{dw'}$ becomes encrypted, the server's weights will become encrypted after updating the parameters as in Equation 2. After updating this parameters for several forward and backward pass, the noise level in w can cause overflow, rendering the computation incorrect. To solve this issue, the server also sends the encrypted weights to the client after adding some fixed noise to it to preserve the weight's privacy. Upon reception, the client decrypts the weights to reset the HE noise level and sends the weights back to the server. After receiving the decrypted weights, the server subtracts the fixed noise added earlier and continues to the next forward propagation pass. The forward and backward propagation continue until the model converges to learn a suitable set of parameters.

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{(w'(L))} &= HE.Enc(w'(L)) \\ \overline{(w'(L))} &= \overline{(w'(L))} - \frac{\partial J}{\partial w'(L)} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Algorithm 3 Client Side

Initialization:

```

s ← socket initialization s.connect
η, n, N, E ← s.synchronize()
{w(i), b(i)}∀i∈{0..l} ← Φ
{z(i)}∀i∈{0..l}, {a(i)}∀i∈{0..l} ← ∅
{∂J/∂zi}i∈{0..l}, {∂J/∂ai}i∈{0..l} ← ∅

```

Context Initialization:

```

ctxpri ← P, C, Δ, pk, sk
ctxpub ← P, C, Δ, pk
s.send(ctxpub)

```

for e in E do
for each batch (x, y) from D do
Forward propagation :

```
O.zero_grad()
```

```
a0 ← x
```

for i ← 1 to l do

```
z(i) ← f(i)(a(i-1))
```

```
ai ← g(i)(z(i))
```

end for

```
a(l) ← HE.Enc(pk, a(l))
```

```
s.send(a(l))
```

```
s.receive(a(l))
```

```
a(L) ← HE.Dec(sk, a(l))
```

```
ŷ ← Softmax(a(L))
```

```
J ← L(ŷ, y)
```

Backward propagation :

```
Compute {∂J/∂ŷ & ∂J/∂a(L)}
```

```
s.send(∂J/∂a(L))
```

```
s.receive(∂J/∂a(l))
```

for i ← l down to 1 do

```
Compute {∂J/∂w(i), ∂J/∂b(i)}
```

```
Update w(i), b(i)
```

end for

```
w'(L) = HE.Dec(w'(L))
```

```
s.send(w'(L))
```

end for
end for

Algorithm 4 Server Side

Initialization:

```
s ← socket initialization s.connect
```

```
η, n, N, E ← s.synchronize()
```

```
{w(i), b(i)}∀i∈{0..l} ← Φ
```

```
{z(i)}∀i∈{l+1..L} ← ∅
```

```
{∂J/∂z(i)}}∀i∈{l+1..L} ← ∅
```

for e ∈ E do
for i ← 1 to N do
Forward propagation :

```
O.zero_grad()
```

```
s.receive(a(l))
```

```
a(L) ← (a(l)).w' + b
```

```
s.send(a(L))
```

Backward propagation :

```
s.receive(∂J/∂a(L))
```

```
Compute {∂J/∂w'(L), ∂J/∂b(L), ∂J/∂a(L)}
```

```
Encrypt and add noise to w'(L)
```

```
Update w'(L), b(L).
```

```
Compute ∂J/∂a(l)
```

```
s.send(∂J/∂a(l))
```

```
s.send(w'(L))
```

```
s.receive(w'(L))
```

```
Subtract noise from w'(L)
```

end for
end for

6.4.2 Performance Analysis

We evaluate the performance of our framework on two Electrocardiography (ECG) datasets: the MIT-BIH dataset [124] and the PTB-XL dataset [125].

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

MIT-BIH This dataset contains 48 half-hour excerpts of two-channel ECG recordings, obtained from 47 subjects from 1975 to 1979. We use the processed version of the dataset from [117], which contains 26,490 heartbeat samples. Each sample belongs to one out of five classes: Normal (N), Left bundle branch block (L), Right bundle branch block (R), Atrial premature contraction (A), Ventricular premature contraction (V). To train the Neural Networks (NNs), the dataset is split into a 50-50 ratio. A train or test split contains 13,245 examples, each example is a time series signal of length 128.

PTB-XL It is a large ECG dataset that contains 21837 clinical ECGs from 18885 patients, collected between 1989 and 1996. Each ECG waveform has 12 channels (leads) and is 10 seconds long. The raw waveforms are sampled at two different sampling rates (100 Hz and 500 Hz) and annotated by up to two cardiologists, who may assign multiple statements to one ECG signal. An ECG signal can be diagnosed to belong to one out of five superclasses: Normal ECG (NORM), Myocardial Infarction (MI), ST/T Change (STTC), Conduction Disturbance (CD), and Hypertrophy (HYP). The dataset is processed according to [126], where a sampling rate of 100 Hz is used. Following the example of [126], if an ECG signal belongs to more than one classes, we only choose one (the first class). The whole dataset is then split into train-test splits at a ratio of 90%-10%. More specifically, the training split contains 19,267 data samples and the test split contains 2,163 data samples.

Hyper- and HE- parameters settings: First, we reproduced the training results for the local version and the split version on HESplit network plaintext data from [126] and concluded in the same results, namely 88.06% accuracy on the MIT-BIH dataset. We also trained a plaintext split network on the PTB-XL dataset and got 67.68% accuracy. Note that these accuracies are low, however, as we only focus on comparing the accuracies when training on plaintext versus encrypted data, getting high predictive accuracies on these datasets is not our focus. To train the network on these datasets, we use 10 epochs with a learning rate of 0.001 and batch size 4. For plaintext training, we used the Adam optimizer on both the client and server side.

We use the same NN HPs when training the HESplit network on encrypted activation maps, however, the optimizer on the server side is a simple stochastic gradient descent. To encrypt the activation maps before sending them to the server, we employ two sets of HE parameters as following:

1. S1: $N = 2^{13} = 8192$, $C = [40, 21, 21, 21, 40]$, $\Delta = 2^{21}$

2. S2: $N = 2^{14} = 16384$, $C = [40, 21, 21, 21, 40]$, $\Delta = 2^{21}$

The only difference between the two sets of HE parameters is the polynomial modulus degree N , which directly affects the computational performance of the scheme (bigger is worse) and

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Table 8 – Training results of HESplit network on the MIT-BIH abd PTB-XL dataset using different sets of HE parameters and batch sizes. The training duration (in sec) and communication (in Gb) overhead are reported as the average value per epoch

Dataset	HE param set	Batch Size	Accuracy (%)	Training Time (s)	Communication (Gb)
MIT-BIH	S1	4	83.49	8100.60	239.53
		8	78.01	4780.73	121.57
		16	74.77	2855.29	62.58
		32	73.79	1658.73	33.09
		64	62.08	987.42	18.35
	S2	4	83.09	19746.85	471.57
		8	67.94	10378.92	239.33
		16	70.33	5358.59	123.20
		32	72.47	3152.82	65.14
		64	64.42	1913.11	36.11
PTB-XL	S1	4	58.71	100060.60	2624.85
		8	58.95	49334.95	1315.38
		16	57.10	22501.79	660.65
		32	59.36	12370.38	333.23
		64	56.45	5702.29	169.60

its security level (bigger is better). Apart from that, the coefficient modulus \mathcal{C} is a list of prime numbers that define scheme noise levels and HE multiplication depth. Each HE multiplication consumes a prime in \mathcal{C} , and after all primes in the list are consumed, we will no longer be able to perform multiplication in the encrypted domain. Δ is called the scaling factor, which is the factor where the plaintext message is multiplied by to maintain a certain level of precision during the encoding process. We vary only N to assess the trade-off between security and performance of our protocol. The results of training the HESplit network with S1 and S2 on the MIT-BIH dataset can be found in [Table 8](#). Due to computational limitations, we can only train HESplit with \mathcal{S}_1 on the PTB-XL dataset.

For the MIT-BIH dataset, the best test accuracy, after training on encrypted activation maps, is 83.49% when using S1 with the training batch size of 4. Overall, we can see that for MIT-BIH, S1 achieve better accuracy than S2, and the training time as well as communication cost using S1 are also about half when using S2. This indicates the trade off between security and utility. For both S1 and S2, the batch size of 4 achieve the best accuracies overall, since once the batch size get bigger, more compression will be done in HE batch processing and more noise will be introduced in HE batch computations. Nonetheless, the bigger the batch size, the less training time and communication needed, and this relationship is linear as observed from our experiments. When the batch size is small ($n = 4$), S1 and S2 produce very comparable accuracies (83.49% vs 83.09%), and S2 incur double training time as well as communication cost compared to S1. However, when n gets bigger, the accuracies of S2 degrade very quickly

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

compared to S1, as can be observed when $n = 16$ and $n = 32$. When $n = 64$, both S1 and S2 produce very low predictive power with 62.08% and 64.42%. We reason that when n gets big, the accumulated noise also become very big that the NN does equally bad on both cases. For the PTB-XL dataset, accuracies across all batch sizes vary much less compared to those from MIT-BIH. The reason for this is that because an ECG example from PTB-XL is much bigger than that from MIT-BIH (length 1000 vs length 128), compressing along the batch size when doing HE encryption and noise incurred during HE computation produce less effects on the results.

6.5 Private SL training protocol using FSS

We have used [Algorithm 5](#) and [Algorithm 6](#) to train the private SL model using FSS. This model consists of the initialization, forward and backward propagation. The initialization phase only takes place once at the beginning of the procedure, whereas the other phases continue until the model iterates through all epochs. There are two phases in training the whole protocol, forward and backward propagation phase.

Forward Propagation During the forward propagation, the client forward propagates the input x through f_{θ_C} to generate an activation map ATm . The private input which is ATm is first masked using random mask α to construct the public input $x_{pub} = ATm + \alpha$ before sending it to the server. Once x_{pub} is constructed, the next step is to send x_{pub} to the server. As can be seen in [Figure 7](#), we have two servers labelled as P_0 and P_1 . Each server receives the public input x_{pub} and initiates forward propagation by executing their respective portion of the model. On the server-side, we employ FSS, allowing us to compute the function keys. Specifically, these keys are generated for the ReLU layers. We employ the FSS KeyGen algorithm, to create these keys for each server. Additionally, to compute the FC layers on the server-side, we used the beaver triples. As in private vanilla SL, the final output layer is executed on the server-side, hence both servers execute their respective share of the layer to produce the final output \hat{y}_j . Both the servers calculate the loss using the equation $J \leftarrow \mathcal{L}(\hat{y}_j, y_j)$. During the loss calculation, the intermediate results and the final loss remain in the form of additive shares. Specifically, y_j is the additive shares of the target value while \hat{y}_j are the predicted output computed by each server. As the loss computation is performed by each servers, now, in order to get the final predicted output, the two servers must collaborate to add their secret shares. In this setting, the servers must know the actual target values as well as the predicted output of the model.

Backward Propagation After completing the forward propagation, each server starts the backward propagation by first computing $\frac{\partial J_j}{\partial \hat{y}_j}$ and continue the backward propagation algorithm

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 7 – Utilizing FSS between two servers

until layer $l + 1$ and update the weights and biases of the layers using the given equations.

$$w = w - \eta \frac{\partial J}{\partial w}, \quad (3)$$

$$b = b - \eta \frac{\partial J}{\partial b} \quad (4)$$

During backward propagation, each server also calculates:

$$\frac{\partial J_j}{\partial AT_m^{(l)}} = \frac{\partial J}{\partial AT_m^{(l+1)}} \frac{\partial AT_m^{(l+1)}}{\partial AT_m^{(l)}}, \quad (5)$$

and sends $\frac{\partial J}{\partial AT_m^{(l)}}$ to the client. After receiving $\frac{\partial J}{\partial AT_m^{(l)}}$, the client calculates the gradients of J w.r.t the weights and biases of its part of layers using the chain-rule, which can generally be described as:

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

$$\frac{\partial J_j}{\partial \mathbf{w}^{(i-1)}} = \frac{\partial J_j}{\partial \mathbf{w}^{(i)}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{w}^{(i)}}{\partial \mathbf{w}^{(i-1)}} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial J_j}{\partial \mathbf{b}^{(i-1)}} = \frac{\partial J_j}{\partial \mathbf{b}^{(i)}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}^{(i)}}{\partial \mathbf{b}^{(i-1)}} \quad (7)$$

Finally, after calculating the gradients $\frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathbf{w}^{(i)}}$, $\frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathbf{b}^{(i)}}$, the client updates $\mathbf{w}^{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{b}^{(i)}$. The forward and backward propagation continue until the model converges to learn a suitable set of parameters.

Algorithm 5 Client-Side Vanilla SL

Initialization:

$soc \leftarrow$ socket initialized with port and address $soc.connect$
 $\eta, n, N, E \leftarrow soc.synchronize$
 $\{\mathbf{w}^{(i)}, \mathbf{b}^{(i)}\}_{\forall i \in \{0..l\}} \leftarrow$ initialize using Φ
 $\{ATm^{(i)}\}_{\forall i \in \{0..l\}} \leftarrow \emptyset$
 $\left\{ \frac{\partial J}{\partial ATm^{(i)}} \right\}_{\forall i \in \{0..l\}} \leftarrow \emptyset$

```

1: for  $e \in E$  do
2:   for each batch  $(x, y)$  generated from  $D$  do
3:     Forward Propagation :
4:     for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $l$  do
5:        $ATm^{(i)} \leftarrow f_{\theta_C}(x^{(i)})$ 
6:     end for
7:      $x_{pub}^i \leftarrow ATm^{(i)} + \alpha$ 
8:      $soc.send(x_{pub}^i)$ 
9:     Backward Propagation :
10:     $soc.receive\left(\frac{\partial J}{\partial ATm_j^{(l+1)}}\right)$ 
11:    Compute  $\left\{ \frac{\partial J}{\partial ATm^l} \right\}$ 
12:    for  $i \leftarrow l$  to 1 do
13:      Compute  $\left\{ \frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathbf{w}^{(i)}}, \frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathbf{b}^{(i)}} \right\}$ 
14:      Update  $\mathbf{w}^{(i)}, \mathbf{b}^{(i)}$ 
15:    end for
16:  end for
17: end for

```

Algorithm 6 Server-Side Vanilla SL

Initialization:

$soc \leftarrow$ socket initialized with port and address $soc.connect$
 $\eta, n, N, E \leftarrow soc.synchronize$

```

1: for  $e \in E$  do
2:   for  $i \leftarrow l+1$  to  $N$  do
3:     Forward Propagation :
4:      $soc.receive(x_{pub}^i)$ 
5:     for  $j = 0, 1$  do
6:        $\hat{y}_j \leftarrow f_{\theta_{P_j}}(x_{pub})$ 
7:        $J_j \leftarrow \mathcal{L}(\hat{y}_j, y_j)$ 
8:     end for
9:     Backward Propagation :
10:    Compute  $\left\{ \frac{\partial J_j}{\partial \hat{y}_j} \right\}$ 
11:    for  $i \leftarrow L$  to  $l+1$  do
12:      Compute  $\left\{ \frac{\partial J_j}{\partial \mathbf{w}_j^{(i)}}, \frac{\partial J_j}{\partial \mathbf{b}_j^{(i)}} \right\}$ 
13:      Update  $\mathbf{w}_j^{(i)}, \mathbf{b}_j^{(i)}$ 
14:    end for
15:     $soc.send\left(\frac{\partial J_j}{\partial ATm_j^{(l+1)}}\right)$ 
16:  end for
17: end for

```

6.5.1 Threat Model & Security Analysis

In this section we first define the threat model we consider. Then, we proceed by proving the security of our protocol.

Threat model In SL, collaborative learning of local models introduces potential risk due to interactions among the participants [127]. We consider a semi-honest adversary, denoted as

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

\mathcal{ADV} , capable of corrupting one of the two servers engaged in our protocol. In this context, the corrupted parties adhere to the protocol's specifications, all the while attempting to gather as much information as possible about the inputs and function shares of other participants. Within our specific framework, secure protocols are employed to facilitate collaborative CNN model training by three parties: a client and two servers. The client, who also serves as the data owner (note that considering a malicious client in this context is pointless), initiates the process by executing the initial layers of the model. This action produces an intermediary result, denoted as AT_m , which is subsequently kept confidential through secret sharing between two independent servers. Following this, these two servers proceed to jointly train the remaining segments of the model using the client's data, achieved by employing the FSS protocol.

Apart from that, the behavior of \mathcal{ADV} can be summarized as follows:

- \mathcal{ADV} does not possess information about the client participating in the distributed training, except the necessary details required to execute the SL protocol.
- \mathcal{ADV} is familiar with a *shadow* dataset, which captures the same domain as the clients' training sets.
- \mathcal{ADV} has no knowledge of the architecture and weights of the whole model.
- \mathcal{ADV} is unaware of the specific task on which the distributed model is trained.

Finally, we extend the above threat model by defining two attacks available to \mathcal{ADV} who wishes to launch an Feature-Space Hijacking Attack (FSHA) or perform data analysis through Visual Invertibility (VI).

Attack 1 (Feature-Space Hijacking Attack). *Let \mathcal{ADV} be an adversary that has compromised at most one of the servers (P_0 or P_1). \mathcal{ADV} successfully performs FSHA if she manages to substitute the original learning task chosen by the client with a new function intentionally designed to mold the feature space of f .*

Attack 2 (Visual Invertibility Inference Attack). *Let \mathcal{ADV} be an adversary, that has compromised at most one of the servers (P_0 or P_1). \mathcal{ADV} successfully performs a Visual Invertibility Inference Attack (VIA) if she manages to infer sensitive information of the original input data using the acquired convolutions from the client. \mathcal{ADV} attempts to identify the original images characteristics and truth labels using intermediate data received during the SL process.*

Feature-space hijacking attack Here, we describe the main concept behind FSHA. In such an attack, the client owns its private data and is responsible for training the f_{θ_C} . Instead of running its part of the SL protocol, the server runs the code provided by the \mathcal{ADV} . To carry out the attack \mathcal{ADV} relies on three networks: The first two \tilde{f} and \tilde{f}^{-1} are used to build an

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

autoencoder (AE) which is trained with a shadow dataset. Specifically, \tilde{f} maps the data space to a feature space whereas \tilde{f}^{-1} act as a decoder that maps back the feature space into the original data space. The third one is Discriminator (D), the network that substitutes $f_{\theta_{P_j}}, j \in \{0, 1\}$, and is trained to distinguish between the output of f_{θ_C} and the output of network \tilde{f} . It is used to cast the gradients for f_{θ_C} during training and bring it in an insecure state. D indirectly guides f_{θ_C} to learn a mapping between the private data and the feature space defined from \tilde{f} . More specifically, D is used to train f_{θ_C} to produce an output that is as close as possible to the one of \tilde{f} . Ultimately, this is the network that substitutes server network in the protocol, and that defines the gradient which is sent to the client during the distributed training process. After certain number of iterations, the feature space learned by f_{θ_C} overlaps with one defined from \tilde{f} . Once this happens, \tilde{f}^{-1} is used to map back this smashed data sent by the client to do the training and recover the approximation of the original private data.

Figure 8 – Visual invertibility inference attack: First row shows the original images (image size: 28×28) from the MNIST dataset. Second row shows the ATm after the first Conv2D layer before the first max-pooling operation (image size: 24×24). Third row displays the ATm after the second Conv2D layer before the second max-pooling operation (image size: 8×8).

Visual invertibility inference attack VI serves as a privacy assessment metric designed to measure the correlations between the split layer ATm and original raw data samples. The underlying concept of VIIA involves the client initially training its part of the model to create the ATm . Afterwards, the client sends the ATm to the server. Upon reception, if the server is malicious, it could exploit the received ATm to extract private information by inferring the client's raw data and the corresponding truth label. In essence, VIIA assesses the risk for unintended data exposure during the model's collaborative learning process. In our SL setup, the client computes f_{θ_C} before outsourcing the remaining operations to a server. The client must share ATm to the server for computing f_{θ_P} . However, ATm have patterns that are very similar to the raw image data and cause a privacy leakage. This similarity is visible in [Figure 8](#), where the first row shows the raw image data and the second and third rows show intermediate outputs

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

after the first and second Conv2D layers respectively. Even though the similarities are reduced after the second Conv2D layer, the ADV could extract some information and features of the private data, compromising the client's data privacy.

Security analysis With our threat model established, we can now move forward to demonstrate the security of our protocol.

Proposition 2 (FSHA Soundness). *Let ADV be a semi-honest adversary that corrupts at most one of the two servers (P_0 or P_1) involved in the protocol. Then ADV cannot launch a successful FSHA.*

Proof. Let ADV be a semi-honest adversary that has compromised P_0 or P_1 . In addition to that, assume $f_j, j \in [0, 1]$ be the key distribution of an arbitrary function f . Then, if ADV can only distinguish the key distribution f_j from another f'_j (for some other function f'), with negligible probability then our protocol is secure against the FSHA.

To show that ADV can only distinguish between these values with negligible probability, we will use a proof by contradiction. Let's assume the opposite, that ADV can distinguish from which function (f or f') the key came from. This means that ADV has a non-negligible advantage to correctly determine whether the key came from f or f' .

To test this assumption, let's consider a security game, where ADV has access to both f and f' and receives f_j from a challenger $CHAL$:

Following this game, the ADV would have a method to correctly guess which function the key f_j represents, through the bit b' , so that $b' == b$. However, the key f_j is generated in such a way, that it does not reveal any information about the original function f . As such, the ADV has a 50% chance of successfully guessing the original function, just like flipping a fair coin with a negligible advantage. This reaches a contradiction because the ADV cannot accurately guess the original function with a non-negligible advantage from the obtained function key f_j .

Now, in order to show the soundness of our protocol against FSHA, we will focus on a scenario where the ADV takes control of one of the servers and leaves the other server and client untouched. The ADV tries to manipulate the feature space or the model's output and to accomplish this the ADV would need to understand the underlying feature space of f_{θ_P} . However, through the use of FSS, f_{θ_P} is split between two servers which makes understanding the model and feature space improbable. Each server holds a share of the function but not the entire function itself. This makes it more challenging for an ADV to compromise the entire model by taking control of one server. Additionally, guessing the function share of the non-compromised server from the share of the compromised server is not possible (2). Hence, we prove that proposed

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

private vanilla SL protocol is secure against FSHA.

<p><u>ADV</u> sends: f and f' to \mathcal{CHAL}</p>	<p><u>ADV</u> guesses: b', where $b' == b$</p>
<p><u>CHAL</u> computes: $b \leftarrow \text{Rand}(\cdot)$, where $b \in \{0, 1\}$; If $b == 0$, $f_j \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda, f)$; Else, $f_j \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda, f')$; \mathcal{CHAL} sends f_j to \mathcal{ADV}</p>	

□

Proposition 3 (VIA Soundness). *Let \mathcal{ADV} be a semi-honest adversary that corrupts at most one of the two servers (P_0 or P_1) involved in the protocol. Then \mathcal{ADV} cannot successfully infer the raw input data through VIA.*

Proof. Let \mathcal{ADV} be a semi-honest adversary that has compromised one of the two servers P_j , $j \in [0, 1]$. In addition, assume a noisy intermediate map $x_{pub} = ATm + \alpha$, where ATm is the original intermediate activation map and α is a set amount of noise. Then, if \mathcal{ADV} cannot acquire ATm from x_{pub} , then our protocol is secure against raw data inference through Visual Invertibility Inference Attack.

The use of FSS addresses the privacy leakage caused by VIA as the ATm is masked with a specific amount of noise ($x_{pub} = ATm + \alpha$) for both servers P_j . Following this a single corrupted server P_j would not be able to discern any additional information from the obtained x_{pub} without guessing the function share held by the other, non-corrupted server as proven in Proposition 2. Additionally, if the \mathcal{ADV} is unable to obtain α , then it is improbable that ATm could be reconstructed through x_{pub} , when an adequate amount of noise is added. To this extent, we also showcase a visualization of the masked ATm from both servers in Figure 9a and Figure 9b to show that x_{pub} becomes unrecognisable to the original convolutions ATm .

□

6.5.2 Performance Analysis

This section covers experimental setup and the results of private SL training protocol using FSS.

Figure 9 – Visual invertibility inference attack with FSS applied: First row shows the original AT_m after the first Conv2D (before the max-pooling operations) from the MNIST dataset. Second row shows what P_0 receives when the FSS protocol is applied. Third row what P_1 receives when the FSS protocol is applied. (a) Image Size: 24×24 ; (b) Image Size: 8×8

Experimental setup. FSS implemented using the PySyft framework⁴ and a modified version of AriaNN⁵. To get a more consistent and reproducible result, we ran experiments a total of 10 times for each experiment, totaling 60 executions of the code with different settings. However, we are reporting the top three results for each model (refer to Table 9). In the experiments we measured the communication costs, training times, and accuracy of the model after each epoch and report the total costs after full training. The communication costs are calculated by measuring the byte length of serialized objects sent through packets. Time measurements are taken by making use of the in-built *time* module from Python. The loss is calculated using mean squared error (MSE).

In terms of HPs, we train all networks with $E = 10$ epochs, $\eta = 0.002$ learning rate, $p = 0.9$ momentum, a batch size of $n = 128$, and the total training data samples $m = 59904$ (as the incomplete final batch is dropped).

6.5.3 Evaluation

This section provides an overview of the outcomes derived from experiments. It is organized into three distinct parts: first, the local models with and without SL are covered. These models run in plaintext without making use of FSS to create a baseline to compare further results and also measure the effects of FSS on the performance of the models.

Plaintext models. As previously mentioned, it's important to note that training the models

⁴<https://github.com/OpenMined/PySyft/tree/ryffel/0.2.x-fix-training>

⁵<https://github.com/LaRiffle/ariann>

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

on plaintext data does not account for FSS. These models consist of both a local model and a standard SL model. We have successfully implemented and replicated the results for these models. After training local model for approximately 10 epochs, we achieved the highest test accuracy at 99.36%, with the second and third highest test accuracies at 99.33% and 99.28%, respectively.

Furthermore, experiments indicate that training the vanilla SL model on plaintext data yield similar accuracy results when compared to training the local model. As illustrated in Table 9, the top three results for the vanilla SL model are 99.29%, 99.28%, and 99.21%. These accuracy values closely align, suggesting that the SL model can be effectively applied to CNN models on the MNIST dataset without experiencing a significant degradation in classification accuracy.

We also consider the training time and communication cost of the vanilla SL model and compare it to the local model. The total training time for 10 epochs is nearly identical, ranging between 1 and 2 minutes. Interestingly, even though the vanilla model involve communication between the client and server to exchange ATm and gradients, their training times remain similar to that of the local model. This similarity arises because the local model's training time encompasses the duration during which the client transmits images to the server. Consequently, both models have nearly the same training times.

Regarding the communication cost, we are considering costs on both the client-side and server-side, as well as the total costs during training and testing. In Table 9 we show the variation between the client-side and server-side communication costs between the local and SL model. We observe that the SL approach has slightly higher server-side communication costs, than the local model, but client-side communications are about $3\times$ larger on the local model. This difference arises from the size of the data being shared as in the local model, the client must send 28×28 images, while in the SL model, the client send the intermediate ATm , which is only 8×8 .

Even though the vanilla SL model provides similar accuracy and has the same training and communication cost when compared to the locally computed model, it is essential to note that the vanilla SL model introduce a privacy leakage, which we mitigate using FSS.

FSS without SL. For benchmarking we used AriaNN [128] – a promising solution for doing PPML on sensitive data. In experimentation, we replicated the results for AriaNN, which we refer to as the private local model. To thoroughly assess and compare the impact of FSS on performance, we initialized two models: one before applying FSS (referred to as the “public local model”) and one after applying FSS, both with the same set of initial weights. Our analysis, clearly indicates that the accuracy obtained before and after applying FSS remains nearly identical. In simpler terms, the implementation of FSS exhibits no noticeable effect on

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Table 9 – Performance comparison: training and testing results for various privacy-preserving models

PETs		Training Statistics			Testing Statistics		
FSS	SL	Client Communication (MB)	Server Communication (MB)	Training Time (minutes)	Training Communication (MB)	Testing Communication (MB)	Testing Accuracy (%)
Public	Local	1931.855552	1.656024	1.4402	1933.511576	313.394140	99.36
		1931.853762	1.656288	1.4307	1933.510050	313.394040	99.33
		1931.854346	1.658358	1.4265	1933.512704	313.394140	99.28
	Vanilla	641.172596	25.745798	1.4183	666.702220	102.522446	99.29
		641.170668	25.745258	1.4324	666.699764	102.522176	99.28
		641.173568	25.746834	1.426	666.704240	102.522820	99.21
Private	Local	3863.333306	3.571760	1288.6959	3866.905066	1253.010860	97.04
		3860.620376	3.574165	1271.6553	3864.194541	1253.010740	97.29
		3861.326498	3.576877	1190.5958	3864.903375	1253.010820	96.71
	Vanilla	1332.080326	3.573196	191.6493	1335.653522	204.857314	97.26
		1332.082984	3.572936	220.4564	1335.655920	204.857348	97.14
		1332.086146	3.574748	161.4921	1335.660894	204.857618	96.89

the performance of the models. As can be seen in [Table 9](#), the private local model achieves an impressive test accuracy of approximately 97.29%, closely followed by accuracies of 97.04% and 97.61%. This showcases that the private local model attains a commendable level of accuracy, lacking only by a modest 2% to 3% when compared to the public local models.

However, when we examine the training time for private local model over 10 epochs, a significant contrast emerges. Private local model necessitates approximately 1288 minutes, which is roughly 900× more time-consuming than the training of the public local models. Additionally, the training communication cost incurred by private local model is 2× higher, and the testing communication cost is 4× greater compared to the public local models. The communication costs reported in [Table 9](#) do not take into account the preprocessing communication costs for transmitting the FSS keys and securely computing each function. The preprocessing costs for the private local model is 10.572851 MB per batch.

In conclusion, private local model demonstrates its potential as a promising solution for maintaining data privacy while achieving commendable accuracy in ML. Nonetheless, it is important to remember that using private local model comes with significant drawbacks in terms of the time it takes to train models and the extra communication needed. This should be carefully weighed when deciding if it is the right choice when selecting a privacy-preserving framework for specific use cases.

Private vanilla SL. The private vanilla SL model addresses privacy concerns in public models while maintaining nearly the same accuracy, experiencing only a 2% reduction compared to both public local and public vanilla models (see [Table 9](#)). This is because, as previously discussed, both SL and FSS can be implemented without a notable reduction in model accuracy. It also achieves comparable accuracy to the private local model in around 192 minutes, a sig-

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

nificant advantage. The shorter training time is due to executing all client-side layers in plain, unlike the private local model, which employs various techniques such as beaver triples (for convolution layers) and FSS (for ReLU). Additionally, the total communication cost of private vanilla SL is $2.9\times$ lower than that of the private local model. Notably, the server-side communication cost for private vanilla SL is remarkably low (similar to the public vanilla SL model), compared to the private local model. It is important to note that private vanilla SL additionally requires 0.119634 MB of preprocessing communications per batch, which is a $88.3\times$ reduction when compared to private local FSS (10.572851 MB per batch). This is because we execute client-side layers on plaintext, whereas private local model involves more interaction between parties, increasing communication costs. In summary, private vanilla SL model outperforms the private local model in terms of training time and communication cost while maintaining similar accuracy. Moreover, it offers better privacy than either public models, though with a slight accuracy trade-off. It is important to mention that private vanilla SL model has higher training time and communication costs compared to the public models.

6.6 Privacy-preserving Video and Audio Classification

As part of our research, we have deeply explored privacy-preserving techniques for image, video, and audio classification. One of our main achievements has been in privacy-preserving image classification, where we addressed both theoretical foundations and practical applications. This included the application of state-of-the-art privacy-preserving techniques to image-based ML tasks, ensuring that sensitive data can be processed without exposing it directly.

However, privacy-preserving video and audio classification presents additional challenges. These data types are more complex and significantly larger in size, requiring much more computational power and storage. Furthermore, the field of PPML is still evolving. In this context, We have done some early theoretical work on privacy-preserving video classification [129, 130]. This preliminary research forms a strong foundation for future implementations.

Considering technical and resource limitations involved in fully deploying such systems, especially given the large size and complexity of video and audio data, which demand advanced algorithms and significant computational power, this work will continue once more efficient techniques and better resources become available.

7 Privacy preserving federated learning

This section introduces four improvements to the privacy of FL implemented as part of the Harpocrates project. To protect against potential privacy breaches during training, PPFL integrates PETs such as secure aggregation, DP and others. These methods obscure or encrypt model updates to prevent the central server or other clients from inferring sensitive data.

The first two solutions described in this section focus on implementing secure aggregation for FL using HE. In particular, PPFL with secure aggregation (Section 7.1) implements a plugin to the Flower FL framework, adding support for secure aggregation using several popular HE schemes and other variants. FL with HE (Section 7.2) extends the Vantage6 FL framework implementing support for secure aggregation with CKKS. In the third subsection (Section 21), we explore the challenge of performing HP tuning in a privacy-preserving way within a FL environment. We propose a method that balances both privacy and accuracy during the tuning process. Then, in subsection 21, we present a framework that combines a privacy-aware time-series data synthesizer with a robust FL aggregation technique, which includes weight tuning for protecting the training process by Byzantin attacks.

7.1 Privacy-preserving federated learning with secure aggregation

FL [15] is a ML approach that allows multiple parties to collaborate on training one global model without sharing their raw training data with others. In FL, each party runs an FL client for local model training and only shares the intermediate results with the server for global model aggregation. The overall goal is to retain data privacy, and in this way local data remains on the local party side, and the global model is trained in a decentralized manner [14]. The FL process is illustrated in 10.

Figure 10 – FL Process

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

However, recent research shows that even the exposure of model parameters may cause leakage of sensitive information [131, 132, 133]. To address these issues, some cryptographic technologies are integrated with FL, leading to PPFL. PPFL leverages various cryptographic technologies, allowing model aggregation in a secure manner where the local updates are not exposed to any other party or the central server during the whole FL process [132, 134]. Various technologies are useful for PPFL, such as DP, SMPC, TEEs and HE [135, 136]. By adding carefully calibrated noise to model parameters, DP algorithms ensure that individual model parameters cannot be efficiently determined [137, 138]. However, achieving strong privacy guarantees with DP requires injecting significant amounts of noise, adversely affecting the accuracy of the global model [139]. SMPC enables multiple parties to jointly compute a function (e.g. FL aggregation) over their private inputs [140]. MPC protocols ensure that no party can learn more information than the output of the function. While MPC offers a strong privacy guarantee without sacrificing model accuracy, it can be very expensive in terms of both computation and communication costs, especially as the number of parties increases [136, 141]. TEEs create secure enclaves where sensitive computations are performed in isolation from the rest of the system [142]. Although the overhead of TEE is minimal, vulnerabilities, like various types of side-channel attacks, could potentially compromise the confidentiality of data processed within TEEs [143]. Worse, preventing such attacks is challenging and costly due to their platform-specific nature [144]. HE [134] enables computations to be performed securely on encrypted data without revealing sensitive information. While HE incurs computational and communication costs as well, recent solutions have shown significantly improved performance, making HE techniques promising for PPFL [145, 136].

7.1.1 Homomorphic Encryption

HE is a cryptographic technology for performing computations, e.g. addition or multiplication, on encrypted data directly [146]. That is, letting E denote the encryption method, and using \oplus to denote the supported operation and \mathcal{M} is the (plain text) message domain, we have

$$E(m_1) \oplus E(m_2) = E(m_1 \oplus m_2), \quad \forall m_1, m_2 \in \mathcal{M}. \quad (8)$$

In this work, we studied three prevalent HE schemes. Flashe [145] is a symmetric additive HE scheme specifically designed for FL (See Section 7.1.2). Both CKKS [147] and BFV [148] are fully HE schemes that support both addition and multiplication without limitations. CKKS [147] can encrypt rational numbers and support approximate arithmetic operations (both additive and multiplicative), producing approximate instead of exact results for homomorphic operations. BFV [148] scheme is another prevalent HE scheme, supporting encryption on integer-type

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 11 – Example Flashe usage

plaintexts. Unlike CKKS, BFV is able to provide exact arithmetic operations on encrypted data. However, for FL, floating-point model parameters need to be quantized into integers before encryption.

In summary, HE imposes several limitations, making implementation challenging. Processing speeds of HE operations are comparatively slow. For instance, the CKKS algorithm can be more than 10,000 times slower than the corresponding (but unencrypted) operations on plaintext [145]. In an FL setting, encrypted data is sent to the server, so communication costs also matter. As HE ciphertexts are larger than the corresponding plaintext, typically by a factor of 10 or more [145], the resulting protocol impact must also be considered [149, 145, 150].

7.1.2 Flashe: A practical symmetric additive HE scheme

To mitigate the problem of extremely low efficiency of classic HE schemes, Jiang et al. proposed *Flashe* [145], which is a lightweight mask-based HE scheme specifically designed for FL. Flashe leverages an elegant mask-based cryptosystem to fulfill the minimum requirements for FL. Fig. 11 illustrates the Flashe process. The seed used for mask generation composes two parameters i, j . $||$ denotes concatenation. In FL i is the client id while j can be set as the number of FL rounds. $F_k : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ represents a pseudorandom function that uses k as the key to map the given value to a random value. The key is shared among all clients. To generate various mask values for all plaintext values, the input of F_k is the concatenation of the seed and the location of each plaintext value.

Note that Flashe reduces the decryption time by defining the minus component as $i + 1$ so that masks cancel each other during the decryption.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

7.1.3 Quantization Method

The ML model parameters are typically floating-point numbers. However, most HE schemes, e.g. BVF and Flashe, focus on the integer domain. We use quantization techniques to map floating-point model parameters to integers. For example, depending on accuracy requirements, an application may, e.g., map 32-bit floating-point numbers into 16-bit integers. The precision of this mapping is determined by the number of bits r used for quantization.

In this work we implement the *symmetric quantization* method proposed in [141]. Let v denote a vector of model parameters and m the quantized values, then quantization is defined as $Q_{\alpha,r}(v) = \text{Sign}(v) \cdot \lceil \lceil (2^{r-1} - 1) \cdot \frac{|v|}{\alpha} \rceil \rceil$, where $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ is the rounding function. Correspondingly, the reverse dequantization process is given by $Q_{\alpha,r}^{-1}(m) = \hat{v} = m \cdot \frac{\alpha}{2^{r-1}-1}$. Obviously, $Q_{\alpha,r}$ maps values in $[-\alpha, \alpha]$ to the (symmetric) interval of $[-(2^{r-1} - 1), 2^{r-1} - 1]$. The rounding in the quantization results in a precision error $e_q \leftarrow |v - \hat{v}|$ which is in the range $[0, \frac{\alpha}{2^{r-1}-1})$.

Although quantization leads to loss of precision, recent work shows that it is often sufficient to use 16-bit variables for quantized model parameters to retain model accuracy [151], which motivates our choice of $r = 16$ in this work. Intuitively, α should be as close as possible to the maximum of the model parameters to cover the whole range while avoiding wasting bits. For more details about choosing α , we referring to the dACIQ clipping method introduced in [141].

7.1.4 The Challenge of Weighted Averaging

In practical scenarios, the clients tend to have different contribution levels, i.e., clients with larger or higher-quality datasets should contribute more to the global model [152, 14]. However, integer-based HE schemes like BFV or Flashe do not support division on ciphertexts, making it more complicated to apply weighted averaging. To get the final aggregated result, weighted aggregation with HE can be implemented using Algorithm 7 [141, 145].

The highest risk for overflows occurs during the weighted summation, as the final summation result can be out of range for the HE representation, which always has strict limitations, e.g. $[-2^{27}, 2^{27}]$. The weights, which might frequently change, greatly increase the possibility of overflowing. Suppose $r = 2^{16}$ of quantization and the weight of one client is the size of the local dataset, which could be much larger than $2^{10} = 1024$. In this case, $W \leftarrow \sum_{i \in I} w_i$ is probably larger than 2^{16} (if the client count $N \geq 4$), making overflows in $\sum w_i m_i$ probable if the range of HE is $[-2^{27}, 2^{27}]$. To mitigate this problem, we introduce our solution in heflp.

7.1.5 Threat Model

The threat model we consider in this work includes two types of adversaries.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Algorithm 7 Classic Weighted Aggregation

Aggregator:

- 1: **for** each training round **do**
- 2: Collect all encrypted model updates $E_k(m_i)$
- 3: $g \leftarrow E_k(\sum_{i \in I} m_i w_i) = \sum_{i \in I} E_k(m_i) \cdot w_i$ ▷ Weighted Summation
- 4: Compute total weight $W \leftarrow \sum_{i \in I} w_i$
- 5: Dispatch g, W to the clients
- 6: **end for**

Client i :

param: $i \in I, \alpha, r, k$

- 1: **for** each training round **do**
 - 2: Get model parameters v_i after training
 - 3: Set weight w_i as the size of the local dataset
 - 4: $m_i \leftarrow Q_{\alpha, r}(v_i)$ ▷ Quantization
 - 5: Compute encrypted update $E_k(m_i)$ using key $\{k\}$
 - 6: Send $E_k(m_i), w_i$ to the Aggregator
 - 7: ...
 - 8: Receive g, W from the Aggregator
 - 9: Decrypt and dequantize $\sum_{i \in I} \hat{v}_i w_i = Q_{\alpha, r}^{-1}(D_k(g))$
 - 10: Obtain the aggregated result $\hat{v} \leftarrow \sum_{i \in I} \frac{\hat{v}_i w_i}{W}$
 - 11: Trigger next round of training
 - 12: **end for**
-

1. The **server adversary** who is *honest-but-curious*. It can access all the data received from other parties or stored in memory, including the model updates of clients, the aggregated results, and all the relevant settings maintained by the central server. The adversary does not aim to break the FL process but tries to infer both the local model parameters of clients and the global model parameters.
2. The **client adversaries** who perform as *honest-but-curious* clients. The adversaries are valid clients, having all the necessary data for FL, e.g. the keys for communication and HE encryption, local dataset for training, and local model. However, one client adversary is able to eavesdrop on the messages sent from other clients to the central server. It aims to infer the local models that contain sensitive information but do not belong to them, violating the data privacy of other parties, without harming their benefits of FL collaboration or leaking their own sensitive data.

Our solution allows the cooperation of client adversaries. However, we assume that at least two clients are honest, in order to maintain the security guarantees. Collusion of different types of adversaries is out of the scope of this work.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 12 – An example of Flashev2

7.1.6 Heflp

Flashev2: An Improved Version of Flashe Although Flashe is a good HE scheme choice specifically for FL, it faces some shortcomings:

1. Since the rule to set i and j is public and all the clients use the same key for both encryption and decryption, if one malicious user is able to obtain the encrypted models from other benign users, it can recover the plaintext by using its key.
2. Flashe only supports additive operation and does not allow the multiplication between ciphertext and a constant, thus it is impossible to calculate the weighted average of multiple Flashe ciphertext.

To address these problems, we optimized and modified Flashe's cryptosystem. The optimizations rely on two ideas: 1. Replace the i and j with a customized item p and let the server define $S : \{p_1, p_2, \dots\}$ for encryption so that the S_i of each client remains private, enhancing the privacy between clients. 2. Attach one t parameter to each item p in $S : \{(p_1, t_1), (p_2, t_2), \dots\}$, which specifies the multiplier when adding the masks to plaintext or removing them from the ciphertext. The revised version of Flashe is named as *Flashev2*. Similarly, we give another example of Fig. 12 to show the process of Flashev2.

Mask precomputation As shown in Fig. 12, not like CKKS or BFV, the masks used for Flashev2 encryption are independent of the model parameters. So one effective trick to save the time of Flashev2 encryption involves computing the encryption masks in advance while training the model, which we called mask pre-computation. It leverages idle CPU resources to effectively eliminate the time overhead for encryption.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 13 – MAE comparison

MWAvg: A Practical Weighted Averaging Strategy To address the challenge of overflowing explained in Section 7.1.4, we proposed an advanced weighted averaging strategy by rescaling its range as early as possible. We call this strategy *MWAvg*.

Considering the refactored formula of weighted averaging:

$$\bar{v} = \frac{\sum_{i \in I} v_i w_i}{W} = \left(\sum_{i \in I} v_i \cdot \epsilon_i \cdot \frac{\mu_i}{M} \right) \cdot \frac{M}{W} \quad \text{where} \quad (9)$$

$$\epsilon_i = \frac{w_i}{\mu_i}, \quad \mu_i = 2^{\lceil \log_2(w_i) \rceil} \in [w_i, 2w_i), \quad w_i > 0.5 \quad \forall i \in I$$

$$M = \min(\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots), \quad W = \sum_{i \in I} w_i$$

where v_i is any model parameter of client i participating in weighted averaging and \bar{v} is the averaging result.

The idea is to first rescale the arbitrary weight w_i to range $(0, 1]$ so that the model parameters can be multiplied with it before quantization while keeping the same clipping threshold α . As shown in Equation 9, we transform weight w_i into $\epsilon_i \leftarrow \frac{w_i}{\mu_i}$. Because $\mu_i = 2^{\lceil \log_2(w_i) \rceil} \in [w_i, 2w_i)$, we can get $\epsilon_i \in (0.5, 1]$ that fits the requirement. To generalize μ_i so that the final result is correct, each ϵ_i is multiplied with $\frac{\mu_i}{M}$. M is the minimum value among all μ_i , therefore, $\frac{\mu_i}{M}$ is an integer power of 2 as well. As M has nothing to do with client id i , the item $\frac{M}{W}$ can be moved outside of summation. By implementing MWAvg into weighted aggregation, we propose Algorithm 8. Considering that each received model update might be large and should be processed immediately to avoid wasting memory, we implement an incremental summation upon weighted summation in order to dynamically adjust M .

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

With the approach described above, the result of weighted summation g is M times smaller, mitigating the risk of overflows.

Fig 13 shows the comparison of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) $\bar{e} \leftarrow \frac{\sum |\hat{v} - \bar{v}|}{l}$ between classic WAvg and MWAvg. l denotes the length of \hat{v} or \bar{v} . The MAE of MWAvg keeps decreasing⁶ but the MAE of classic weighted aggregation grows sharply when the client count is over about 1000, indicating that overflowing occurs. Actually, the position of this inflection point depends on the experimental setting. The disadvantage of MWAvg is that, because the original values are multiplied by $\epsilon_i \in (0.5, 1]$ before quantization, it will result in a maximum 2x higher error of quantization if $\epsilon_i \rightarrow 0.5$, compared to the classic weighted aggregation. That is also why the line of MWAvg is slightly higher in Fig. 13.

7.1.7 MWAvg with M-prime

One advantage of Flashev2 is the ability to let masks of the same p item and reverse t item cancel each other during aggregation. However, according to Equation. 10, multiplication on the ciphertext will change item t , breaking the mask canceling.

$$(c_1, j, S_1) \oplus (c_2, j, S_2) = (c_1 + c_2, j, S_1 \cup S_2) \quad (10)$$

$$(c, S) \otimes L = (c \cdot L, S^L) \quad \text{where} \quad (11)$$

$$p' = p, t' = t \cdot L \quad \forall (p', t') \in S^L, (p, t) \in S$$

To address this issue, we leverage a practical feature called **M-prime**, which allows clients to negotiate a M' after the first round of training, then divide the model parameters by M' in advance of the MWAvg process. The relevant steps are noted in blue in Algorithm 8. M' is initialized as 1 and updated by $M' \leftarrow M' \cdot \frac{\max(w_i) + \max(\mu_i)}{2}$. Ideally, if the weights of clients are smaller than M' , after the transformation $w_i \leftarrow \frac{w_i}{M'}$ all the μ of MWAvg will be equal to 1, so that Flashev2 can maintain the mask-canceling advantage. Even if the weights change and become larger than M' in the next round of training, it will only impact the efficiency of decryption, with no negative effect on the correctness, which is guaranteed by MWAvg.

7.1.8 MWAvg with Flashev2

Except for Flashev2 with MWAvg, some alternatives can also achieve similar functionality, i.e., reducing the risk of overflow while handling arbitrary weights for a large number of clients in

⁶The MAE decreases with the increase of client count because the more clients that participate in FL, the more random error resulted by quantization and encryption can be eliminated by each other after doing the aggregation.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Algorithm 8 Weighted Aggregation with MWAVg

Aggregator:

```
1: Initialize  $M' \leftarrow 1$ 
2: for each training round do
3:   Initialize  $M \leftarrow \infty, g \leftarrow 0$ 
4:   for received model update  $E_k(m_i)$  do
5:     if  $\mu_i < M$  then
6:        $g \leftarrow g \cdot \frac{M}{\mu_i} + E_k(m_i)$  ▷ Incremental Summation
7:        $M \leftarrow \mu_i$  ▷ Update  $M$ 
8:     else
9:        $g \leftarrow g \cdot + E_k(m_i) \cdot \frac{\mu_i}{M}$  ▷ Weighted Summation
10:    end if
11:  end for
12:  Compute total weight  $W \leftarrow \sum_{i \in I} w_i$ 
13:  Update  $M' \leftarrow M' \cdot \frac{\max(w_i) + \max(\mu_i)}{2}$ 
14:  Dispatch  $g, \frac{M}{W}, M'$  to the clients
15: end for
```

Client i :

param: $i \in I, \alpha, r, k$

```
1: for each training round do
2:   Get model parameters  $v_i$  after training
3:   Set weight  $w_i$  as the size of the local dataset
4:    $w_i \leftarrow \frac{w_i}{M'}$ 
5:   Calculate  $\mu_i, \epsilon_i$  according to Equation 9
6:    $m_i \leftarrow Q_{\alpha, r}(v_i \cdot \epsilon_i)$  ▷ Quantization
7:   Compute encrypted update  $E_k(m_i)$  using key  $\{k\}$ 
8:   Send  $E_k(m_i), w_i, \mu_i$  to the Aggregator
9:   ...
10:  Receive  $g, \frac{M}{W}, M'$  from the Aggregator
11:  Decrypt and dequantize  $\sum_{i \in I} \hat{v}_i w_i = Q_{\alpha, r}^{-1}(D_k(g))$ 
12:  Obtain the aggregated result  $\hat{v} \leftarrow (\sum_{i \in I} \hat{v}_i w_i) \cdot \frac{M}{W}$ 
13:  Trigger next round of training
14: end for
```

the context of HE-enabled FL. For instance, before sending the model updates to the server, each client can communicate with each other to know the range of weights of all clients so that all the weights can be rescaled according to an appropriate factor. However, this approach requires additional steps for information exchange between the server and clients, increasing the communication overhead and possibly causing longer latency. Moreover, these additional steps make the FL process more complicated, increasing the difficulty of its implementation to existing FL frameworks. Flashev2/MWAVg, instead, transmits the additional information (μ, M') along with model updates, with several additional bytes of communication overhead.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 14 – System overview

Another alternative can be sending the weights and model updates directly to the server. In this case, each client only conducts the quantization and encryption without multiplying the model parameters by weight in advance. After receiving the weight and the encrypted model parameters, the server can rescale the weights and do the weighted summation. For example, the server can transform weights 1000, 1180 to 10, 12. However, as explained in Section 7.1.4, for the integer-based HE schemes, the weights after processed by the server should be integers as well. Therefore, as the example indicates, the price of rescaling might be the precision of weights. MWAvg avoids this problem by carefully offloading part of the rescaling task to each client, with a minimal computational cost to calculate μ_i and update M during aggregation.

7.1.9 Implementation

The system implements a client-server architecture (see Fig. 14). The client side consists of multiple client instances, each operated by a distinct contributing party. The server side only represents one server application that runs on the cloud platform and provides the aggregation service for FL. Each client maintains one TLS connection with the server and transmits data on it [153].

Each client runs two core components (underlined in Fig. 14). The local training component trains the received model on the private local dataset. After training, the local model is forwarded to the HE cipher component. The cipher uses MWAvg and a certain HE scheme to quantize and encrypt the received model parameters from local training. The client then transmits the encrypted data to the server. Accordingly, it is also responsible for decrypting the received data from the server using the same HE configuration, then forwarding the decrypted model parameters to the local training component to trigger the next round of training.

The server includes one aggregator for aggregating the received model weights and one FL controller to manage the FL and HE configuration (underlined in Fig. 14). The aggregator re-

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

security through additional HE mechanisms. The designed framework supports multiple HE schemes but follows a similar procedure. As shown in Fig. 15, the process consists of three stages: the initial setup, FL training, and completion.

Stage 1: Initial Setup The first stage is the initial setup of the framework, including the initialization of HE cipher and quantizer in each client, the setup of the clients and the server, and the building of communication channels between the clients and the server. In this stage, the FL controller inside the server also loads an initial model and generates the corresponding configurations (explained above), then sends them to all clients and waits until receiving a predetermined number of responses from clients. Each client installs the received initial model and sets up the local training environment according to the received configuration parameters.

Stage 2: FL Training The second stage is the main part of FL process. In this stage, all clients collaborate on training the global model iteratively with the help of the aggregation server until achieving the convergence of model training or the maximum number of rounds preset in the initial setup. In each round, each client first trains the model on its local dataset. Then all local models are transmitted to the server after being quantized (if required by the HE scheme) and encrypted. Considering that when using specific HE schemes clients may also need to send some additional data, e.g. quantization parameters and the range of model weights, an optional field called metadata is attached as well. After receiving enough updates from clients, the server aggregates all the received local models and updates the configuration for each client, then sends back the updated global model to clients with corresponding configurations. On the client side, each client can obtain the global model by decoding the received message with the same quantizer and cipher. Before moving on to the next round of training, the server requires a predetermined number of clients to evaluate the performance of the updated global model and send back the evaluation results so that it can collect, record, and analyze such kind of information to monitor the training process and make a better decision about whether to stop training earlier. The evaluation results can also be helpful for other purposes such as setting better training configurations and evaluating the effects of different HE schemes and FL algorithms on convergence speed or global accuracy. However, it always takes additional time and the users need to evaluate the trade-off.

Stage 3: Completion The last stage is to complete training. When the global model is converged or the training reaches the maximum number of rounds, the server stops and instructs clients to end the FL process as well.

7.1.11 Evaluation

We next evaluate several aspects of the performance of the Heflp design and implementation.

Error Rate

To evaluate the effects of HE schemes on the model training, we conduct one experiment to evaluate the MAE of aggregation results of all HE schemes that Heflp supports. The MAE between the estimated result \hat{v} and the theoretical result \bar{v} is defined as $\bar{e} \leftarrow \frac{\sum |\hat{v} - \bar{v}|}{l}$. l denotes the length of vector \hat{v} and \bar{v} . Considering the impact of weights of clients on the performance of MWAVg, the experiment is divided into two tests, a uniform test and a nonuniform test. For the three integer-based HE approaches (Flashe, Flashev2, BFV), quantization is the main reason for the error. Therefore, three r -bit quantizations are evaluated ($r = 16/18/20$).

Figure 16 – Error rate evaluation of CKKS, BFV+MWAVg, Flashe and Flashev2+MWAVg+M-prime. (a) The results of the uniform test, where the weights of all clients are the same. (b) The results of the nonuniform test, where the weights of clients vary.

The uniform test sets 5 clients equally, each of which shares the same weight of 500 (as an example, actually any weight value is valid). In this setting the aggregation is simply calculating the average of all received model updates.

The nonuniform test allocates various weights to the 5 clients (1k, 2k, 3k, 4k, and 5k). Thus, the weighted averaging strategy plays an important role in the aggregation.

Efficiency

Evaluation Settings To evaluate the efficiency of different HE schemes, the average time costs of encryption and decryption of one client and the aggregation are recorded respectively. The sizes of ciphertext are collected as well, indicating the traffic overhead.

When conducting the experiments for various scenarios, three main aspects of use cases are considered:

1. Model Type: three types of ML models of different scales are selected for experiments. They are a 5-layer FCN (49.7k parameters), An LSTM model (215.2k parameters), and a MobileNet model (2.13M parameters).
2. Number of clients: we conduct our experiments when the client count is 5 / 10 / 20.
3. Weights of clients: The weights can influence MWAvg and have a relatively big impact on the performance of the Flashev2 scheme. So this experiment considers the worst case where the weights of clients are diverse (in [1000, 5000]).

Figure 17 – Results of the time efficiency test when the weights of clients are in the range [1000, 5000]. Fv2+ denotes Flashev2+MWAvg without M-prime.

Evaluation of Time Cost When fixing the model type as LSTM, we get the results shown in Fig. 17. Flashe and Flashev2 almost spent no time on aggregation. However, CKKS and BFV take much time to execute homomorphic operations when aggregating model updates, resulting in higher total time costs as the number of clients increases. What is more, it is clear that Flashe’s encryption and decryption have approximately the same time cost, even though the client weights are diverse. But for Flashev2 the mask-canceling can be impacted when the weights are significantly different. If the MWAvg multiplicative factor of client i and $i + 1$ are $\mu_i \neq \mu_{i+1}$, the Flashev2 masks cannot cancel each other, causing a higher time cost of decryption than encryption. By applying M-prime and mask-precomputation, the time cost of Flashev2 is significantly reduced, making it the most efficient alternative, especially when the number of clients is large.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 18 – Results of the time efficiency test for three models: FCN (49.7k parameters), LSTM (215.2k parameters), and MobileNet (2.13M parameters).

Fig. 18 shows the time cost of three types of models. Considering the scale of parameters, the MobileNet model is about 10 times larger than LSTM, while LSTM is about 4 times larger than FCN. The total time costs of each HE scheme also have approximately the same proportions. Therefore, we argue that there is an approximate linear relationship between the time cost and the scale of model parameters, which applies to all HE schemes.

Model Type	Plaintext Size	Ciphertext Size - Plaintext Size			
		Flashe	CKKS	BFV+	Fv2++
FCN	198KB	4B	6.81MB	7.81MB	0.11KB
LSTM	861KB	4B	26.16MB	27.16MB	0.11KB
MobileNet	8737KB	4B	265.5MB	265.48MB	0.11KB

Table 10 – Results of the communication overhead test for three models.

Evaluation of Communication Overhead To evaluate the communication overheads, we collected the byte data of models when transmitting to the server in various settings. The results are shown in Table 10. Flashe and Flashev2 add masks directly to the plaintext and thus do not increase the size of ciphertext (except several bytes of metadata). The encryption of BFV and CKKS relies on complex cryptography primitives, making a ciphertext about 32 times larger than the plaintext. Therefore, Flashe and Flashev2 can significantly reduce network overhead compared to CKKS and BFV, especially when the number of clients or the model scale is large.

Training Performance To evaluate the effects of HE mechanisms on the FL training process, two simulations run on the MNIST dataset and the TI dataset. One VM instance is set as the FL server, while another VM instance simulates three clients. The simulated clients connect to the server while setting up the FL training process together. To monitor the training curve, the performance of the global model is recorded after each round of training. For the test on the MNIST dataset, the model used for training is a 5-layer FCN model, and the evaluation metric

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

is the accuracy (or *Acc*) defined as the number of correct classifications divided by the total number of test samples. The test on TI dataset uses an LSTM for training and chooses MSE as the evaluation metric. The centralized training without FL also runs on the client VM in order to compare the performance between the FL and centralized training.

Figure 19 – (a) The training curve of the FCN model using metric *Acc* on MNIST dataset. (b) The training curve of the LSTM model using metric *MSE* on TI dataset.

After running the simulation, the results of the two tests are shown in Fig. 19. From the curves, it is clear that for both FL training on the MNIST dataset and TI dataset, the model has a similar evaluation result no matter if it applies HE and which HE scheme is used. This observation confirms that under the given settings, the HE security mechanisms do not sacrifice the benefits of FL training. The FL training has a slower convergence speed than the centralized training. It is caused by FL itself instead of the HE schemes we discuss in this paper [14, 154].

7.1.12 Conclusion

In this section we described Heflp, enabling a PPFL framework powered by HE for security and an advanced quantization approach for scalability. Through a series of evaluations, we show that the proposed Flashev2 with MWAvg is able to achieve higher time and network efficiency while retaining the protection in the FL process compared to the other three HE schemes (Flashe, CKKS, and BFV). The practicality of Heflp is proved by simulating the FL training process on the TI dataset and MNIST dataset and evaluating its security and performances correspondingly, which shows that Heflp is able to protect data confidentiality during the whole lifecycle of FL training from the predefined adversaries while retaining the time and spatial efficiency.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

7.2 Federated learning with homomorphic encryption

This section presents a PPFL architecture that integrates HE using the CKKS scheme, implemented via the Pyfhel library, within the Vantage6 framework. The proposed system enables secure collaborative training across multiple nodes while ensuring that model updates remain encrypted end-to-end. All computations are containerized using Docker and orchestrated by Vantage6, providing modularity, reproducibility, and verifiability. The following subsections describe the proposed solution, threat model, system architecture, and implementation workflow.

7.2.1 Proposed Solution

To mitigate the security and privacy challenges inherent in FL systems, we propose an enhanced architecture that integrates HE with a containerized FL workflow. Each participating node performs local training on private data, encrypts model parameters using the CKKS scheme, and transmits only ciphertexts to a central server. The server performs aggregation directly over encrypted data, without access to any plaintext model updates or private keys.

This design leverages the Pyfhel library for HE operations and runs entirely within the Vantage6 infrastructure. Containerized execution ensures isolation and verifiability of algorithms, while CKKS supports approximate arithmetic on real-valued encrypted vectors, making it well-suited for ML tasks. The result is a secure, scalable, and modular FL system suitable for deployment in sensitive application domains such as healthcare and finance.

7.2.2 Threat Model

In the proposed system, the primary threat comes from a semi-honest (honest-but-curious) central server, which may attempt to analyze models to extract private information, as well as from potentially malicious nodes that could manipulate the model through model poisoning or data poisoning attacks. However, by integrating HE with FL, proposed system mitigates these risks and ensures data privacy throughout the entire training process. The central server receives only encrypted model updates and performs aggregation operations directly on ciphertexts. It never accesses any decrypted intermediate or final results.

7.2.3 Architecture System and Components

This integration has been implemented within the Vantage6 FL environment, where all computations are performed in isolated Docker containers. Vantage6 serves as the orchestration layer, managing FL tasks while ensuring data privacy throughout the model training process. All data operations are confined within isolated Docker environments, and the integration of

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Docker Notary technology guarantees that only verified and authenticated algorithms are executed, enhancing system security and integrity.

The system consists of several key components:

- Client (User): Initiates tasks processed by the server and executed on nodes, defines tasks and algorithms, and analyzes the results generated from computations.
- Algorithm: A set of predefined instructions or code designed to accomplish a specific objective. It is packaged as a Docker image, which runs within the FL infrastructure. The algorithm is extended with Pyfhel-based encryption and decryption logic using the CKKS scheme. It supports three core operations: encryption of local model updates, homomorphic aggregation at the central level, and local decryption of aggregated models.
- Node: Executes the algorithm contained within the Docker image on local data. It receives tasks from the server, downloads the necessary Docker image, runs the algorithm, and returns the computed results to the server. After training, model updates are encrypted locally and securely transmitted to the server.

Figure 20 – Node architecture

Server (Master): Acts as the central coordination point, managing task processing and handling administrative functions such as authentication and authorization. It distributes algorithms as Docker images to nodes, ensuring they are both secure and compatible. Additionally, it collects results from nodes and facilitates communication between researchers and participating nodes. In HE-enabled workflows, the server performs only operations on encrypted data. It is never in possession of private keys and cannot decrypt any of the model updates or final aggregated results.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 21 – Server architecture

To ensure additional privacy guarantees within the FL framework, the system integrates HE using the CKKS scheme. CKKS is particularly suitable for ML tasks because it enables approximate arithmetic over encrypted real-valued vectors, supporting essential operations such as addition and multiplication directly on ciphertexts. This allows encrypted model parameters—such as weights and biases—to be aggregated without requiring decryption at any stage of the workflow. In addition, CKKS offers semantic security by introducing randomness during the encryption process, ensuring that identical plaintexts yield different ciphertexts across multiple encryptions. This property prevents frequency-based or pattern-based attacks on the encrypted parameters. The Pyfhel library is used to implement CKKS in this system. Pyfhel provides a convenient Python interface for managing cryptographic contexts, generating keys, and executing encrypted computations. Each node generates its encryption parameters locally, including the polynomial modulus degree, scaling factor, and coefficient modulus, ensuring that security, performance, and precision are balanced according to the needs of the specific learning task. All encryption and decryption operations are executed within the secure, isolated environment of each Docker container at the node level. Model updates are encrypted immediately after training and sent to the central server in ciphertext form. The server then performs homomorphic aggregation without ever accessing plaintext values or holding any private keys. This design ensures that raw data and intermediate model states are never exposed, even to the central coordinating server, offering robust protection against both passive eavesdropping and active inference attacks. As demonstrated in benchmarking studies such as Jiang Ju (2022), CKKS offers an optimal trade-off between functionality, security, and performance in FL scenarios—particularly when dealing with real-number computations and gradient-based models [155].

7.2.4 Workflow Execution

The overall execution flow of the proposed PPFL system is illustrated in Figure 22, which shows the interaction between the client, central server, and nodes within the Vantage6 infrastructure, alongside the HE and aggregation stages.

Figure 22 – Sequence diagram of the HE-enhanced FL workflow

The process begins when the client defines a FL task, selects the appropriate algorithm (packaged as a Docker image), and submits the task via the central server. The server then distributes the task to participating nodes, each of which pulls the image and prepares the environment for execution. At the beginning of execution, each Docker container—deployed as part of the Vantage6 infrastructure—initializes a secure encryption environment. This setup includes the definition of the encryption context and parameters, such as the polynomial modulus degree, scaling factor, and precision level, tailored for approximate arithmetic on real numbers as supported by the CKKS scheme. These cryptographic parameters are generated as part of the algorithm.

Once the encryption environment is established, the algorithm proceeds with local data pro-

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

cessing. This includes essential preprocessing tasks such as handling missing values, encoding categorical features, and normalizing input variables. These steps are critical to preparing the data for training, especially in real-world federated settings where datasets across organizations may differ in format and quality. Following preprocessing, the algorithm trains a logistic regression model on the local dataset using conventional ML libraries. The model itself is constructed in plaintext, but its resulting parameters - the learned weights and intercept - are encrypted before any communication with the central server takes place. Encryption is performed using the public key associated with the CKKS context, and all sensitive outputs remain encrypted throughout their transmission. The encrypted parameters are then sent to the central server, which acts purely as an orchestrator and aggregator. The server performs aggregation operations directly on the ciphertexts without access to any private decryption keys. This design ensures that even if the server is compromised or behaves in a semi-honest manner, it cannot infer any meaningful information about the data or models trained at individual nodes.

Upon receiving the encrypted model updates from all participating nodes, the central server performs secure aggregation directly on the ciphertexts. Since the server does not possess any decryption key, it acts purely as a computational orchestrator, incapable of accessing any individual contribution or inferring sensitive patterns. The aggregated encrypted model can then be used as the initial model for the next training round.

7.2.5 Conclusion

We introduced a PPFL pipeline that integrates HE using the CKKS scheme within the Vantage6 framework. The system enables secure training across multiple organizations by ensuring that model updates are encrypted end-to-end and never exposed in plaintext. Each node performs local training, encrypts its model parameters using a shared encryption context, and transmits only ciphertexts to the central server, which aggregates them without access to any secret keys. This architecture offers strong privacy guarantees aligned with GDPR principles: sensitive data remains local, and all communications are protected both in transit and at rest. The use of CKKS is particularly suitable for ML tasks involving real-valued computations, enabling efficient and secure aggregation of encrypted model weights. Nevertheless, several practical challenges remain. HE introduces computational and communication overhead, especially due to ciphertext size and noise accumulation. Maintaining compatibility across nodes requires precise coordination of encryption parameters. While key management is decoupled from the server, robust synchronization between participants is essential to ensure protocol correctness. In summary, the proposed architecture provides a modular and scalable foundation for PPFL in sensitive domains. Future work will focus on performance optimization, integration of hybrid privacy mechanisms such as DP, and exploring decentralized approaches to key management

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

and orchestration.

7.3 Privacy-Preserving Hyperparameter Tuning for Federated Learning

7.3.1 Introduction

While recent research has exhaustively studied the convergence of the global model for various distributed learning algorithms [156, 157, 158, 159], little effort has been devoted to tuning HPs which might affect the performance and accuracy of FL given its collaborative nature [160, 161]. Traditional HP tuning techniques, such as grid/random search or Bayesian optimization, due to their iterative operation, introduce significant computation and communication overhead making them impractical for FL settings. Moreover, their tuning performance on heterogeneous, non-iid data remains unclear.

Although the FL training process ensures that sensitive data does not leave the clients' local premises, recent research has shown that it does not provide strong levels of privacy as model updates leak information about the training data [162, 163, 164, 165, 166, 167, 168, 169, 170]. To mitigate the risk of privacy leakage, researchers have proposed PPFL solutions employing PETs such as (i) DP [171, 172, 173, 174, 175, 176], (ii) secure multiparty computation (MPC) [75, 177, 178, 179, 180, 181, 29, 182, 183, 184, 185], or (iii) HE [186, 187, 188]. While all these solutions are crucial for preserving data privacy in FL, they assume that HPs, such as learning rate and momentum, are somehow predefined and configured. Performing HP tuning in the presence of PETs for FL becomes even more challenging given their modus operandi, e.g., DP solutions need to spend a significant portion of the privacy budget on the HP tuning itself, while MPC/HE approaches incur significant communication/computation overhead and thus cannot tolerate additional training iterations for HP tuning. As a result, there is a need for efficient HP tuning solutions for PPFL.

Existing *efficient* HP tuning methods for FL, such as FLoRa [1], rely on the *single-shot* HP tuning paradigm: Each client locally discovers its optimal set of HPs and communicates it to the central server that decides the most suitable HPs for FL before the training process starts. However, sharing local HPs with the FL server might result in new forms of privacy leakage as prior work has shown that data samples with special attributes, e.g., outliers, can noticeably skew the optimal HP configuration and remain vulnerable to privacy attacks such as membership inference [189]. While employing noise-based techniques during HP tuning is a potential solution [189, 190], these might severely degrade the utility and the performance of the trained model, highlighting the need for efficient methods that ensure both privacy and accuracy in federated HP tuning.

We aim to address this research gap by proposing an efficient and accurate method for tun-

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 23 – Our HP tuning method for cross-silo FL. hp_k and hp_g denote the local best HP configuration at client k and the global best configuration (denoted by g), respectively.

ing HPs in cross-silo FL, compatible with PPFL pipelines. Following the single-shot HP tuning paradigm [1], we let each client discover their optimal HPs locally and we combine them in a privacy-preserving manner at the central server (Figure 23). To understand how to combine client-found local HPs at the server side, we conduct a comprehensive measurement study across various datasets and model architectures, simulating both iid and non-iid FL settings, and benchmark diverse strategies. Inspired by aggregation methods commonly used in FL, we employ a variety of strategies such as computing the mean [191], the median [192, 193], the trimmed mean [192], trimmed mean/median with the highest validation accuracy, and density-based clustering [194, 195], and we compare their performance. Our study reveals that HP averaging is simple and effective for iid settings, while density-based clustering identifies optimal HPs in non-iid settings. Then, to protect the privacy of the clients' local HPs (hence, their sensitive data) we design a novel framework, PRIVTUNA, that facilitates their privacy-preserving combination at the server using multi-party HE (MHE) techniques. We use PRIVTUNA to implement two privacy-preserving combination strategies for HP tuning, i.e., federated mean and density-based clustering, and we evaluate its performance in terms of computation/communication overhead and HP tuning precision.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

7.3.2 Related Work

We review related work on HP tuning for centralized and decentralized ML and discuss the privacy aspects of HPs.

Centralized Hyperparameter Tuning. Several well-established HP tuning techniques, such as grid search, exist for centralized data contexts [196, 197], random search [198], Bayesian [199] or evolutionary optimization [200]. However, adapting these techniques to FL is challenging due to their iterative nature; they require multiple rounds of model training, resulting in significant communication overhead in FL's collaborative training process. This overhead is exacerbated when PETs (e.g., MPC or HE) are used to strengthen the privacy of FL.

Decentralized HP Tuning. Several works focus on neural architecture search (NAS) solutions tailored to FL. Khodak et al. propose weight-sharing techniques for FL-HP tuning [201, 202]. However, prior work shows that weight sharing in FL raises significant privacy concerns [162, 163, 164, 165, 166, 167, 168]. Other works propose performing NAS offline [203, 204], i.e., before the federated training starts, or online [205, 206], i.e., the HP optimization (HPO) and the training are done simultaneously. However, offline NAS for FL requires a high number of communication rounds while online ones introduce significant computation overhead [207]. We note that our focus is on tuning the FL server HPs and not the model architecture.

Zhang et al. automate FL-HP tuning, adjusting parameters like training rounds and client numbers while respecting application-specific preferences [208]. Agrawal et al. cluster FL clients based on their HPs, updated through a genetic algorithm [194]. Chen et al. propose an online *tuning while training* method, and Dai et al. adapt Bayesian optimization to FL by employing Federated Thompson Sampling [209]. Mostofa proposes a representation matching scheme to reduce local-global model divergence and introduces adaptive HP tuning [210]. Kuo et al. suggest performing HP tuning on public proxy data to address the challenges of data heterogeneity and privacy [161]. While these solutions advance HP tuning in FL, they are unsuitable for PPFL, as they require access to the federated model, which is protected by PETs like MPC or HE in high-privacy settings. Moreover, they introduce significant communication and computation overhead which is exacerbated in the presence of PETs.

To address the communication efficiency issue of prior FL HP tuning approaches, Zhou et al. propose FLoRA, a single-shot HP tuning approach [1]. FLoRa discovers the optimal server HPs based on the local HPs of the clients by projecting them to a unified loss surface with various techniques. Our work differs in two ways: (i) we employ as ground truth a realistic baseline through federated grid search, while FLoRA only considers the default HP set of scikit-learn algorithms, and (ii) we introduce a novel framework for privacy-preserving HP tuning using MHE while FLoRA does not prevent information leakage from the shared HPs.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Hyperparameters and Privacy. Papernot and Steinke demonstrate that the optimal HPs discovered on a dataset can leak information about its samples via membership inference attacks [189] (MIAs). While the authors propose the usage of Renyi DP to eliminate such leakage, this technique can severely degrade utility during HP tuning and introduce further challenges, e.g., tuning the DP parameters themselves. Koskela and Kulkarni use a random subset of the confidential data for HP tuning to achieve lower DP bounds and yield better privacy-utility trade-offs [211]. However, a recent auditing study reveals that the privacy bounds of previous DP-based HP tuning are not tight [212]. Mohapatra et al. show how the HP tuning process in DP settings can be integrated within the broader privacy budget allocation through adaptive optimizations [213]. Ding et al. develop a DP-HP tuning framework with constant privacy overhead, allowing the expansion of the HP search space without affecting the privacy loss [214]. All these studies, however, do not take the FL setting into consideration.

Privacy-Preserving Hyperparameter Tuning for FL. Zawad et al. [215] propose a proxy-based HP scheme that allows the tuning tasks to be executed on the server side using synthetic data. Their method, however, is tailored to client-side parameters, and sharing synthetic data raises additional privacy concerns [216, 217]. Seng et al. perform NAS and HP tuning using DP [218]. However, their solution operates in an online manner introducing additional communication overhead compared to single-shot HP tuning approaches.

7.3.3 Problem Statement & Solution Roadmap

We consider a cross-silo FL setting, where several (tens or hundreds of) entities (e.g., hospitals) aim at collaboratively training a ML model on their sensitive data. To this end, they need to employ a PPFL solution where the aggregator receives model updates enhanced with a PET, e.g., DP, SMPC or HE. To ensure the convergence and performance of the trained model, the entities need to tune HPs related to the learning process **before** the training starts. The HP tuning process should be efficient, accurate, and respect the privacy of each client's sensitive data.

FL requires tuning both server- and client-side HPs: server-side HPs update the global model, while client-side HPs guide local training iterations. In this work, we focus on the problem of configuring **server-side HPs**, e.g., server learning rate or momentum, since these play a significant role in the accuracy of the global model, especially when PPFL solutions are employed. For instance, differentially private solutions introduce noise in the learning process, thus these HPs need to be adapted accordingly [189], while SMPC and HE approaches require the approximation of non-polynomial functions (e.g., activations) whose performance is affected by these HPs [186, 187, 188, 30, 29, 219, 220]. As an example, POSEIDON [187] employs a least-squares approximation of non-polynomial activation functions within a specific interval to

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Algorithm 9 Single-shot HP tuning for Cross-silo FL.

- 1: **for** Each client $S_i \in S$ **do**
 - 2: Perform LHO for all HPs in the set $\{hp\}$ ▷ Client executes
 - 3: Send the best $(\{hp\}_i, \{accuracy\}_i)$ pairs found by LHO to the server
 - 4: **end for**
 - 5: $\{hp\}_g = \text{Combine}(\{hp\}_i, \{accuracy\}_i)$ ▷ Server executes
-

facilitate their execution under HE. Our observations indicate that appropriately adjusting the learning rate is crucial for selecting this interval, as a higher learning rate causes gradient values to exceed the interval boundaries quickly, leading to imprecise executions.

To address the efficient, accurate, and privacy-preserving HP tuning problem for cross-silo FL, we follow a single-shot approach similar to [1] which is based on the hypothesis that an effective HP configuration for the global model can be derived from the client-specific local HPs. Thus, our idea is to infer optimal global HPs based solely on HPs discovered by the clients locally. Algorithm 9 presents the high-level overview of our approach for efficient HP tuning in cross-silo FL settings: (i) Each client performs local optimization (LHO) to tune the HPs in the set $\{hp\}$ on its dataset. Then, (ii) each client communicates the optimal sets of HPs along with an indicator of their performance (e.g., the accuracy achieved on a local validation set) to the server. Finally, (iii) the server combines ($\text{Combine}(\cdot)$, Line 5) the HP sets received from all the clients to derive the optimal global HPs $\{hp\}_g$.

Aiming to find effective strategies to combine (i.e., $\text{Combine}(\cdot)$, Line 5, Algorithm 9) the client local HPs and derive the optimal global HPs at the server side, we perform a comprehensive measurement study to better understand the connection between local and global HPs in FL based on various factors such as the dataset, the model architecture, the client configuration, and the data distribution (Section 7.3.4). Through our measurement study, we benchmark various strategies which infer server HPs from the client HPs and which are compatible with PPFL pipelines. Inspired by aggregation methods commonly used in FL, we experiment with combination strategies such as computing the mean [191], the median [192, 193], the trimmed mean [192], trimmed mean/median with the highest validation accuracy, and density-based clustering [194, 195]. Then, to address the privacy concerns raised by sharing local HPs with the FL server, we introduce PRIVTUNA, a novel framework that enables the HP combination at the server side in a privacy-preserving manner (Section 7.3.5). PRIVTUNA is based on MHE and can be used to develop various HP tuning techniques for FL with strong privacy guarantees. We use PRIVTUNA to develop two HP combination strategies that our measurements indicated as promising approaches, and we evaluate their performance in terms of computation/communication overhead, and HP tuning precision.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

7.3.4 Evaluating Single-shot HP Tuning Strategies for Federated Learning

Methodology. To benchmark combination methods and find a suitable one for the global HP tuning based on the local HPs discovered by the clients, we conduct a measurement study on various datasets with different NN architectures simulating both iid and non-iid FL settings. Our measurement study follows the subsequent footprint: (i) We first perform local HPO (**LHO**) per client to derive the optimal HPs on local datasets. We also perform global HPO (**GHO**) using federated grid search to construct a *ground truth* for the optimal server HPs. Then, (ii) following Algorithm 9, we employ various combination strategies to derive the server HPs based on the LHO results of each client (i.e., their $\{hp\}_i, \{accuracy\}_i$ pairs). The tuning strategies that we benchmark for the $\text{Combine}(\cdot)$ method of Algorithm 9 are the following:

Mean: Inspired from vanilla FedAvg [191], we compute the mean of the HPs obtained by LHO at each client.

Median: Based on the (coordinate-wise) median aggregation rule for robust FL [192, 193], we adopt a method that estimates the median of the HPs obtained by LHO at each client.

Trimmed-mean: We apply a similar strategy to the trimmed-mean aggregation rule for FL [192]. We discard the top and bottom 10% of HPs (sorted by value) obtained through LHO at each client, then compute the mean of the remaining HPs.

Mean/Median of Best HPs: We rank each client's HPs by validation accuracy, select the top 5%, and compute their mean or median on the server side.

DBSCAN: Following recent work on clustered FL [195, 194], we apply density-based clustering—suited to low-dimensional data and robust to outliers—to group the top HPs from LHO at each client by validation accuracy. We use the cluster centroids as the final HP set.

Finally, (iii) we compare the results of each HP combination strategy with the ground truth baseline (i.e., the **GHO**), aiming to identify the most suitable methods for various settings.

Experiment Setup. We describe the datasets that we use, the model architectures, the FL settings, and the HPs and their configurations for our measurement study. All experiments are implemented in Python, using the FedJax library [221] for the FL operations.

Datasets. We employ four datasets and we perform HP tuning based on validation accuracy which measures the model's ability to predict labels for a validation set that constitutes a subset of the original training data. We list the datasets below:

MNIST. The MNIST [222] dataset is a popular collection of 28×28 pixel grayscale images of handwritten digits across 10 classes (0–9), with 60K training samples and 10K test samples.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Extended MNIST (EMNIST). EMNIST [223] is an extension of the MNIST dataset that contains a total of $\sim 814\text{K}$ 28×28 pixel grayscale images of handwritten characters including upper- and lower-case letters and digits. The number of classes is 62.

Street View House Numbers (SVHN). SVHN [224] is digit recognition dataset which contains 32×32 RGB images of house numbers collected by Google Street View. The training and test datasets comprise approximately 100K digits.

CIFAR-10. CIFAR-10 [225] contains 60K 32×32 -pixel RGB images labeled across 10 categories (e.g., cat, ship, dog, etc.).

Model Architectures. In our study, we rely on 3 NN architectures:

Network A. This model consists of two sequential convolutional layers with a kernel size 5×5 , and 32 output channels followed by an average pooling (with window shape 2, stride of 1), and a dense layer with 64 neurons. The model has a total of 54,274 parameters. We use Network A in all experiments with MNIST.

Network B [226]. This model consists of two sequential convolutional layers with kernel size 5×5 , and 6 and 16 output channels, respectively. We use average pooling (with a window shape of 2 and stride of 1) and two dense layers of 120 and 84 neurons, respectively. We use Network B in all experiments with EMNIST and SVHN dataset. The EMNIST and SVHN models have 29,896 and 32,756 parameters, respectively.

Network C. The model consists of six sequential convolutional layers with kernel size 5×5 using average pooling (with window shape 2 and stride 1), and a dense layer with 128 neurons. The model has a total of 699,018 parameters. We use dropout, a regularization method that randomly omits units during the training. We use Network C in experiments with the CIFAR-10 dataset.

FL Settings. Our measurement study accounts for both iid and non-iid FL settings. To simulate the former we equally and randomly distribute the original dataset to N clients with $N = [10, 20, 50]$. To simulate a more realistic FL deployment, we consider a non-iid environment with $N = [10, 20]$ clients. Non-iid refers to data that is not independently and identically distributed across samples. In other words, the data is not drawn from the same distribution and the samples are not independent of each other. We generate various non-iid distributions following the methods described in [226] to account for label, feature, and quantity skews:

Label Skew. The label distributions vary across clients. Each client i is allocated a proportion p_i of the samples of each label according to a Dirichlet distribution (Dir_N), where $p_i \sim \text{Dir}_N(\beta_\ell)$. In our experiments, we use $\beta_\ell \in \{0.1, 1.0, 5.0\}$.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

HP	Grid
learning rate	iid \rightarrow [0.001, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5] non-iid \rightarrow [0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5]
momentum	iid \rightarrow [0, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9, 0.92, 0.93, 0.95] non-iid \rightarrow [0, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9]

Table 11 – HP grids for LHO and GHO.

Feature Skew. The feature distributions vary across clients. First, we partition randomly and equally the dataset among each client i . Then, each client's local dataset is subjected to varying degrees of Gaussian noise n_i to generate distinct feature distributions, where $n_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \frac{\beta_f * i}{N})$. In our experiments, we use $\beta_f \in \{0.02, 0.1\}$.

Quantity Skew. The size of the local dataset varies across clients. Each client i is allocated a proportion q_i of the total data samples according to a Dirichlet distribution, where $q_i \sim \text{Dir}_N(\beta_q)$. We use $\beta_q \in \{0.1, 0.4, 1.0, 2.0\}$ for our experiments.

In all of the above cases, the distribution parameter β used to generate diverse levels of data skew has the following property: a smaller β value results in greater heterogeneity among the clients.

HPs & Grids. We focus on the server learning rate and momentum, conducting both LHO and GHO (ground truth) grid searches. Table 11 presents the grids used in our experiments. We fix one parameter and conduct a grid search on the other, given the time-intensive nature of these experiments. The remaining HPs are kept constant: client learning rate at 0.01, client momentum at 0.01, number of epochs at $e = 30$ (for both LHO and GHO), and local iterations at $\ell = 2$ for GHO experiments. We keep 10% of the training data as a validation set. For the specified grid sizes, each experiment requires $7 \times 7 = 49$ training rounds for iid and $6 \times 4 = 24$ rounds for non-iid. Thus, the LHO experiments require $N \times 49$ and $N \times 24$ training rounds per client. In total, we conducted over 4,067 experiments for the iid and 6,912 for the non-iid settings.

Experimental Results. We showcase the results of our measurement study on both iid and non-iid cross-silo FL settings. Then, we compare the tuning performance of the strategies identified by our measurement study with the state-of-the-art efficient HP tuning method for FL, FLoRA [1].

IID Setting. We display our results on the iid setting for learning rate and momentum with $N = [10, 20, 50]$ clients using the **Mean** strategy as the Combine(\cdot) method in Figure 24. We observe that the learning rate or momentum determined by applying the **Mean** strategy on

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 24 – Barplots of learning rate, momentum, and accuracy for the iid setting with Mean as the Combine(.) strategy, on various datasets and experiments. The ground truth (GHO result) is indicated by black dots. The remaining bar colors represent the results of combining the clients’ optimal HPs with the Mean Combine(.) strategy, for a variable number of clients (N).

the client HPs closely approximates the ground truth, and the resulting HPs do not hinder the achieved test accuracy. We note that obtaining the optimal learning rate and momentum on the CIFAR-10 dataset is more challenging than on other datasets; we speculate that this is due to the more complex classification task. Moreover, we observe that discovering the optimal server HPs from the client HPs is more difficult with an increasing number of clients; this is because the dataset size at each client decreases as the number of clients increases, i.e., the HPs that they locally discover are less *optimal*. This is also reflected on Figure 24c which shows that the test accuracy slightly decreases with an increasing number of clients, however, the HPs obtained by the **Mean** strategy yield similar accuracy to the (GHO) ground truth.

Non-iid Setting. Figure 25 showcases our measurement results for various Combine(.) strategies, datasets, and non-iid settings with $N = 20$ clients: (i) feature skew with $\beta_f = 0.02$ (top-row), (ii) label skew with $\beta_\ell = 1.0$ (middle-row), and (iii) quantity skew with $\beta_q = 0.4$ (bottom-row). Overall, we observe that straightforward combination strategies, such as computing the mean, its trimmed version, or the median, yield HPs that are not close to the ground truth; this demonstrates the challenge of performing HP tuning in non-iid settings. However, we observe that other combination strategies perform better: DBSCAN optimally derives the ground truth server learning rate across all skews and datasets, while the mean/median of the top 5% performs well for estimating the server momentum. For instance, the DBSCAN combination strategy perfectly matches the ground truth for learning rate (Figures 25a, 25c and 25e) as well as the momentum in experiments with the SVHN and EMNIST datasets (Figures 25b, 25d, and 25f). Similarly, the mean/median of the top 5% HPs achieves the best results for estimating the momentum when there is feature or label skew on the MNIST and CIFAR10 datasets. When we consider the joint optimization of learning rate and momentum, across all our experimental settings with various skew types and parameters, datasets, and the number of clients, we find that, on average, DBSCAN outperforms the other combination strategies. Specifically, among 144 experiments, DBSCAN achieves the lowest absolute distance from the ground truth in 95

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Figure 25 – Barplots of learning rate and momentum for the non-iid setting with $N = 20$ clients, variable datasets and $\text{Combine}(\cdot)$ strategies. The top-row results are for feature skew ($\beta_f = 0.02$), middle-row results for label skew ($\beta_\ell = 1.0$), and bottom-row results are for quantity skew ($\beta_q = 0.4$). Bar colors represent the HPs derived using various combination strategies.

cases when evaluating the absolute distance of HP estimates from the ground truth for each combination function. The second best approach was the mean/median of the top 5% with 25 experiments achieving the lowest absolute distance.

Comparison with Prior Work. We perform a comparison between the best-performing combination strategy, i.e., DBSCAN, and the closest related work, FLoRa [1]. FLoRa [1] is an HP tuning solution for FL that leverages local HP tuning to derive optimal global HPs (θ^*). Its one-shot approach and suitability for non-iid settings make it ideal for comparative analysis. In FLoRa, each client i performs local HP tuning and sends (HPs, validation loss) pairs E_i to the aggregator. Then, the aggregator constructs a unified loss surface $l : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ using the pairs E_i and finds the best HP configuration $\theta^* \leftarrow \text{argmin}_{\theta \in \Theta} l(\theta)$. The authors propose four ways of constructing such loss surfaces, which we re-implement within our experiments for a fair comparison:

Single global model (SGM). All E_i sets are merged and used to train a global regressor $f : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. The loss surface is $l(\theta) = f(\theta)$.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

(a) Validation accuracies averaged across the quantity skew setting.

(b) Validation accuracies averaged across the feature skew setting.

(c) Validation accuracies averaged across the label skew setting.

(d) Validation accuracies averaged across all skews.

Figure 26 – Comparison of the various combination strategies proposed in FLoRA [1] vs. the density-based clustering (DBSCAN) strategy identified in our measurement study. The blue bar indicates the federated grid search results as ground truth. Each plot represents a different skew type (averaged across skew parameters with 10 and 20 clients).

SGM with uncertainty (SGM+U). All E_i sets are merged and used to train a global regressor that provides uncertainty quantification around its predictions $f : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $u : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$, where $f(\theta)$ is the mean prediction of the model at θ and $u(\theta)$ quantifies the uncertainty around this prediction. The loss surface is defined as $l(\theta) = f(\theta) + \alpha * u(\theta)$ for some $\alpha > 0$.

Maximum of per-party local models (MPLM). This approach trains a regressor $f_i : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for each client set E_i . The loss surface is defined as $l(\theta) = \max f_i(\theta)$.

Average of per-party local models (APLM). This approach trains a regressor $f_i : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for each client set E_i . The loss surface is defined as $l(\theta) = \text{average} f_i(\theta)$.

All trained regressors are Random Forest ones, except for SGM+U, which trains a Gaussian Process regressor with a radial basis function kernel. We compare the validation accuracies of the models trained with (a) our derived global HPs, (b) FLoRA-derived global HPs, and (c) the optimal, global HPs found by GHO. Figure 26 shows the average validation accuracies achieved among various skew types (Figures 26a, 26b, and 26c) and among all skew types (Figure 26d). Comparing the validation accuracy achieved with the HPs estimated by the DBSCAN combination with various FLoRA approaches, we find that, on average, and for each skew individually, our strategy outperforms FLoRA across all datasets. The feature skew experiments for the SVHN dataset are deemed to be especially challenging for FLoRA (note the high uncertainty indicated by the error bars). Compared to the optimal HPs found by GHO, our strategy achieves near-perfect results on all datasets except CIFAR-10, the most challenging

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

dataset in our experiments. Moreover, we observe that the label skew (Figure 26c) is more challenging than other skews (Figures 26a and 26b) which is compliant with the findings of Li et al. [226].

7.3.5 Towards Privacy-Preserving Hyperparameter Tuning for Federated Learning

Our measurement study provided interesting insights into the connection between the client and server HPs in various FL settings. Moreover, it allowed us to establish simple and efficient techniques for tuning the server HPs by combining the optimal client HPs. However, revealing optimal client HPs to the FL server introduces a new privacy attack surface, as prior research indicates that specific data samples, such as outliers, can heavily influence HPO and become susceptible to inference attacks [189]. To address this, we introduce a novel framework, PRIVTUNA, which enables privacy-preserving HP tuning techniques using MHE. We use our framework to implement and experimentally evaluate the two main strategies, i.e., averaging and density-based clustering. Our framework is flexible and easily extensible to other HP tuning techniques that might be discovered by researchers.

Multi-Party HE. HE supports arithmetic operations to be carried out on encrypted data. Our framework relies on MHE, a variant of HE for multi-party settings, to support the HP combination on the server side and to facilitate distributed cryptographic operations among the clients. Specifically, we utilize the multiparty version of Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song (CKKS), a leveled HE scheme based on the problem of ring learning with errors (RLWE) as introduced by Cheon et al. [227] and extended to the multiparty setting by Mouchet et al. [228]. This particular scheme offers plausible security against post-quantum attacks, supports floating-point arithmetic, and can withstand collisions of up to $N-1$ parties under an honest-but-curious threat model (anytrust model).

For a cyclotomic polynomial ring with a dimension \mathcal{N} (a power-of-two integer), the MHE scheme establishes the plaintext and ciphertext space, denoted as $R_Q = \mathbb{Z}_Q[X]/(X^{\mathcal{N}} + 1)$. Here, Q serves as the ciphertext modulus at an initial level which represents the depth of homomorphic operations that can be performed on a ciphertext. A plaintext/ciphertext encodes a vector of values, up to a maximum of $\mathcal{N}/2$ to its slots. As such, the scheme enables parallel operations through single instruction, multiple data (SIMD) to $\mathcal{N}/2$ values encoded in a plaintext/ciphertext. We introduce below the primary operations used in our framework. Note that CKKS only allows for limited arithmetic operations, i.e., additions and multiplications. For other operations such as division or comparison, we rely on approximations.

- $\text{SecKeyGen}(1^\lambda)$: Returns the set of secret keys $\{sk_i\}$, i.e., sk_i for each party P_i , given a security parameter λ .

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- $DKeyGen(\{sk_i\})$: Returns the collective public key pk and the evaluation keys $[ek]$.
- $DDecrypt(c, \{sk_i\})$: Returns the plaintext p , the decryption of a ciphertext c .
- $Encrypt(pk, p)$: Returns $c_{pk} \in R_Q^2$ such that the decryption results in $DDecrypt(c_{pk}, \{sk_i\}) \approx p$.
- $Add(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})$: Returns $(c + c')_{pk}$.
- $Divide(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})$: Returns c_{pk}/c'_{pk} following Goldschmidt's iterative division algorithm [229].
- $Compare(c_{pk}, t_{pk})$: Compares c_{pk} and t_{pk} by using Cheon et al.'s comparison approximation [230]. It returns a value in $[-1, 1]$ by using several consecutive polynomial evaluations of two different polynomials f and g over the difference of two ciphertexts. If $c_{pk} = t_{pk}$, it returns 0.
- $Sub(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})$: Returns $(c - c')_{pk}$.
- $Mul_{pt}(c_{pk}, p)$: Returns $(c \cdot p)_{pk}$.
- $Mul_{ct}(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})$: Returns $(c \cdot c')_{pk}$.
- $DBootstrap(c_{pk}, \{sk_i\})$: Returns c_{pk} with initial level L (i.e., it refreshes the ciphertext).

The functions above that start with 'D' are distributed, and executed among all the clients, while the others can be executed locally by any client (that holds the collective public key).

PRIVTUNA Overview. Our approach for efficient HP tuning in cross-silo FL (Algorithm 9) relies on (i) the clients to perform LHO on their dataset, and to send the resulting HP sets to the server, and (ii) the server to combine ($Combine(\cdot)$, Line 5, Algorithm 9) the received HP sets and derive the optimal global HPs for the FL process. To enable this workflow in a privacy-preserving manner, PRIVTUNA encrypts all LHO results and executes the combination strategy **under encryption** using MHE functionalities summarized earlier. As such, PRIVTUNA ensures that neither the server nor other clients can directly access the HP values discovered by LHO at each client.

PRIVTUNA operates as follows: (i) The clients generate their secret keys ($SecKeyGen(1^\lambda)$) and interact with each other to generate a collective public key ($DKeyGen(\{sk_i\})$) and possibly additional evaluation keys required to execute the combination function under encryption. (ii) Each client encrypts its LHO results (i.e., the (HP, accuracy) pairs) with the collective public key and communicates the resulting ciphertexts to the server. (iii) The server executes the $Combine(\cdot)$ function on the received ciphertexts, taking advantage of the homomorphic properties of the underlying encryption scheme. (iv) The server interacts with the clients that collectively decrypt ($DDecrypt(c, \{sk_i\})$) the global HPs. We note that the evaluation of certain $Combine(\cdot)$

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

strategies under encryption introduces challenges due to the limited arithmetic operations supported by the MHE scheme. In the following, we describe how to construct private versions of federated mean and density-based clustering combination strategies in PRIVTUNA.

Private Federated Mean (PF-Mean). Computing the mean of the HPs discovered by LHO at each client requires their summation and division by the number of HP values contributed. If the number of contributed HP values is known in advance (e.g., if each client only sends a single best HP), then computing the mean under encryption is straightforward: It only requires homomorphic additions (i.e., $\text{Add}(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})$) and a homomorphic multiplication by a constant, i.e., the (plaintext) inverse of the number of clients, using $\text{Mul}_{\text{pt}}(c_{pk}, p)$. However, in PRIVTUNA, we assume that each client can contribute multiple LHO results (e.g., their top $x\%$ HP sets based on validation accuracy). Thus, PRIVTUNA executes the PF-Mean computation by letting each client encrypt the sum of each HP in the slots of one ciphertext and an additional ciphertext indicating how many HP sets they are contributing. Then, the server computes the mean of each HP by performing additions that are inherently supported by the CKKS scheme and on the division operation ($\text{Divide}(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})$) that is possible with Goldschmidt's algorithm [229]. Note that excluding the key generation protocol ($\text{DKeyGen}(\{sk_i\})$), the PF-Mean computation in PRIVTUNA requires a single communication round: Each client sends its optimal HPs encrypted to the server, the server performs the summation and the division and returns the encrypted result to the clients for collective decryption.

Private Federated Density-based Clustering (PF-DBSCAN). Performing density-based clustering under encryption at the server side is challenging; DBSCAN requires the homomorphic evaluation of multiple non-linear operations, i.e., comparisons, which makes its privacy-preserving realization impractical. To avoid this issue, we leverage a federated density-based clustering [231] that enables collective clustering by all the clients. This algorithm operates as follows: It partitions the feature (i.e., HP) space into a grid with cells of a fixed granularity L , a parameter analogous to \mathcal{E} in traditional DBSCAN. Then, each client reports the number of points within the grid cells to the aggregation server. The server aggregates these by summing up the number of points in each cell, and creates/expands clusters across neighboring cells based on MinPts. Finally, each client receives the cluster label of each cell within the feature space. In the following, we enhance this algorithm with privacy protection using MHE and modify its workflow by offloading operations that are not supported by the CKKS scheme to the client side.

Algorithm 10 displays the privacy-enhanced version of the federated DBSCAN. The process starts after the clients perform LHO to obtain $(\{hp\}_i, \{accuracy\}_i)$ pairs and after they establish their cryptographic keys. The algorithm proceeds in four stages:

Algorithm 10 Private Federated DBSCAN (PF-DBSCAN).

Grid Setup:

- 1: **for** Each client S_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ **do**
- 2: Preprocessing: MinMax scaling of HPs
- 3: $M_i \leftarrow \text{Discretize}(\{hp\}_i)$:
- 4: Precompute *the closest cell map* $Cell_i$
- 5: $M_i \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(pk, M_i)$
- 6: Send M_i to the server
- 7: **end for**

Aggregation – Round 1: ▷ Server executes

- 8: $M \leftarrow \text{Add}(M, M_i), \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$
- 9: Create dense cell mask: $D \leftarrow \text{Compare}(M, \text{MinPts})$
- 10: Send D to the clients
- 11: $D \leftarrow \text{DDecrypt}(D, \{sk_i\})$

Local Clustering:

- 12: **for** Each client S_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ **do**
- 13: $LD_i \leftarrow D \odot M_i$
- 14: Move non-dense *points* to the closest dense cell
- 15: Merge adjacent cells to form final local clusters
- 16: Create grid $HP_{ij}, \forall j \in \{hp\}_i$, and accuracies A_i
- 17: Create matrix T_i with total number of points in each cluster
- 18: $HP_{ij} \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(pk, HP_{ij}), \forall j \in \{hp\}_i$
- 19: $A_i \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(pk, A_i), T_i \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(pk, T_i)$
- 20: Send $HP_{ij}, \forall j \in \{hp\}, A_i, T_i$ to the server
- 21: **end for**

Aggregation – Round 2: ▷ Server executes

- 22: $HP_j \leftarrow \text{Add}(HP_j, HP_{ij}), \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \forall j \in \{hp\}_i$
- 23: $T \leftarrow \text{Add}(T, T_i), A \leftarrow \text{Add}(A, A_i), \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$
- 24: $HP_j \leftarrow \text{Divide}(HP_j, T), \forall j \in \{hp\}$
- 25: $A \leftarrow \text{Divide}(A, T)$
- 26: Send $HP_j, \forall j \in \{hp\}, A$ to the clients
- 27: $HP_j \leftarrow \text{DDecrypt}(HP_j, \{sk_i\})$
- 28: sort HP_j w.r.t. A

Grid Setup. Initially, each client preprocesses by retaining the HPs with the best validation accuracy and scaling them to $[0, 1]$ using a MinMax scaler. This step is pivotal for a homomorphic comparison operation required later in the algorithm. Then, each client performs discretization (Line 3, Algorithm 10) and creates a grid of cells represented as a matrix M_i ; this matrix is populated by the total number of points inside each cell. A point is defined by HP values; for example, the learning rate and momentum form a two-dimensional point. Each client then computes *the closest cell map* $Cell_i$ for each point, retaining a *point* $-i$ *closest cell* mapping. The closest cell is determined by the shortest Euclidean distance between the point and its

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

neighboring cells. To prevent the leakage of the HP grids, each client encrypts M_i and sends it to the server (Lines 5 and 6, Algorithm 10). By using the encoding (packing) capability of the MHE scheme, one matrix is encrypted into a single ciphertext, with each ciphertext slot representing a matrix entry.

Aggregation – Round 1. After the collection of the encrypted M_i matrices from the clients, the server aggregates (i.e., homomorphically sums) the grids and homomorphically compares each cell with the threshold MinPts to discover the *dense* cells (Line 9, Algorithm 10). To enable this under encryption, PRIVTUNA employs the approximate comparison scheme proposed by Cheon et al. [230]. The server then sends the encrypted dense mask (with 0s for sparse cells and 1s for dense cells) to the clients for collective decryption (Line 11, Algorithm 10).

Local Clustering. Upon receiving the dense cell mask D , each client identifies its local dense cells by multiplying it with M_i . If a dense cell has no data points, clients check Cell_i to validate whether the mapped “closest cell” qualifies as dense. If the closest cell is dense, the client retains the data point, assigning its value to the nearest cell; otherwise, the point is excluded. This filters points eligible for clustering, i.e., those within or mapped to dense cells via the *closest cell map*. Non-dense points that are retained are assigned to the nearest adjacent dense cell to prevent two clusters from connecting through a point from a non-dense cell. Each client then merges adjacent cells by selecting a cell, adding all its neighbors to a queue, and checking if each queued cell is zero or non-zero. (Line 15, Algorithm 10). Subsequently, each client populates the dense cells with HPs and accuracy values of the retained data points, creating a matrix for each HP and an additional matrix for validation accuracies (Line 16, Algorithm 10). Finally, the clients record the total number of points in each cluster (required for averaging and deriving the final HP values). Each client encrypts their HPs and accuracies into a single ciphertext leveraging the packing capability of CKKS and encrypts the final count matrices. These two ciphertexts are sent to the server (Lines 18-20, Algorithm 10).

Aggregation – Round 2. The server aggregates the matrices, computing the average HPs and corresponding accuracy to determine the final global configuration on a single packed-ciphertext (Lines 22-25, Algorithm 10). For averaging, we use the Divide operation with Goldschmidt’s iterative algorithm [229]. The averaged HP and accuracies are sent to clients, who collaboratively decrypt them. Finally, clients use the decrypted average accuracy matrix to rank and finalize the HP values (Line 28, Algorithm 10).

PRIVTUNA Experimental Evaluation. We experimentally evaluate PRIVTUNA with a focus on the runtime performance, communication overhead, and (HP tuning) precision, of the private federated mean (PF-Mean) and DBSCAN (PF-DBSCAN). We implement PRIVTUNA on top of the Lattigo [232] lattice-based (M)HE library. All experiments are executed on an Apple M2 Pro

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Operation	Mean \pm Std Dev [ms]
SecKeyGen(1^λ) (per client)	14.42 \pm 1.12
DKeyGen($\{sk_i\}$) (pk generation)	49.27 \pm 3.79
DKeyGen($\{sk_i\}$) ($[ek]$ generation)	872.18 \pm 14.38
Encrypt(pk, p)	180.94 \pm 9.41
Add(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	4.92 \pm 1.57
Mul _{ct} (c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	3.73 \pm 1.33
Divide(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	135.69 \pm 6.54
DBootstrap (protocol initialization)	91.42 \pm 4.62
Compare(c_{pk}, t_{pk}) (with bootstrapping)	3474.72 \pm 371.59
DDecrypt($c, \{sk_i\}$)	0.31 \pm 0.06

Table 12 – Microbenchmarks with $N=10$ clients, $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$.

Operation	Mean \pm Std Dev [ms]
SecKeyGen(1^λ) (per client)	51.24 \pm 2.41
DKeyGen($\{sk_i\}$) (pk generation)	370.14 \pm 3.09
DKeyGen($\{sk_i\}$) ($[ek]$ generation)	842.7 \pm 5.06
Encrypt(pk, p)	189.637 \pm 0.64
Add(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	71.024 \pm 12.55
Mul _{ct} (c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	3.49 \pm 1.27
Divide(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	154.810 \pm 4.22
DBootstrap (protocol initialization)	185.85 \pm 4.39
Compare(c_{pk}, t_{pk}) (with bootstrapping)	5021.61 \pm 138.93
DDecrypt($c, \{sk_i\}$)	0.29 \pm 0.06

Table 13 – Microbenchmarks with $N=20$ clients, $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$.

processor running at 3.49GHz with 16GB of RAM. We run our experiments with two HPs, i.e., server learning rate and momentum, and we simulate cross-silo FL settings with $N = 10$ and $N = 20$ clients and all the skew settings and datasets described in Section 7.3.4. We report timings for ring dimensions of both $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$ and $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$. The ciphertext moduli are $Q \sim 2^{438}$ and $Q \sim 2^{880}$. These parameters achieve 128-bit security according to the HE standard [233]. For the PF-DBSCAN experiments, we set the grid cell granularity to $L = 0.15$ and MinPts = 4, except for the quantity skew setting, where MinPts = 2.

Runtime Performance. We report total runtime results for two scenarios: one with 10 clients and $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$ (Table 12), and another with 20 clients and $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$ (Table 13), without accounting for communication delays. The larger ring size is employed to address the cryptographic noise accumulation that occurs with more clients. Note that the runtime of PRIVTUNA is independent of the number of HPs as it packs them in the same ciphertext and leverages on SIMD operations. PRIVTUNA executes PF-Mean among 10 clients in 1.6s ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$) and among 20 clients in 1.8s ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$). The total runtime for PF-DBSCAN among 10 clients is ~ 5.8 s ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$). For $N = 20$ clients and larger cryptographic parameters ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$), PRIVTUNA runs PF-DBSCAN in ~ 18.3 s. Note that the timings do not include LHO as this process is performed on cleartext data and optimizations on the local HP search are out of the scope of this work. Tables 12

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

and 13 provide a more detailed microbenchmark of the cryptographic operations. We observe that $\text{DKeyGen}(\{sk_i\})$ and $\text{Compare}(c_{pk}, t_{pk})$ are the most time-consuming operations. However, note that $\text{DKeyGen}(\{sk_i\})$ is executed only once and that $\text{Compare}(c_{pk}, t_{pk})$ relies on an approximation with a circuit of large depth, necessitating the use of the DBootstrap operation to refresh the ciphertexts.

Consequently, PRIVTUNA demonstrates substantial efficiency in global HP tuning, with a computational delay of just a few seconds. In contrast, performing the same HPO task in PPFL frameworks can take days or even months. For example, in a setting similar to ours with 10 parties and the MNIST dataset, the HE-based FL framework POSEIDON [187] requires approximately 3 hours for a single training round. Therefore, conducting a global HP search with a grid size comparable to our experimental setup in an iid setting (with learning rate and momentum grids of size 7) would necessitate 49 training rounds, resulting in 147 hours of computation to tune the HPs. In the same setting, PRIVTUNA performs PF-DBSCAN among 10 clients in ~ 5.8 seconds.

Communication Overhead. The communication overhead of PRIVTUNA depends on the $\text{Combine}(\cdot)$ strategy, and the number of clients. A single ciphertext with $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$ ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$) has a size of 2.62MB (9.43MB). We observe that the communication scales linearly with the number of clients. In PF-Mean, each client sends one ciphertext of size 2.62MB encrypting the sum of the learning rate and momentum discovered by LHO, and another one encrypting the number of HP sets contributed, yielding a total of 5.24MB per client and 52.4MB for 10 clients. In PF-DBSCAN, each client sends 3 ciphertexts (one for Aggregation-Round 1 and two for Aggregation-Round 2), yielding a total of 7.86MB and 28.29MB per client without bootstrapping, for $(\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}, N = 10)$ and $(\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}, N = 20)$, respectively. Finally, the $\text{DBootstrap}()$ operation, required for the comparison operations, incurs a communication cost of ~ 13.1 MB with $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$, $N = 10$ clients. While PF-Mean does not utilize bootstrapping, PF-DBSCAN uses it 6 times. Note that the number of bootstrapping operations depends on the circuit depth and the degree of the approximations; less/more precise implementations require less/more bootstrapping operations.

HP Tuning Precision. Finally, we evaluate the precision of PRIVTUNA for HP tuning in the context of both PF-Mean and PF-DBSCAN. We quantify the distortion between the HPs discovered by the plaintext and encrypted federated versions using the MSE. PF-Mean incurs an MSE of $\sim 2.4 \times 10^{-4}$ for $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$, $N = 10$ and $\sim 1.8 \times 10^{-4}$ for $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$, $N = 20$ which is mainly due to the division algorithm. PF-DBSCAN, which involves an approximation of both division and comparison operations, yields an MSE of $\sim 3.2 \times 10^{-4}$ and $\sim 1.02 \times 10^{-3}$, for $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$, $N = 10$ and $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$, $N = 20$, respectively, underscoring the minimal distortion in tuning performance incurred by our framework.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

7.4 Federated learning with DP-based data synthetization and weight tuning

7.4.1 Introduction

FL has gained traction as a powerful approach for decentralized learning in distributed environments. It enables multiple participants to collaboratively train a shared model without exposing their local datasets, with a central coordinator (or aggregator) managing the learning process. Despite its advantages, conventional aggregation methods like FedAvg [191] are highly susceptible to adversarial threats, particularly BAs, where even a single malicious participant can derail the entire training process. As new adversarial strategies continue to surface in FL, developing robust defense mechanisms has become an increasingly significant and active area of research, due to the substantial risks such attacks pose to real-world applications [234, 235, 236, 237].

On the other hand, not only in an FL setup, but also in general, most work on ML focuses on improving the performance of ML methods and neglects the privacy aspect. Due to the increased awareness about private individual data and policies like the EU's GDPR laws, big tech companies like Apple, Google, and even the US Census have been implementing privacy measurements in their data collection [238, 239]. One of the first groundbreaking works on actually quantifying the privacy leakage in ML models has been studied in [240], where Shokri et. al. have designed a framework to perform MIAs on basic classification tasks. MIA on ML models tries to infer whether a certain record has been used when training the respective model. This becomes a privacy issue when, e.g., an adversary can infer whether a certain patient's data was used to train a model associated with a disease. Then, the adversary can conclude that this particular patient likely has this disease [240]. Hence, their results indicate a strong vulnerability in terms of privacy for data-based models.

For the HARPOCRATES project, we introduce a comprehensive framework, depicted in Figure 27, which enhances privacy-preserving training while ensuring robustness against BAs. To strengthen privacy, our approach combines synthetic data generation with DP techniques. DP, introduced by Dwork et al. [116], is a well-established mathematical framework that provides formal privacy guarantees using principles from probability theory and statistics.

A key component of our framework is the DP-Synthesizer, which serves as a client-side module for local model training. Its purpose is to protect against adversaries on the server (or aggregator) side, particularly in scenarios involving honest-but-curious servers that may attempt to infer sensitive information from client updates. To address robustness against Byzantine threats, we propose another core module called the weight tuner. This subcomponent operates on the aggregator side and dynamically assigns weights to participating clients, effectively minimizing the impact of any malicious contributors. Together, these components enable secure and

Figure 27 – Proposed Framework

reliable FL in adversarial environments.

7.4.2 DP-Synthesizer

When working with sensitive data, privacy plays a major role in the general acceptance of those models. In some circumstances, NNs can memorize specific data samples, constituting a heavy privacy breach [241]. Previous simple anonymization attempts that removed some identifying attributes (e.g., name, birthday, etc.) have been proven ineffective. This is why technological advances in the area of PPML have increased in the past few years, with the development of various ML models that aim to preserve the privacy of individual data records. Protecting privacy becomes crucial, e.g., heartbeat data, because it can be used to identify patients, thus heavily impacting the patient's privacy [242, 243].

One promising solution [244] is to replace the original, possibly sensitive data set with a synthetic data set that resembles the original raw data in some statistical properties. Much research has been done to generate tabular or image data. In contrast, dedicated time series data generation is still a burgeoning area of research, according to a recent benchmark [245]. Regardless of the data type, data generators with no formal privacy guarantees have been shown to still be susceptible to privacy leaks [216].

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Differential privacy

Several notions of privacy have been proposed in the last decade, among which DP has emerged as the “*de-facto standard in data privacy*” [246]. The detailed DP property defined in Definition 12. Reasons for its popularity, according to a recent survey [247] are among others:

- DP is future-proof and requires no extra knowledge about the adversary.
- DP provides rigorous privacy guarantees.
- DP provides a notion of a privacy budget, which can be adapted to the specific use case to balance privacy and utility.

Definition 2 (Differential Privacy [116]). *A randomized algorithm \mathcal{M} is (ϵ, δ) -differential private if for any two datasets \mathcal{D} and \mathcal{D}' that differ in at most one record, and for any subset S of the output range of \mathcal{M} , we have:*

$$\Pr[\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{D}) \in S] \leq \exp(\epsilon) \Pr[\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{D}') \in S] + \delta \quad (12)$$

where $\Pr[\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{D}) \in S]$ is the probability that the output of \mathcal{M} on dataset \mathcal{D} belongs to S , and $\exp(\epsilon)$ is a privacy budget parameter that controls the amount of noise added to the output of $\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{D})$. The basic idea is to add calibrated, random noise either to the data, during model training, or to the output.

Problem Statement

We focus on a cross-silo FL environment, where multiple entities (such as hospitals), potentially numbering in the tens or hundreds, work together to train a ML model on their sensitive data. In this context, we assume the presence of an honest-but-curious aggregator—one that correctly follows the FL protocol but may attempt to infer sensitive information from the model updates submitted by the participants.

Let $\mathcal{D}_{Priv} = \{s_i\}_{i=1}^N$ denote a set of private samples, where $s_i = (s_i^0, \dots, s_i^L)$ is a sequence of data of fixed length L . Each sequence is associated with a corresponding label denoting whether it is normal or anomalous, respectively. We aim to design a generative model $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{D}_{Priv})$ satisfies Definition 12, then dataset \mathcal{D}_{Gen} will not reveal sensitive information about individual data points in a dataset \mathcal{D}_{Priv} , and any adversary who might discover samples in the training dataset will not be able to link to any data samples in \mathcal{D}_{Priv} by inferring the model.

AE-(dp)MERF

DP-MERF [248] is an efficient all-purpose data generation algorithm that is based on minimis-

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

ing the so-called Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) between the real and the synthetic data distributions. It employs a so-called kernel mean embedding to transform the underlying probability distribution of the original data into a Hilbert space. The distance between two distributions in the Hilbert space is then measured by the MMD. However, DP-MERF does not work well to generate time series data. We speculate that the algorithm is not able to capture the temporal dependencies and inherent ordering in sequential data. The authors have verified their algorithm mainly on tabular data as well as image data, where it delivers competitive results. Hence, we leverage the capabilities and translate them into the sequential setting. Therefore, we use an AE architecture that maps the time series to a compact latent representation of fixed dimension. Data points in the latent space can then be treated as tabular data with no temporal dependencies.

Figure 28 – AE-(dp)MERF architecture

- AE component: The AE consists of an encoder and a decoder. The encoder is based on two LSTM blocks to handle sequential data. It encodes the heartbeat sequence as a vector of fixed length. The decoder will have the same architecture as the encoder but reversed. Thus, it will learn to recover the heartbeat sequence from the latent representation.
- DP-MERF component: The DP-MERF component consists of a simple feed-forward NN,

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

called the generator, that takes in Gaussian noise as input and maps it into the latent space. We compute the MMD distance between the original encoded data and the output of the generator and use this as the loss function.

We will proceed to train the two components separately, i.e., we will first train the AE and then the generator component. The AE will learn a latent representation of the original time series. The DP-MERF generator is trained to generate data in the latent space, which will then be transformed back to a time series sample using the decoder. For the DP version of this model, we employ the same DP techniques from the original DP-MERF algorithm. The post-processing theorem 12 for DP ensures (differential) privacy for the generated time series samples after being passed to the decoder.

Evaluation for DP-Synthesizer

The aim is to assess the utility of synthetic data generated by AE-(dp)MERF. The utility is measured in an automotive scenario, involving vehicles with Adaptive Cruise Control systems (ACC). We use the OpenACC dataset [249] to evaluate the DP-Synthesizer. The purpose of OpenACC is to provide comprehensive data on ACC behavior to the scientific community, aiming to enhance understanding of ACC vehicle characteristics and assess the potential impact of widespread ACC adoption on traffic dynamics, including the anticipation of related challenges.

The dataset comprises vehicle trajectory data collected from various car-following experiments, primarily involving ACC driving. For comparison, a limited number of trajectories reflect manual driving. Data collection took place during the final quarter of 2018 over two days of car-following tests, involving either two or three vehicles in a platoon formation. The tests were conducted on public highways between Ispra and Cherasco in northern Italy, specifically scheduled during off-peak hours to reduce external traffic interference. As an on-road study, all participating vehicles were equipped with Ublox 8 GNSS devices for data acquisition. The recorded data had a sampling frequency of approximately 3–5 Hz, which was enhanced to 10 Hz through cubic spline interpolation. The lead vehicle was manually driven and instructed to perform realistic, random accelerations and decelerations around a target speed. The following vehicles operated in ACC mode whenever possible, except during specific manual driving test scenarios.

Detecting ACC driving from human driving behavior is valuable for identifying safety risks and near-miss scenarios unique to each driving mode. To this end, we train an LSTM-based classifier to distinguish ACC driving patterns from human driving behavior, while simultaneously aiming to preserve the privacy of individual driving habits. We synthesize the data using the DP-synthesizer. We are testing differentially private and non-private versions of the models and comparing them to a baseline model that is trained on the original data.

Table 14 summarizes the performance scores of all evaluated models. We compare results un-

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Table 14 – Summary of anomaly detection performance

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
OpenACC_Centralized				
Clean	0.9691	0.9176	0.9609	0.9388
AE-MERF	0.9205	0.7989	0.9055	0.8489
AE-(dp)MERF ($\epsilon = 1$)	0.9164	0.7927	0.8952	0.8409
AE-(dp)MERF ($\epsilon = 0.5$)	0.9144	0.7880	0.8932	0.8373
AE-(dp)MERF ($\epsilon = 0.1$)	0.9063	0.7603	0.9055	0.8266
AE-(dp)MERF ($\epsilon = 0.01$)	0.9008	0.7495	0.8973	0.8168
OpenACC_Federated Learning				
Clean	0.9924	0.9765	0.9947	0.9854
AE-MERF	0.9763	0.9382	0.9846	0.9605
AE-(dp)MERF ($\epsilon = 1$)	0.9731	0.9295	0.9799	0.9536
AE-(dp)MERF ($\epsilon = 0.5$)	0.9754	0.9301	0.9767	0.9523
AE-(dp)MERF ($\epsilon = 0.1$)	0.9617	0.8993	0.9706	0.9328
AE-(dp)MERF ($\epsilon = 0.01$)	0.9615	0.9057	0.9625	0.9325

der both centralized and FL settings. In the FL setup, training involves three clients, each holding data collected from different vehicles, dates, and locations—resulting in a non-iid data scenario. The results show that model utility is already reduced during the (non-privacy-preserving) data generation phase, with AE-MERF experiencing approximately a 5% drop in performance. Importantly, introducing DP does not significantly degrade model utility up to a certain privacy budget (ϵ). As indicated in the table, the F1 score decreases by only about 3% under the lowest ϵ setting. Notably, overall model performance improves in the FL scenario, which is expected given that collaboratively trained models tend to be more generalized than those trained in a centralized manner. These results also demonstrate that even when models are trained on highly privacy-preserving synthetic data generated by the DP-Synthesizer, they can still achieve strong utility within a FL framework.

7.4.3 Weight Tuning for FL

We propose a robust aggregation scheme for FL that assigns a score to each participating client according to their trustworthiness in the model updates provided at each training round, relying on a set of five metrics.

We assume there are n clients which own data, denoted as $C = \{c_1, \dots, c_n\}$. Each client has its dataset $\mathcal{D}_k = \{\mathbf{x}_j, y_j\}_{j=1}^{|\mathcal{D}_k|}$, where $|\mathcal{D}_k|$ is the total number of data samples in the dataset on client k , \mathbf{x}_j indicates the j -th sample, and y_j is the corresponding label. The objective can be

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

formulated as minimizing the loss function of the global model $F(\mathcal{W})$:

$$F(\mathcal{W}) = \sum_{k=1}^N p_k F_k(\mathcal{W}_k; \mathcal{D}_k), \quad (13)$$

where \mathcal{W} denotes the parameters of the global model, N indicates the total number of the clients, p_k represents the weight, or trust score, of the k th client, so that, $p_k > 0$ and $\sum_k p_k = 1$. With slight abuse of notation, we also denote trust score by p_t^k , where t denotes the specific iteration.

Our five metrics are detailed below. Here, we denote c_s as the client with the model that is going to be shared (source model).

1) Data size: as in FL (e.g. FedAvg) we assume that larger local training datasets provide more relevant information and can correspond to increased improvement during the training process.

2) Data Variance: We consider the variance of the local dataset on c_s , assuming that higher variance will correspond with a more diverse dataset. For instance, in intrusion detection systems (IDSs), having datasets with larger variance implies that the client has seen a wider variety of traffic and, possibly, attacks.

3) Similarity: In t^{th} iteration, the similarity between the global model, denoted as \mathcal{W}_t , and the model on c_s , denoted as $\hat{w}_{t,s}$, is computed. The more similar $\hat{w}_{t,s}$ to \mathcal{W}_t , the safer c_s is assumed in the current iteration. In this paper, we measure the Cosine similarity.

4) Divergence: Contrary to similarity, when two models are divergent from each other, then this divergence brings more unpredictability to the global model, which can be seen as a disadvantage. Therefore, in t^{th} iteration, we measure how much $\hat{w}_{t,s}$ diverges from \mathcal{W}_t , and it can be defined as:

$$Div_t(\hat{w}_{t,s}, \mathcal{W}_t) = \frac{\|\hat{w}_{t,s} - \mathcal{W}_t\|}{\|\mathcal{W}_t\|}, \quad (14)$$

Similarity and divergence are complementary metrics and are the most relevant aspects for our robust aggregation rule. In contrast, the first three metrics help to provide a better weight for benign nodes. Note that even if the attackers lie about the first three metrics, the similarity and divergence can help identify and detect the attacks.

When the aggregator calls for an update in t^{th} iteration, it assigns a score to each client in the set $N_c = \{s : c_s\}$, based on these four metrics. The score to the client $s \in N_c$ is denoted by p^s and is defined as a linear combination of the five metrics, where the last metric, i.e., divergence, is regarded as a penalty to the linear combination. Thus, the score p^s in t^{th} iteration can be

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

obtained as:

$$p_t^s = a_1 \cdot DataSize(c_s) + a_2 \cdot DataVar(c_s) + a_3 \cdot Cost(\hat{w}_{t,s}, \mathcal{W}_t) - a_4 \cdot Div_t(\hat{w}_{t,s}, \mathcal{W}_t), \quad (15)$$

where $a_1 \cdots a_4 \in \mathcal{A} \in \mathbb{R}^4$ are the scalar coefficients, and a_4 is regarded as the penalty term. In our experimental evaluation, among these four metrics, $DataSize(c_s)$ and $DataVar(c_s)$ remain constant throughout the training process; whereas $Cost(\hat{w}_{t,s}, \mathcal{W}_t)$ and $Div_t(\hat{w}_{t,s}, \mathcal{W}_t)$ change dynamically in every iteration. To find the optimal set of \mathcal{A} to correctly score the neighbor clients in N_c , we use Bayesian optimization to tune p_t^s . This black-box optimization technique relies on Bayes' Theorem to direct the search to find the minimum or maximum of an objective function [250]. In our case, we use the loss on the local training dataset of the client c_d to learn the best coefficient combination. We build a probabilistic model of the objective function as the surrogate function on every client. We call this the *tuner module*, which is formulated based on Bayes' Theorem as:

$$P(F_i^{sur}(\mathcal{W}_i) | \mathcal{A}) \propto P(\mathcal{A} | F_i^{sur}(\mathcal{W}_i)) * P(F_i^{sur}(\mathcal{W}_i)), \quad (16)$$

where $P(F_i^{sur}(\mathcal{W}_i) | \mathcal{A})$ is the posterior of the surrogate function given the explored scalar coefficients \mathcal{A} , and this posterior can be used to estimate the cost of different combinations of the coefficients; $P(\mathcal{A} | F_i^{sur}(\mathcal{W}_i))$ is the likelihood function and $P(F_i^{sur}(\mathcal{W}_i))$ represents the prior on the surrogate function with the training dataset. Furthermore, to accelerate the exploration, we constrain the search space of the coefficients $a_1 \cdots a_3$ to $[0, 1]$, where $a_1 + \cdots + a_3 = 1$, and empirically set the upper and lower bounds of the penalty coefficient a_4 depending on different scenarios. Thus, using Bayesian optimization for updating the client c_d , the weights p_t^s of the connected neighbors $s \in N_c$ will be learned dynamically according to the five metrics during the training process.

The input to Algorithm 11 includes the local dataset \mathcal{D}_j , and HPs, such as the learning rate η , global and local training epochs. In the very beginning, an initial model will be received, e.g., from the cloud. Next, every client trains the local model within a specific number of epochs. In the aggregation phase, the metrics mentioned before are calculated for each $s \in N_c$, and Bayesian optimization is applied to obtain the optimal coefficient set \mathcal{A}_{opt} . After that, the weights of the connected clients are updated by Equation 15 and the model on client c_j is updated for the next iteration. The algorithm repeats this process until it reaches the maximum number of global epochs E_{global} .

Evaluation for weight tuning

The purpose of this is to assess the ability of the proposed method to defend against a BA in FL. BA is an untargeted model poisoning attack that the adversary sends malicious model updates at random, drawn from a distribution with a very large variance [251]. In order to

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Algorithm 11 Algorithm of Robust Weighting Scheme

Input: The local dataset: \mathcal{D}_j on client $c_j \in C = \{c_1, \dots, c_n\}$.
Hyper-parameters: Learning rate: η , Number of local epochs: E_{local} , Number of global epochs: E_{global} .

- 1: Model \leftarrow Receive initial model from the cloud.
- 2: **for** $t = 0, 1, \dots, E_{global}$ **do**
- 3: **for** $j = 1, \dots, n$ **do**
- 4: **for** $e = 0, 1, \dots, E_{local}$ **do**
- 5: $\mathcal{W}_{t,j} = \text{LocalTrain}(\text{Model}, \mathcal{D}_j, \eta)$
- 6: **end for**
- 7: **end for**
- 8: **for** $j = 1, \dots, n$ **do**
- 9: $P_{c_j} \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 10: $datasize_{t,j} = \text{DataSize}(c_j)$;
- 11: $datavar_{t,j} = \text{DataVar}(c_j)$
- 12: $sim_{t,j} = \text{Cos}_t(\hat{w}_{t,j}, \mathcal{W}_t)$
- 13: $div_{t,j} = \text{Div}_t(\hat{w}_{t,j}, \mathcal{W}_t)$
- 14: $\mathcal{A}_{opt} \leftarrow \text{BayesOpt}(\mathcal{W}_t, \hat{w}_{t,j}, \mathcal{A}, datasize_{t,j}, datavar_{t,j}, sim_{t,j}, div_{t,j})$
- 15: Update p^j with \mathcal{A}_{opt} by Equation 15
- 16: Append p^j to P_{c_j}
- 17: Update \mathcal{W}_{t+1} with P_{c_j} by Equation 13
- 18: **end for**
- 19: **end for**

compare with robust aggregation rules, we choose Trimmed Mean and Median proposed by Yin et al. [236], and Krum proposed in [235] as baselines. Both the Trimmed mean and the Median are coordinate-wise aggregation rules. Trimmed Mean collects all the model updates from the neighbors in a sorted order. Given a threshold $k < \frac{|N|}{2}$, where $|N|$ is the number of clients, the aggregator discards k largest and smallest parameters, and compute the mean of the rest; Median simply use the median value of each parameter to update the local model instead of using the mean value. Finally, we also compare with standard FedAvg [191] to compare the results when no defense is present.

We evaluate the proposed weight tuner in an intrusion detection use case. We select N-BaloT dataset [252] for the experimental evaluation. It consists of real-world network traffic flows from 9 commercial IoT devices, including 4 different-branding security cameras, 2 different-branding doorbells, a thermostat, a baby monitor, and a webcam. There are 23 incremental statistics features extracted from 5 different time windows (100ms, 500ms, 1.5sec, 10sec, and 1min). This dataset is collected for detecting Botnets in IoT networks. It captures both benign traffic and malicious traffic carried by 2 botnets (Mirai, BASHLITE). We chose the malicious traffic from Mirai as our target for IDS to detect in our experiments. To evaluate the robustness of the

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

Table 15 – BAs on defenses with 10 clients (1 adv.) and 20 clients (3 adv.)

	10 clients (1 adv.)				20 clients (3 adv.)			
	AUC	F1	FPR	FNR	AUC	F1	FPR	FNR
FedAvg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tri-Mean	99.97%	98.58%	0.07%	2.70%	-	-	-	-
Median	99.15%	98.97%	0.03%	1.91%	99.83%	98.32%	0.06%	2.79%
Krum	99.92%	98.34%	0.12%	3.12%	99.89%	98.28%	0.11%	3.24%
Weight_tuner	99.97%	99.69%	0.15%	0.51%	99.93%	99.06%	0.18%	2.03%

model, we use the Area Under Curve (AUC) and the F1-score (F1) to evaluate the performance of each model. We also consider the False Negative Rate (FNR) of the local model on every client to analyze their ability to detect anomalies, and the False Positive Rate (FPR). Among these metrics, AUC measures the area under the ROC curve, which plots the TPR against the FPR at various threshold settings.

The empirical results are presented in Table 15. We observe that the performance of all aggregation methods significantly improves as the number of participating clients in FL increases. A larger pool of clients helps dilute the impact of malicious participants. We hypothesize that this is particularly beneficial for aggregation strategies that rely on robust statistics, such as Median and Trimmed-Mean, which gain stability from the presence of more benign data sources.

Among all the methods evaluated, the proposed approach consistently achieves over 99% F1-score across all scenarios, indicating that the weight tuner delivers more stable and reliable performance than the baseline methods, even in the presence of a greater number of adversaries. As shown in Table 15, both FedAvg and Trimmed-Mean fail to converge under BAs (denoted by “-” in the table), whereas Median proves to be a strong baseline. We introduce the weight tuner as a novel robust aggregation mechanism designed to protect the FL process from Byzantine clients. The results demonstrate its effectiveness: the tuner successfully reduces the influence of compromised clients by assigning them lower weights, thereby safeguarding the integrity of the global model.

7.4.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we proposed a framework offering a robust and privacy-preserving solution for FL in adversarial environments. By integrating DP with synthetic data generation through the DP-Synthesizer, the framework effectively safeguards sensitive client data from honest-but-curious servers. Empirical results show that the DP-Synthesizer maintains strong utility even under low privacy budgets. Simultaneously, the inclusion of the weight tuner component enhances resilience against BAs by mitigating the influence of malicious clients through adaptive

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

weighting. Experimental findings confirm that the weight tuner outperforms existing secure aggregation methods in mitigating adversarial impact. Together, these complementary sub-components demonstrate the framework's potential to enable secure, private, and trustworthy collaborative learning.

DRAFT

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

8 Conclusion

The HARPOCRATES project has made significant progress in developing practical, efficient, and secure solutions for PPML. Throughout the project, we addressed core challenges in feature selection, model training, and FL, always with privacy as a central design goal. Our work shows that strong privacy guarantees do not have to come at the cost of performance or scalability. By combining cryptographic methods like HE and FSS with advanced ML techniques such as SL and FL, we designed novel protocols that protect data during every stage of the ML pipeline. In feature selection, we introduced a lightweight and scalable approach using SMPC, making MI-based selection practical in privacy-sensitive settings. In classification tasks, we secured the SL framework against data leakage using encryption-based techniques, while maintaining model accuracy. In FL, we went further to improve encrypted model aggregation, byzantine-robust aggregation, privacy-preserving HP tuning, and even evaluated synthetic data generation under DP for federated anomaly detection use cases. What makes HARPOCRATES unique is its focus on real-world usability. All of our solutions were designed with efficiency in mind, tested with experimental benchmarks, and aimed at deployment in realistic scenarios. Privacy is not just a theoretical goal—it must work in practice. Looking forward, the tools and insights developed in HARPOCRATES can support the next generation of trustworthy AI systems. As regulation and public awareness around data privacy continue to grow, projects like HARPOCRATES play a key role in bridging the gap between innovation and responsibility.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

References

- [1] Y. Zhou, P. Ram, T. Salonidis, N. B. Angel, H. Samulowitz, and H. Ludwig, “Single-shot general hyper-parameter optimization for federated learning,” in *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2023.
- [2] I. Guyon and A. Elisseeff, “An introduction to variable and feature selection,” *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 2003.
- [3] R. Raab, A. Küderle, A. Zakreuskaya, A. D. Stern, J. Klucken, G. Kaissis, D. Rueckert, S. Boll, R. Eils, H. Wagener, and B. M. Eskofier, “Federated electronic health records for the european health data space,” *The Lancet Digital Health*, 2023.
- [4] A. Sangers, M. van Heesch, T. Attema, T. Veugen, M. Wiggerman, J. Veldsink, O. Bloemen, and D. Worm, “Secure multiparty pagerank algorithm for collaborative fraud detection,” in *23rd International Conference on Financial Cryptography and Data Security*, Springer, 2019.
- [5] X. Li, R. Dowsley, and M. De Cock, “Privacy-preserving feature selection with secure multiparty computation,” in *International Conference on Machine Learning*, PMLR, 2021.
- [6] H. Chabanne, A. De Wargny, J. Milgram, C. Morel, and E. Prouff, “Privacy-preserving classification on deep neural network,” *Cryptology ePrint Archive*, 2017.
- [7] O. Gupta and R. Raskar, “Distributed learning of deep neural network over multiple agents,” *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 116, pp. 1–8, 2018.
- [8] P. Vepakomma, O. Gupta, A. Dubey, and R. Raskar, “Reducing leakage in distributed deep learning for sensitive health data,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1812.00564*, 2019.
- [9] C. Gentry, “Fully homomorphic encryption using ideal lattices,” in *Proceedings of the forty-first annual ACM symposium on Theory of computing*, pp. 169–178, 2009.
- [10] E. Boyle, N. Gilboa, and Y. Ishai, “Function secret sharing,” in *Annual international conference on the theory and applications of cryptographic techniques*, pp. 337–367, Springer, 2015.
- [11] E. Boyle, N. Gilboa, and Y. Ishai, “Function secret sharing: Improvements and extensions,” in *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, pp. 1292–1303, 2016.
- [12] K. Nguyen, T. Khan, and A. Michalas, “Split without a leak: Reducing privacy leakage in split learning,” in *International Conference on Security and Privacy in Communication Systems*, pp. 321–344, Springer, 2023.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [13] T. Khan, M. Budzys, and A. Michalas, “Make split, not hijack: Preventing feature-space hijacking attacks in split learning,” in *Proceedings of the 29th ACM Symposium on Access Control Models and Technologies*, pp. 19–30, 2024.
- [14] B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, S. Hampson, and B. A. y. Arcas, “Communication-Efficient Learning of Deep Networks from Decentralized Data,” in *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, pp. 1273–1282, PMLR, Apr. 2017. ISSN: 2640-3498.
- [15] M. Aledhari, R. Razzak, R. M. Parizi, and F. Saeed, “Federated Learning: A Survey on Enabling Technologies, Protocols, and Applications,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 140699–140725, 2020. Conference Name: IEEE Access.
- [16] N. Rieke, J. Hancox, W. Li, F. Milletari, H. R. Roth, S. Albarqouni, S. Bakas, M. N. Galtier, B. A. Landman, K. Maier-Hein, S. Ourselin, M. Sheller, R. M. Summers, A. Trask, D. Xu, M. Baust, and M. J. Cardoso, “The future of digital health with federated learning,” *npj Digital Medicine*, vol. 3, pp. 1–7, Sept. 2020. Number: 1 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [17] A. Alferaidi, K. Yadav, Y. Alharbi, W. Viriyasitavat, S. Kautish, and G. Dhiman, “Federated Learning Algorithms to Optimize the Client and Cost Selections,” *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2022, p. e8514562, Apr. 2022. Publisher: Hindawi.
- [18] H. B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, S. Hampson, and B. A. y. Arcas, “Communication-Efficient Learning of Deep Networks from Decentralized Data,” Jan. 2023. arXiv:1602.05629 [cs].
- [19] S. Hardy, W. Henecka, H. Ivey-Law, R. Nock, G. Patrini, G. Smith, and B. Thorne, “Private federated learning on vertically partitioned data via entity resolution and additively homomorphic encryption,” Nov. 2017. arXiv:1711.10677 [cs].
- [20] Y. Chen, X. Qin, J. Wang, C. Yu, and W. Gao, “FedHealth: A Federated Transfer Learning Framework for Wearable Healthcare,” *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, vol. 35, pp. 83–93, July 2020. Conference Name: IEEE Intelligent Systems.
- [21] J. Qi, Q. Zhou, L. Lei, and K. Zheng, “Federated Reinforcement Learning: Techniques, Applications, and Open Challenges,” Oct. 2021. arXiv:2108.11887 [cs].
- [22] H. Wang, Z. Kaplan, D. Niu, and B. Li, “Optimizing Federated Learning on Non-IID Data with Reinforcement Learning,” in *IEEE INFOCOM 2020 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*, pp. 1698–1707, July 2020. ISSN: 2641-9874.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [23] J. Konečný, H. B. McMahan, F. X. Yu, P. Richtárik, A. T. Suresh, and D. Bacon, “Federated Learning: Strategies for Improving Communication Efficiency,” Oct. 2017. arXiv:1610.05492 [cs].
- [24] G. A. Kaissis, M. R. Makowski, D. Rückert, and R. F. Braren, “Secure, privacy-preserving and federated machine learning in medical imaging,” *Nature Machine Intelligence*, vol. 2, pp. 305–311, June 2020. Number: 6 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [25] D. Froelicher, J. R. Troncoso-Pastoriza, J. L. Raisaro, M. A. Cuendet, J. S. Sousa, H. Cho, B. Berger, J. Fellay, and J.-P. Hubaux, “Truly privacy-preserving federated analytics for precision medicine with multiparty homomorphic encryption,” *Nature Communications*, vol. 12, p. 5910, Oct. 2021. Number: 1 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [26] X. Yao, T. Huang, C. Wu, R. Zhang, and L. Sun, “Towards faster and better federated learning: A feature fusion approach,” in *IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, 2019.
- [27] S. Banerjee, E. Elmroth, and M. Bhuyan, “Fed-fis: A novel information-theoretic federated feature selection for learning stability,” in *International Conference on Neural Information Processing*, Springer, 2021.
- [28] R. Fu, Y. Wu, Q. Xu, and M. Zhang, “Feast: A communication-efficient federated feature selection framework for relational data,” *Proceedings of the ACM on Management of Data*, 2023.
- [29] S. Wagh, D. Gupta, and N. Chandran, “Securenn: 3-party secure computation for neural network training,” *PETS*, 2019.
- [30] B. Knott, S. Venkataraman, A. Hannun, S. Sengupta, M. Ibrahim, and L. van der Maaten, “Crypten: Secure multi-party computation meets machine learning,” *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2021.
- [31] S. Sav, A. Pyrgelis, J. R. Troncoso-Pastoriza, D. Froelicher, J.-P. Bossuat, J. S. Sousa, and J.-P. Hubaux, “Poseidon: Privacy-preserving federated neural network learning,” in *28th Network And Distributed System Security Symposium (NDSS)*, Internet Society, 2021.
- [32] S. Ono, J. Takata, M. Kataoka, T. I, K. Shin, and H. Sakamoto, “Privacy-preserving feature selection with fully homomorphic encryption,” *Algorithms*, 2022.
- [33] A. Akavia, B. Galili, H. Shaul, M. Weiss, and Z. Yakhini, “Privacy preserving feature selection for sparse linear regression.” Cryptology ePrint Archive, Paper 2023/1354, 2023. <https://eprint.iacr.org/2023/1354>.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [34] T. Araki, J. Furukawa, Y. Lindell, A. Nof, and K. Ohara, "High-throughput semi-honest secure three-party computation with an honest majority," in *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, 2016.
- [35] P. Langley *et al.*, "Selection of relevant features in machine learning," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Fall Symposium on Relevance*, 1994.
- [36] R. Battiti, "Using mutual information for selecting features in supervised neural net learning," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, 1994.
- [37] G. Forman *et al.*, "An extensive empirical study of feature selection metrics for text classification.," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 2003.
- [38] R. Kohavi and G. H. John, "Wrappers for feature subset selection," *Artificial Intelligence*, 1997.
- [39] J. Yang and V. Honavar, "Feature subset selection using a genetic algorithm," *IEEE Intelligent Systems and their Applications*, 1998.
- [40] S. Nakariyakul and D. P. Casasent, "An improvement on floating search algorithms for feature subset selection," *Pattern Recognition*, 2009.
- [41] D. J. Stracuzzi and P. E. Utgoff, "Randomized variable elimination," *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 2004.
- [42] E. Romero and J. M. Sopena, "Performing feature selection with multilayer perceptrons," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, 2008.
- [43] O. Chapelle and S. S. Keerthi, "Multi-class feature selection with support vector machines," in *Proceedings of the American Statistical Association*, 2008.
- [44] P. Mitra, C. Murthy, and S. K. Pal, "Unsupervised feature selection using feature similarity," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 2002.
- [45] M. H. Law, M. A. Figueiredo, and A. K. Jain, "Simultaneous feature selection and clustering using mixture models," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 2004.
- [46] G. Chandrashekar and F. Sahin, "A survey on feature selection methods," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, 2014.
- [47] J. Miao and L. Niu, "A survey on feature selection," *Procedia Computer Science*, 2016.
- [48] J. Li, K. Cheng, S. Wang, F. Morstatter, R. P. Trevino, J. Tang, and H. Liu, "Feature selection: A data perspective," *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 2017.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [49] Y. Hu, Y. Zhang, D. Gong, and X. Sun, "Multi-participant federated feature selection algorithm with particle swarm optimization for imbalanced data under privacy protection," *IEEE Transactions on Artificial Intelligence*, 2022.
- [50] Y. Qin and M. Kondo, "Federated learning-based network intrusion detection with a feature selection approach," in *IEEE International Conference on Electrical, Communication, and Computer Engineering*, 2021.
- [51] P. Cassara, A. Gotta, and L. Valerio, "Federated feature selection for cyber-physical systems of systems," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 2022.
- [52] X. Zhang, A. Mavromatics, A. Vafeas, R. Nejabati, and D. Simeonidou, "Federated feature selection for horizontal federated learning in iot networks," *IEEE Internet of Things*, 2023.
- [53] Y. Jafer, S. Matwin, and M. Sokolova, "A framework for a privacy-aware feature selection evaluation measure," in *13th Annual Conference on Privacy, Security and Trust (PST)*, IEEE, 2015.
- [54] M. Alishahi and V. Moghtadaiee, "Feature selection on anonymized datasets," in *IEEE Intl Conf on Dependable, Autonomic and Secure Computing (DASC)*, 2023.
- [55] M. Alishahi, V. Moghtadaiee, and H. Navidan, "Add noise to remove noise: Local differential privacy for feature selection," *Computers & Security*, 2022.
- [56] M. Banerjee and S. Chakravarty, "Privacy preserving feature selection for distributed data using virtual dimension," in *Proceedings of the 20th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management*, 2011.
- [57] M. Sheikhalishahi and F. Martinelli, "Privacy-utility feature selection as a privacy mechanism in collaborative data classification," in *IEEE International Conference on Enabling Technologies: Infrastructure for Collaborative Enterprises*, 2017.
- [58] V. Rao, Y. Long, H. Eldardiry, S. Rane, R. Rossi, and F. Torres, "Secure two-party feature selection," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.00832*, 2019.
- [59] F. K. Dankar, N. Madathil, S. K. Dankar, and S. Boughorbel, "Privacy-preserving analysis of distributed biomedical data: Designing efficient and secure multiparty computations using distributed statistical learning theory," *JMIR Medical Informatics*, 2019.
- [60] R. Zhang, H. Li, M. Hao, H. Chen, and Y. Zhang, "Secure feature selection for vertical federated learning in ehealth systems," in *IEEE International Conference on Communications*, 2022.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [61] A. Li, J. Huang, J. Jia, H. Peng, L. Zhang, L. A. Tuan, H. Yu, and X.-Y. Li, "Efficient and privacy-preserving feature importance-based vertical federated learning," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, 2023.
- [62] D. Froelicher, H. Cho, M. Edupalli, J. S. Sousa, J. Bossuat, A. Pyrgelis, J. R. Troncoso-Pastoriza, B. Berger, and J. Hubaux, "Scalable and privacy-preserving federated principal component analysis," in *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, 2023.
- [63] V. Nikolaenko, U. Weinsberg, S. Ioannidis, M. Joye, D. Boneh, and N. Taft, "Privacy-preserving ridge regression on hundreds of millions of records," in *IEEE S&P*, 2013.
- [64] A. Gascón, P. Schoppmann, B. Balle, M. Raykova, J. Doerner, S. Zahur, and D. Evans, "Privacy-preserving distributed linear regression on high-dimensional data," *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2017.
- [65] D. Bogdanov, L. Kamm, S. Laur, and V. Sokk, "Rmind: a tool for cryptographically secure statistical analysis," *IEEE TDSC*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 481–495, 2018.
- [66] P. Mohassel and Y. Zhang, "Secureml: A system for scalable privacy-preserving machine learning," in *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, 2017.
- [67] P. Schoppmann, A. Gascón, M. Raykova, and B. Pinkas, "Make some room for the zeros: data sparsity in secure distributed machine learning," in *Proceedings of the ACM Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, 2019.
- [68] N. Agrawal, A. Shahin Shamsabadi, M. J. Kusner, and A. Gascón, "Quotient: two-party secure neural network training and prediction," in *Proceedings of the 2019 ACM Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, 2019.
- [69] M. Byali, H. Chaudhari, A. Patra, and A. Suresh, "Flash: Fast and robust framework for privacy-preserving machine learning," *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2020.
- [70] S. Wagh, S. Tople, F. Benhamouda, E. Kushilevitz, P. Mittal, and T. Rabin, "Falcon: Honest-majority maliciously secure framework for private deep learning," *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2021.
- [71] S. Tan, B. Knott, Y. Tian, and D. J. Wu, "Cryptgpu: Fast privacy-preserving machine learning on the gpu," in *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, 2021.
- [72] T. Ryffel, P. Tholoniati, D. Pointcheval, and F. Bach, "Ariann: Low-interaction privacy-preserving deep learning via function secret sharing," *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2022.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [73] Y. Aono, T. Hayashi, L. Wang, S. Moriai, *et al.*, “Privacy-preserving deep learning via additively homomorphic encryption,” *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, 2017.
- [74] Q. Zhang, C. Wang, H. Wu, C. Xin, and T. V. Phuong, “Gelu-net: A globally encrypted, locally unencrypted deep neural network for privacy-preserved learning.,” in *International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence*, 2018.
- [75] W. Zheng, R. A. Popa, J. E. Gonzalez, and I. Stoica, “Helen: Maliciously secure cooperative learning for linear models,” in *IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, 2019.
- [76] T. Stevens, C. Skalka, C. Vincent, J. Ring, S. Clark, and J. Near, “Efficient differentially private secure aggregation for federated learning via hardness of learning with errors,” in *31st USENIX Security Symposium*, 2022.
- [77] D. Froelicher, J. R. Troncoso-Pastoriza, A. Pyrgelis, S. Sav, J. S. Sousa, J.-P. Bossuat, and J.-P. Hubaux, “Scalable privacy-preserving distributed learning,” *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2021.
- [78] S. Sav, A. Diaa, A. Pyrgelis, J.-P. Bossuat, and J.-P. Hubaux, “Privacy-preserving federated recurrent neural networks,” *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2023.
- [79] D. Evans, V. Kolesnikov, M. Rosulek, *et al.*, “A pragmatic introduction to secure multi-party computation,” *Foundations and Trends® in Privacy and Security*, 2018.
- [80] A. C. Yao, “Protocols for secure computations,” in *23rd Annual Symposium on Foundations of Computer Science*, IEEE, 1982.
- [81] O. Goldreich, S. Micali, and A. Wigderson, *How to play any mental game, or a completeness theorem for protocols with honest majority*, pp. 307–328. Association for Computing Machinery, 2019.
- [82] R. Cramer, I. B. Damgård, *et al.*, *Secure multiparty computation*. Cambridge University Press, 2015.
- [83] D. Bogdanov, S. Laur, and J. Willemson, “Sharemind: A framework for fast privacy-preserving computations,” in *13th European Symposium on Research in Computer Security (ESORICS)*, Springer, 2008.
- [84] P. Rindal, “The ABY3 Framework for Machine Learning and Database Operations..” <https://github.com/ladnir/aby3>.
- [85] M. Keller, “Mp-spdz: A versatile framework for multi-party computation,” in *Proceedings of the ACM Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, 2020.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [86] L. Braun, D. Demmler, T. Schneider, and O. Tkachenko, "Motion—a framework for mixed-protocol multi-party computation," *ACM Transactions on Privacy and Security*, 2022.
- [87] R. Küsters, J. Liedtke, J. Müller, D. Rausch, and A. Vogt, "Ordinos: A verifiable tally-hiding e-voting system," in *IEEE European Symposium on Security and Privacy (EuroS&P)*, 2020.
- [88] L. Kamm, D. Bogdanov, S. Laur, and J. Vilo, "A new way to protect privacy in large-scale genome-wide association studies," *Bioinformatics*, 2013.
- [89] A. Polychroniadou, G. Asharov, B. E. Diamond, T. Balch, H. Buehler, R. Hua, S. Gu, G. Gimler, and M. Veloso, "Prime match: A privacy-preserving inventory matching system," in *32nd USENIX Security Symposium*, 2023.
- [90] D. Bogdanov, M. Jõemets, S. Siim, and M. Vaht, "How the estonian tax and customs board evaluated a tax fraud detection system based on secure multi-party computation," in *International Conference on Financial Cryptography and Data Security*, Springer, 2015.
- [91] O. Catrina and S. De Hoogh, "Improved primitives for secure multiparty integer computation," in *7th International Conference on Security and Cryptography for Networks*, Springer, 2010.
- [92] O. Catrina and A. Saxena, "Secure computation with fixed-point numbers," in *14th International Conference on Financial Cryptography and Data Security*, Springer, 2010.
- [93] P. Russell Graves-Morris, E. B. Saff, and R. S. Varga, "Rational approximation and interpolation," in *Lecture Notes in Mathematics*, Springer, 1983.
- [94] G. Klose, B. Kemp, T. Penzel, A. Schlogl, P. Rappelsberger, E. Trenker, G. Gruber, J. Zeithofer, B. Saletu, W. Herrmann, *et al.*, "The siesta project polygraphic and clinical database," *IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Magazine*, 2001.
- [95] T. Karhu, T. Leppänen, J. Töyräs, A. Oksenberg, S. Myllymaa, and S. Nikkonen, "Abosa – freely available automatic blood oxygen saturation signal analysis software: Structure and validation," *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 2022.
- [96] I. C. Covert, W. Qiu, M. Lu, N. Y. Kim, N. J. White, and S.-I. Lee, "Learning to maximize mutual information for dynamic feature selection," in *International Conference on Machine Learning*, PMLR, 2023.
- [97] S. D. Rane, W. Sun, and A. Vetro, "Secure distortion computation among untrusting parties using homomorphic encryption," in *2009 16th IEEE international conference on image processing*.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [98] N. Islam, W. Puech, K. Hayat, and R. Brouzet, "Application of homomorphism to secure image sharing," *Optics Communications*, vol. 284, no. 19, pp. 4412–4429, 2011.
- [99] M. Kim and K. Lauter, "Private genome analysis through homomorphic encryption," in *BMC medical informatics and decision making*, vol. 15, p. S3, Springer, 2015.
- [100] R. Gilad-Bachrach, N. Dowlin, K. Laine, K. Lauter, M. Naehrig, and J. Wernsing, "Cryptonets: Applying neural networks to encrypted data with high throughput and accuracy," in *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pp. 201–210, 2016.
- [101] N. Dowlin, R. Gilad-Bachrach, K. Laine, K. Lauter, M. Naehrig, and J. Wernsing, "Manual for using homomorphic encryption for bioinformatics," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 105, no. 3, 2017.
- [102] T. Shortell and A. Shokoufandeh, "Secure signal processing using fully homomorphic encryption," *IET Information Security*, 2019.
- [103] A. A. Soofi and A. Awan, "Classification techniques in machine learning: applications and issues," *Journal of Basic & Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, pp. 459–465, 2017.
- [104] G. cloud, "Google prediction api." <https://cloud.google.com/prediction/>.
- [105] M. Azure, "Azure machine learning." <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/services/machine-learning/#features>.
- [106] E. Labs, "Ersatz labs." <http://www.ersatzlabs.com/>.
- [107] M. Ribeiro, K. Grolinger, and M. A. Capretz, "Mlaas: Machine learning as a service," in *2015 IEEE 14th international conference on machine learning and applications (ICMLA)*, pp. 896–902, IEEE, 2015.
- [108] A. Michalas, N. Paladi, and C. Gehrman, "Security aspects of e-health systems migration to the cloud," in *e-Health Networking, Applications and Services (Healthcom), 2014 IEEE 16th International Conference on*, pp. 212–218, IEEE, 2014.
- [109] E. Hesamifard, H. Takabi, M. Ghasemi, and R. N. Wright, "Privacy-preserving machine learning as a service," *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, 2018.
- [110] T. Khan and A. Michalas, "Learning in the dark: Privacy-preserving machine learning using function approximation," in *2023 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications (TrustCom)*, pp. 62–71, IEEE, 2023.
- [111] O. Goldreich, "Secure multi-party computation," *Manuscript. Preliminary version*, vol. 78, no. 110, pp. 1–108, 1998.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [112] T. Khan, M. Budzys, K. Nguyen, and A. Michalas, “Wildest dreams: Reproducible research in privacy-preserving neural network training,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.03592*, 2024.
- [113] Q. Yang, Y. Liu, T. Chen, and Y. Tong, “Federated machine learning: Concept and applications,” *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology (TIST)*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 1–19, 2019.
- [114] S. Truex, N. Baracaldo, A. Anwar, T. Steinke, H. Ludwig, R. Zhang, and Y. Zhou, “A hybrid approach to privacy-preserving federated learning,” in *ACM A/Sec*, 2019.
- [115] A. Singh, P. Vepakomma, O. Gupta, and R. Raskar, “Detailed comparison of communication efficiency of split learning and federated learning,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.09145*, 2019.
- [116] C. Dwork, “Differential privacy,” in *International colloquium on automata, languages, and programming*, pp. 1–12, Springer, 2006.
- [117] S. Abuadba, K. Kim, M. Kim, C. Thapa, S. A. Camtepe, Y. Gao, H. Kim, and S. Nepal, “Can we use split learning on 1d cnn models for privacy preserving training?,” in *Proceedings of the 15th ACM Asia Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, pp. 305–318, 2020.
- [118] T. Khan, A. Bakas, and A. Michalas, “Blind faith: Privacy-preserving machine learning using function approximation,” in *2021 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*, pp. 1–7, IEEE, 2021.
- [119] A. Falcetta and M. Roveri, “Privacy-preserving deep learning with homomorphic encryption: An introduction,” *IEEE Computational Intelligence Magazine*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 14–25, 2022.
- [120] S. Zapechnikov, “Secure multi-party computations for privacy-preserving machine learning,” *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 213, pp. 523–527, 2022.
- [121] Q. Zhang, C. Xin, and H. Wu, “Privacy-preserving deep learning based on multiparty secure computation: A survey,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 13, pp. 10412–10429, 2021.
- [122] E. Boyle, N. Gilboa, and Y. Ishai, “Secure computation with preprocessing via function secret sharing,” in *Theory of Cryptography: 17th International Conference, TCC 2019, Nuremberg, Germany, December 1–5, 2019, Proceedings, Part I 17*, pp. 341–371, Springer, 2019.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [123] P. Vepakomma, O. Gupta, T. Swedish, and R. Raskar, “Split learning for health: Distributed deep learning without sharing raw patient data,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1812.00564*, 2018.
- [124] G. B. Moody and R. G. Mark, “The impact of the mit-bih arrhythmia database,” *IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Magazine*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 45–50, 2001.
- [125] P. Wagner, N. Strodthoff, R.-D. Bousseljot, D. Kreiseler, F. I. Lunze, W. Samek, and T. Schaeffter, “Ptbx-xl, a large publicly available electrocardiography dataset,” *Scientific data*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2020.
- [126] T. Khan, K. Nguyen, and A. Michalas, “Split ways: Privacy-preserving training of encrypted data using split learning,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.08778*, 2023.
- [127] J. Li, A. S. Rakin, X. Chen, Z. He, D. Fan, and C. Chakrabarti, “Resfl: A resistance transfer framework for defending model inversion attack in split federated learning,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 10194–10202, 2022.
- [128] T. Ryffel, P. Tholoniati, D. Pointcheval, and F. Bach, “Ariann: Low-interaction privacy-preserving deep learning via function secret sharing,” *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, vol. 2022, no. 1, pp. 291–316, 2020.
- [129] E. Frimpong, T. Khan, and A. Michalas, “Secrets in motion: Privacy-preserving video classification with built-in access control,” in *2024 9th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech)*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2024.
- [130] E. Frimpong, B. Liu, C. Nuoskala, and A. Michalas, “Blind brother: Attribute-based selective video encryption,” in *15th ACM Conference on Data and Application Security and Privacy (CODASPY’25)*, ACM, 2025.
- [131] R. Shokri, M. Stronati, C. Song, and V. Shmatikov, “Membership Inference Attacks against Machine Learning Models,” Mar. 2017. arXiv:1610.05820 [cs, stat].
- [132] F. Mo, H. Haddadi, K. Katevas, E. Marin, D. Perino, and N. Kourtellis, “PPFL: privacy-preserving federated learning with trusted execution environments,” in *Proceedings of the 19th Annual International Conference on Mobile Systems, Applications, and Services, MobiSys ’21*, (New York, NY, USA), pp. 94–108, Association for Computing Machinery, 2021.
- [133] J. Geiping, H. Bauermeister, H. Dröge, and M. Moeller, “Inverting Gradients – How easy is it to break privacy in federated learning?,” Sept. 2020. arXiv:2003.14053 [cs].

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [134] J. Park and H. Lim, "Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning Using Homomorphic Encryption," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, p. 734, Jan. 2022. Number: 2 Publisher: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute.
- [135] X. Yin, Y. Zhu, and J. Hu, "A Comprehensive Survey of Privacy-preserving Federated Learning: A Taxonomy, Review, and Future Directions," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 54, pp. 1–36, July 2022.
- [136] M. Mansouri, M. Önen, W. Ben Jaballah, and M. Conti, "SoK: Secure Aggregation Based on Cryptographic Schemes for Federated Learning," *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, vol. 2023, pp. 140–157, Jan. 2023.
- [137] K. Wei, J. Li, M. Ding, C. Ma, H. H. Yang, F. Farokhi, S. Jin, T. Q. S. Quek, and H. Vincent Poor, "Federated Learning With Differential Privacy: Algorithms and Performance Analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, vol. 15, pp. 3454–3469, 2020. Conference Name: IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security.
- [138] O. Choudhury, A. Gkoulalas-Divanis, T. Salonidis, I. Sylla, Y. Park, G. Hsu, and A. Das, "Differential Privacy-enabled Federated Learning for Sensitive Health Data," Feb. 2020. arXiv:1910.02578 [cs].
- [139] H. Zhu, R. Wang, Y. Jin, K. Liang, and J. Ning, "Distributed additive encryption and quantization for privacy preserving federated deep learning," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 463, pp. 309–327, Nov. 2021.
- [140] K. Bonawitz, V. Ivanov, B. Kreuter, A. Marcedone, H. B. McMahan, S. Patel, D. Ramage, A. Segal, and K. Seth, "Practical Secure Aggregation for Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning," in *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security, CCS '17*, (New York, NY, USA), pp. 1175–1191, Association for Computing Machinery, 2017.
- [141] C. Zhang, S. Li, J. Xia, W. Wang, F. Yan, and Y. Liu, "{BatchCrypt}: Efficient Homomorphic Encryption for {Cross-Silo} Federated Learning," pp. 493–506, 2020.
- [142] R. Guanciale, N. Paladi, and A. Vahidi, "SoK: Confidential Quartet - Comparison of Platforms for Virtualization-Based Confidential Computing," in *2022 IEEE International Symposium on Secure and Private Execution Environment Design (SEED)*, pp. 109–120, Sept. 2022.
- [143] F. Mo, Z. Tarkhani, and H. Haddadi, "SoK: Machine Learning with Confidential Computing," Aug. 2022. arXiv:2208.10134 [cs].

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [144] A. Muñoz, R. Ríos, R. Román, and J. López, “A survey on the (in)security of trusted execution environments,” *Computers & Security*, vol. 129, p. 103180, June 2023.
- [145] Z. Jiang, W. Wang, and Y. Liu, “FLASHE: Additively Symmetric Homomorphic Encryption for Cross-Silo Federated Learning,” Sept. 2021. arXiv:2109.00675 [cs].
- [146] C. Fontaine and F. Galand, “A Survey of Homomorphic Encryption for Nonspecialists,” *EURASIP Journal on Information Security*, vol. 2007, pp. 1–10, 2007.
- [147] J. H. Cheon, A. Kim, M. Kim, and Y. Song, “Homomorphic Encryption for Arithmetic of Approximate Numbers,” in *Advances in Cryptology – ASIACRYPT 2017* (T. Takagi and T. Peyrin, eds.), Lecture Notes in Computer Science, (Cham), pp. 409–437, Springer International Publishing, 2017.
- [148] J. Fan and F. Vercauteren, “Somewhat Practical Fully Homomorphic Encryption,” 2012. Report Number: 144.
- [149] M. Gaid and S. Salloum, “Homomorphic Encryption,” May 2021.
- [150] A. Bhattacharya, “Homomorphic Encryption - Basics,” Dec. 2020.
- [151] S. Gupta, A. Agrawal, K. Gopalakrishnan, and P. Narayanan, “Deep Learning with Limited Numerical Precision,”
- [152] M. Beaussart, F. Grimberg, M.-A. Hartley, and M. Jaggi, “WAFFLE: Weighted Averaging for Personalized Federated Learning,” Dec. 2021. arXiv:2110.06978 [cs].
- [153] E. Rescorla, “The Transport Layer Security (TLS) Protocol Version 1.3,” Request for Comments RFC 8446, Internet Engineering Task Force, Aug. 2018. Num Pages: 160.
- [154] T. Li, A. K. Sahu, M. Zaheer, M. Sanjabi, A. Talwalkar, and V. Smith, “Federated Optimization in Heterogeneous Networks,” Apr. 2020. arXiv:1812.06127 [cs, stat].
- [155] L. Jiang and L. Ju, “Fhebench: Benchmarking fully homomorphic encryption schemes,” 3 2022.
- [156] J. Konečný, H. B. McMahan, D. Ramage, and P. Richtárik, “Federated optimization: Distributed machine learning for on-device intelligence,” *CoRR*, vol. abs:1610.02527, 2016.
- [157] H. Yu, R. Jin, and S. Yang, “On the linear speedup analysis of communication efficient momentum sgd for distributed non-convex optimization,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1905.03817, 2019.
- [158] P. Jiang and G. Agrawal, “A linear speedup analysis of distributed deep learning with sparse and quantized communication,” in *Proceedings of the 32nd International Con-*

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- ference on Neural Information Processing Systems, NIPS'18, (Red Hook, NY, USA), p. 2530–2541, Curran Associates Inc., 2018.*
- [159] S. Wang, T. Tuor, T. Salonidis, K. K. Leung, C. Makaya, T. He, and K. Chan, “Adaptive federated learning in resource constrained edge computing systems,” *CoRR*, vol. arXiv:1804.05271, 2019.
- [160] P. Kairouz *et al.*, “Advances and open problems in federated learning,” *CoRR*, vol. arXiv:1912.04977, 2019.
- [161] K. Kuo, P. Thaker, M. Khodak, J. Nguyen, D. Jiang, A. Talwalkar, and V. Smith, “On noisy evaluation in federated hyperparameter tuning,” in *MLSys*, 2023.
- [162] B. Hitaj, G. Ateniese, and F. Perez-Cruz, “Deep models under the GAN: Information leakage from collaborative deep learning,” in *ACM CCS*, 2017.
- [163] Z. Wang, M. Song, Z. Zhang, Y. Song, Q. Wang, and H. Qi, “Beyond inferring class representatives: User-level privacy leakage from federated learning,” in *IEEE INFOCOM*, 2019.
- [164] L. Zhu, Z. Liu, and S. Han, “Deep leakage from gradients,” in *NeurIPS*, vol. 32, 2019.
- [165] L. Melis, C. Song, E. De Cristofaro, and V. Shmatikov, “Exploiting unintended feature leakage in collaborative learning,” in *IEEE S&P*, 2019.
- [166] M. Nasr, R. Shokri, and A. Houmansadr, “Comprehensive privacy analysis of deep learning: Passive and active white-box inference attacks against centralized and federated learning,” in *IEEE S&P*, 2019.
- [167] B. Zhao, K. R. Mopuri, and H. Bilen, “iDLG: Improved deep leakage from gradients,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/2001.02610, 2020.
- [168] A. Wainakh, F. Ventola, T. Müßig, J. Keim, C. Garcia Cordero, E. Zimmer, T. Grube, K. Kersting, and M. Mühlhäuser, “User-level label leakage from gradients in federated learning,” *PETS*, vol. 2022, pp. 227–244, 04 2022.
- [169] J. Deng, Y. Wang, J. Li, C. Wang, C. Shang, H. Liu, S. Rajasekaran, and C. Ding, “TAG: Gradient attack on transformer-based language models,” in *EMNLP*, pp. 3600–3610, 2021.
- [170] D. I. Dimitrov, M. Balunović, N. Konstantinov, and M. Vechev, “Data leakage in federated averaging,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.12395*, 2022. Last revised 1 Nov 2022.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [171] R. Shokri and V. Shmatikov, "Privacy-preserving deep learning," in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGSAC conference on computer and communications security*, pp. 1310–1321, 2015.
- [172] W. Li, F. Milletari, D. Xu, N. Rieke, J. Hancox, W. Zhu, M. Baust, Y. Cheng, S. Ourselin, M. J. Cardoso, and A. Feng, "Privacy-preserving federated brain tumour segmentation," in *Springer MLMI*, 2019.
- [173] M. Abadi, A. Chu, I. Goodfellow, H. B. McMahan, I. Mironov, K. Talwar, and L. Zhang, "Deep learning with differential privacy," in *ACM CCS*, 2016.
- [174] H. B. McMahan, D. Ramage, K. Talwar, and L. Zhang, "Learning differentially private recurrent language models," *CoRR*, vol. abs/1710.06963, 2018.
- [175] W. Wei, L. Liu, M. Loper, K.-H. Chow, M. E. Gursoy, S. Truex, and Y. Wu, "A framework for evaluating gradient leakage attacks in federated learning," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.10397*, 2020. Last revised 23 Apr 2020.
- [176] N. Wu, F. Farokhi, D. Smith, and M. A. Kaafar, "The value of collaboration in convex machine learning with differential privacy," *CoRR*, vol. abs/1906.09679, 2019.
- [177] L. T. Phong, Y. Aono, T. Hayashi, L. Wang, and S. Moriai, "Privacy-preserving deep learning: Revisited and enhanced," in *Springer ATIS*, 2017.
- [178] L. T. Phong, Y. Aono, T. Hayashi, L. Wang, and S. Moriai, "Privacy-preserving deep learning via additively homomorphic encryption," *IEEE TIFS*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1333–1345, 2018.
- [179] C. Zhang, S. Li, J. Xia, W. Wang, F. Yan, and Y. Liu, "Batchcrypt: Efficient homomorphic encryption for cross-silo federated learning," in *Proceedings of the 2020 USENIX Conference on Usenix Annual Technical Conference*, USENIX ATC'20, (USA), USENIX Association, 2020.
- [180] K. Bonawitz, V. Ivanov, B. Kreuter, A. Marcedone, H. B. McMahan, S. Patel, D. Ramage, A. Segal, and K. Seth, "Practical secure aggregation for federated learning on user-held data," in *NIPS PPML Workshop*, 2016.
- [181] D. Reich, A. Todoki, R. Dowsley, M. D. Cock, and A. C. A. Nascimento, "Privacy-preserving classification of personal text messages with secure multi-party computation: An application to hate-speech detection," *CoRR*, vol. abs:1906.02325, 2021.
- [182] S. Wagh, S. Tople, F. Benhamouda, E. Kushilevitz, P. Mittal, and T. Rabin, "FALCON: Honest-majority maliciously secure framework for private deep learning," *PETS*, 2020.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [183] B. Hie, H. Cho, and B. Berger, “Realizing private and practical pharmacological collaboration,” *Science*, vol. 362, no. 6412, pp. 347–350, 2018.
- [184] T. Chen and S. Zhong, “Privacy-preserving backpropagation neural network learning,” *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 20, pp. 1554–1564, Oct 2009.
- [185] H. Zhu, H. Zhang, and Y. Jin, “From federated learning to federated neural architecture search: A survey,” 9 2020.
- [186] D. Froelicher, J. R. Troncoso-Pastoriza, A. Pyrgelis, S. Sav, J. S. Sousa, J.-P. Bossuat, and J.-P. Hubaux, “Scalable privacy-preserving distributed learning,” *PETS*, 2021.
- [187] S. Sav, A. Pyrgelis, J. R. Troncoso-Pastoriza, D. Froelicher, J.-P. Bossuat, J. S. Sousa, and J.-P. Hubaux, “Poseidon: Privacy-preserving federated neural network learning,” in *NDSS*, 2021.
- [188] S. Sav, A. Diaa, A. Pyrgelis, J.-P. Bossuat, and J.-P. Hubaux, “Privacy-preserving federated recurrent neural networks,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/2207.13947, 2022.
- [189] N. Papernot and T. Steinke, “Hyperparameter tuning with renyi differential privacy,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/2110.03620, 2022.
- [190] H. Wang, S. Gao, H. Zhang, W. J. Su, and M. Shen, “Dp-hypo: An adaptive private hyperparameter optimization framework,” 2023.
- [191] H. B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, and B. A. y Arcas, “Federated learning of deep networks using model averaging,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1602.05629, 2016.
- [192] D. Yin, Y. Chen, K. Ramchandran, and P. Bartlett, “Byzantine-robust distributed learning: Towards optimal statistical rates,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1803.01498, 2021.
- [193] X. Chen, T. Chen, H. Sun, Z. S. Wu, and M. Hong, “Distributed training with heterogeneous data: Bridging median- and mean-based algorithms,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/1906.01736, 2019.
- [194] S. Agrawal, S. Sarkar, M. Alazab, P. K. R. Maddikunta, T. R. Gadekallu, and Q.-V. Pham, “Genetic cfl: Hyperparameter optimization in clustered federated learning,” *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, vol. 2021, p. 7156420, Nov 2021.
- [195] C. Briggs, Z. Fan, and P. Andras, “Federated learning with hierarchical clustering of local updates to improve training on non-iid data,” in *2020 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, pp. 1–9, IEEE, 2020.
- [196] Y. Lecun, L. Bottou, G. Orr, and K.-R. Müller, “Efficient backprop,” 08 2000.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [197] R. E. Bellman, *Adaptive Control Processes: A Guided Tour*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1961.
- [198] J. Bergstra and Y. Bengio, “Random search for hyper-parameter optimization,” *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 281–305, 2012.
- [199] J. Mockus, V. Tiesis, and A. Zilinskas, *The application of Bayesian methods for seeking the extremum*, vol. 2, pp. 117–129. 09 2014.
- [200] R. Bardenet and B. Kégl, “Surrogating the surrogate: accelerating gaussian-process-based global optimization with a mixture cross-entropy algorithm,” in *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2010.
- [201] M. Khodak, L. Li, N. Roberts, M.-F. Balcan, and A. Talwalkar, “Weight-sharing beyond neural architecture search: Efficient feature map selection and federated hyperparameter tuning,” in *Proc. 2nd SysML Conf.*, 2019.
- [202] M. Khodak, R. Tu, T. Li, L. Li, N. Balcan, V. Smith, and A. Talwalkar, “Federated hyperparameter tuning: Challenges, baselines, and connections to weight-sharing,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (A. Beygelzimer, Y. Dauphin, P. Liang, and J. W. Vaughan, eds.), 2021.
- [203] H. Zhu and Y. Jin, “Multi-objective evolutionary federated learning,” *CoRR*, vol. arXiv:1812.07478, 2019.
- [204] M. Xu, Y. Zhao, K. Bian, G. Huang, Q. Mei, and X. Liu, “Federated neural architecture search,” *CoRR*, vol. arXiv:2002.06352, 2020.
- [205] C. He, M. Annavaram, and S. Avestimehr, “Towards non-i.i.d. and invisible data with fednas: Federated deep learning via neural architecture search,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/2004.08546, 2021.
- [206] H. Zhu and Y. Jin, “Real-time federated evolutionary neural architecture search,” *CoRR*, vol. arXiv:2003.02793, 2020.
- [207] H. Zhu, H. Zhang, and Y. Jin, “From federated learning to federated neural architecture search: a survey,” *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, vol. 7, 01 2021.
- [208] H. Zhang, M. Zhang, X. Liu, P. Mohapatra, and M. DeLucia, “Fedtune: Automatic tuning of federated learning hyper-parameters from system perspective,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/2110.03061, 2022.
- [209] Z. Dai, B. K. H. Low, and P. Jaillet, “Federated bayesian optimization via thompson sampling,” in *NeurIPS*, 2020.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [210] H. Mostafa, “Robust federated learning through representation matching and adaptive hyper-parameters,” 2020.
- [211] A. Koskela and T. Kulkarni, “Practical differentially private hyperparameter tuning with subsampling,” *CoRR*, vol. arXiv:2301.11989, 2023.
- [212] Z. Xiang, C. Wang, and D. Wang, “How does selection leak privacy: Revisiting private selection and improved results for hyper-parameter tuning,” *CoRR*, vol. abs:2402.13087, 2024.
- [213] S. Mohapatra, S. Sasy, X. He, G. Kamath, and O. Thakkar, “The role of adaptive optimizers for honest private hyperparameter selection,” *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 36, pp. 7806–7813, Jun. 2022.
- [214] Y. Ding and X. Wu, “Revisiting hyperparameter tuning with differential privacy,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/2211.01852, 2022.
- [215] S. Zawad, J. Yi, M. Zhang, C. Li, F. Yan, and Y. He, “Demystifying hyperparameter optimization in federated learning,” 2022.
- [216] T. Stadler, B. Oprisanu, and C. Troncoso, “Synthetic data – anonymisation groundhog day,” 2022.
- [217] M. Giomi, F. Boenisch, C. Wehmeyer, and B. Tasnádi, “A unified framework for quantifying privacy risk in synthetic data,” *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, vol. 2, pp. 312–328, 2023.
- [218] J. Seng, P. Prasad, M. Mundt, D. S. Dhami, and K. Kersting, “Feathers: Federated architecture and hyperparameter search,” *CoRR*, vol. arXiv:2206.12342, 2023.
- [219] M. Keller and K. Sun, “Secure quantized training for deep learning,” in *International Conference on Machine Learning*, pp. 10912–10938, PMLR, 2022.
- [220] E. Hesamifard, H. Takabi, M. Ghasemi, and R. Wright, “Privacy-preserving machine learning as a service,” *PETS*, 2018.
- [221] J. H. Ro, A. T. Suresh, and K. Wu, “FedJAX: Federated learning simulation with JAX,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.02117*, 2021.
- [222] Y. LeCun and C. Cortes, “MNIST handwritten digit database,” 2010.
- [223] G. Cohen, S. Afshar, J. Tapson, and A. Van Schaik, “Emnist: Extending mnist to handwritten letters,” in *2017 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, pp. 2921–2926, IEEE, 2017.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [224] Y. Netzer, T. Wang, A. Coates, A. Bissacco, B. Wu, and A. Ng, “Reading digits in natural images with unsupervised feature learning,” *NIPS*, 2011.
- [225] A. Krizhevsky, “Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images,” *Technical Report, University of Toronto*, 2012.
- [226] Q. Li, Y. Diao, Q. Chen, and B. He, “Federated learning on non-iid data silos: An experimental study,” in *2022 IEEE 38th International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE)*, pp. 965–978, 2022.
- [227] J. H. Cheon, A. Kim, M. Kim, and Y. Song, “Homomorphic encryption for arithmetic of approximate numbers,” in *ASIACRYPT*, 2017.
- [228] C. Mouchet, J. Troncoso-Pastoriza, J.-P. Bossuat, and J.-P. Hubaux, “Multiparty homomorphic encryption from ring-learning-with-errors,” *Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*, vol. 2021, no. 4, pp. 291–311, 2021.
- [229] R. Goldschmidt, “Applications of division by convergence,” m.sc. dissertation. M.I.T., 1964.
- [230] J. H. Cheon, D. Kim, and D. Kim, “Efficient homomorphic comparison methods with optimal complexity,” in *Advances in Cryptology – ASIACRYPT 2020* (S. Moriai and H. Wang, eds.), (Cham), pp. 221–256, Springer International Publishing, 2020.
- [231] G. Marino, “Federated dbscan,” bachelor’s thesis, Università di Pisa, Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell’Informazione, 2022.
- [232] “Lattigo v5.” Online: <https://github.com/tuneinsight/lattigo>, Nov. 2023. (Accessed: 2023-11-11).
- [233] M. Albrecht *et al.*, “Homomorphic Encryption Security Standard,” tech. rep., HomomorphicEncryption.org, 2018.
- [234] L. Muñoz-González, K. T. Co, and E. C. Lupu, “Byzantine-robust federated machine learning through adaptive model averaging,” 2019.
- [235] P. Blanchard, E. M. El Mhamdi, R. Guerraoui, and J. Stainer, “Machine learning with adversaries: Byzantine tolerant gradient descent,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (I. Guyon, U. V. Luxburg, S. Bengio, H. Wallach, R. Fergus, S. Vishwanathan, and R. Garnett, eds.), vol. 30, Curran Associates, Inc., 2017.
- [236] D. Yin, Y. Chen, R. Kannan, and P. Bartlett, “Byzantine-robust distributed learning: Towards optimal statistical rates,” in *Proceedings of the 35th International Conference on*

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- Machine Learning* (J. Dy and A. Krause, eds.), vol. 80 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pp. 5650–5659, PMLR, 10–15 Jul 2018.
- [237] X. Cao, M. Fang, J. Liu, and N. Z. Gong, “Fltrust: Byzantine-robust federated learning via trust bootstrapping,” in *28th Annual Network and Distributed System Security Symposium, NDSS 2021, virtually, February 21-25, 2021*, The Internet Society, 2021.
- [238] C. Dwork, N. Kohli, and D. Mulligan, “Differential privacy in practice: Expose your epsilons!,” *Journal of Privacy and Confidentiality*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2019.
- [239] J. Abowd, R. Ashmead, G. Simson, D. Kifer, P. Leclerc, A. Machanavajjhala, and W. Sexton, “Census topdown: Differentially private data, incremental schemas, and consistency with public knowledge,” *US Census Bureau*, 2019.
- [240] R. Shokri, M. Stronati, C. Song, and V. Shmatikov, “Membership inference attacks against machine learning models,” in *IEEE S&P*, 2017.
- [241] V. Feldman, “Does learning require memorization? a short tale about a long tail,” 2021.
- [242] L. Wang, K. Huang, K. Sun, W. Wang, C. Tian, L. Xie, and Q. Gu, “Unlock with your heart: Heartbeat-based authentication on commercial mobile phones,” *Proc. ACM Interact. Mob. Wearable Ubiquitous Technol.*, vol. 2, 9 2018.
- [243] C. Hegde, H. R. Prabhu, D. Sagar, P. D. Shenoy, K. Venugopal, and L. M. Patnaik, “Heartbeat biometrics for human authentication,” *Signal, Image and Video Processing*, vol. 5, pp. 485–493, 2011.
- [244] J. Jordon, L. Szpruch, F. Houssiau, M. Bottarelli, G. Cherubin, C. Maple, S. N. Cohen, and A. Weller, “Synthetic data – what, why and how?,” 2022.
- [245] Y. Ang, Q. Huang, Y. Bao, A. K. H. Tung, and Z. Huang, “Tsgbench: Time series generation benchmark,” 2023.
- [246] J. W. Kim, K. Edemacu, J. S. Kim, Y. D. Chung, and B. Jang, “A survey of differential privacy-based techniques and their applicability to location-based services,” *Computers & Security*, vol. 111, p. 102464, 2021.
- [247] M. Gong, Y. Xie, K. Pan, K. Feng, and A. Qin, “A survey on differentially private machine learning [review article],” *IEEE Computational Intelligence Magazine*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 49–64, 2020.
- [248] F. Harder, K. Adamczewski, and M. Park, “Differentially private mean embeddings with random features (DP-MERF) for simple & practical synthetic data generation,” *CoRR*, vol. abs/2002.11603, 2020.

D2.1 Privacy Preserving Feature Selection, Classification and Federated Learning

- [249] A. Anesiadou, M. Makridis, B. Ciuffo, and K. Mattas, “Open acc database.” [Online]. Available from: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/9702c950-c80f-4d2f-982f-44d06ea0009f>, 2020.
- [250] J. Snoek, H. Larochelle, and R. P. Adams, “Practical bayesian optimization of machine learning algorithms,” in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (F. Pereira, C. J. C. Burges, L. Bottou, and K. Q. Weinberger, eds.), vol. 25, Curran Associates, Inc., 2012.
- [251] L. Lamport, R. Shostak, and M. Pease, “The byzantine generals problem,” *ACM Transactions on Programming Languages and Systems (TOPLAS)*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 382–401, 1982.
- [252] Y. Meidan, M. Bohadana, Y. Mathov, Y. Mirsky, A. Shabtai, D. Breitenbacher, and Y. Elovici, “N-baiot—network-based detection of iot botnet attacks using deep autoencoders,” *IEEE Pervasive Computing*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 12–22, 2018.